

GAME-ER

April 2026

D4.4

Mapping of Actors

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GLOSSARY AND ABBREVIATIONS

Agence Française de Développement	AFD
Opérateur de compétences de la culture, des industries créatives, des médias, de la communication, des télécommunications, du sport, du tourisme, des loisirs et du divertissement	AFDAS
Agence Française du Jeu Vidéo	AFJV
Associação de Produtores de Videojogos Portugueses	APVP
Opérateur de compétences des services financiers, du conseil et des activités numériques	ATLAS
Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (région administrative)	AURA
Business-to-Business	B2B
Business-to-Consumer	B2C
Banque Publique d'Investissement (Bpifrance)	BPI
Brno University of Technology	BUT
Centro de Acolhimento de Empresas Tecnológicas	CAET
Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	CDE
Contrat à Durée Indéterminée	CDI
Crédit d'Impôt Jeu Vidéo	CIJV
Cité de l'Image en Mouvement (Annecy)	CITIA
Câmara Municipal do Fundão	CMF
Centre National du Cinéma et de l'Image Animée	CNC
Contrat d'Objectifs Emploi-Formation	COEF
Dundee Contemporary Arts gallery	DCA
Direction Générale des Entreprises	DGE
Duncan of Jordanstone College of Art & Design	DJCAD
Direction Régionale des Affaires Culturelles	DRAC
Direction Régionale de l'Économie, de l'Emploi, du Travail et des Solidarités	DREETS
European Commission	EC

École Nationale du Jeu et des Médias Interactifs Numériques	ENJMIN
European Union	EU
Federação Portuguesa de Desportos Eletrónicos	FPDE
Fonds Unique Interministériel	FUI
Game Developers Conference (San Francisco)	GDC
General Data Protection Regulation	GDPR
Global Game Jam	GGJ
Île-de-France (région administrative)	IDF
Instituto de Emprego e Formação Profissional	IEFP
International Game Developers Association	IGDA
Italian Interactive Digital Entertainment Association	IIDEA
Castelo Branco Polytechnic	IPCB
Independent Workers of Great Britain	IWGB
Level Up Lab	LUL
Master Audiovisuel	MAV
Marché International du Film d'Animation (Annecy)	MIFA
Masaryk University	MUNI
National Health Service	NHS
Officine Grandi Riparazioni	OGR
Opérateur de Compétences	OPCO
Programme de Développement International	PDI
Qualité de Vie au Travail	QVT
Régie Autonome des Transports Parisiens	RATP
Société à Responsabilité Limitée	SARL
Société Coopérative d'Intérêt Collectif	SCIC
Société Coopérative et Participative	SCOP
Syndicat des Éditeurs de Logiciels de Loisirs	SELL
Société d'Économie Mixte	SEM
Syndicat National du Jeu Vidéo	SNJV
Portuguese Society for Video Game Science	SPCV
Société Publique Locale	SPL
Secondary School of Art and Design	SŠUD
Syndicat des Travailleurs du Jeu Vidéo	STJV
Universidade da Beira Interior	UBI
Virtual Production in Real Time	VIPRE
Work Package	WP

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents findings from the **GAME-ER** project, specifically the findings relating to **Task 4.4 - Mapping of actors**. **T4.4** employs qualitative methodology based on social network analysis and prior research on video game production ecosystems. Building on previous deliverables from **WP4**, this task aimed to further map and analyse actors and collective actions within each of the six **GAME-ER** clusters. Furthermore, the goal was to explore and visualize the relationships between cluster actors. The empirical research took the form of mapping interview sessions conducted with the cluster representatives. Based on interview transcripts and individual actor maps created during these sessions, research teams created final actor maps, which were confirmed during a workshop with cluster representatives. Beyond mapping the various actors involved in each cluster, including developers, publishers, service providers as well as educational institutions, local governments, and cultural intermediaries, the task also used the collected empirical evidence to describe each cluster's relation to the global video game production value chain – a concept, which addresses how (monetary) value is extracted by actors who do not produce games themselves but participate, for example, as publishers, distributors, or intellectual property owners.

The structure of the report reflects the comparative nature of the project. Each of the six chapters is dedicated to one of the regional clusters, offering an overview of the key cluster actors, collective actions, cluster perimeter, and value chain. These chapters draw on data collected during mapping sessions and workshops.

By focusing on regions often overlooked in digital innovation research, the **GAME-ER** project contributes to a better understanding of the driving forces behind the dynamism of a local video game industry and, as a result, a more inclusive understanding of where and how creative industries can succeed in Europe. This report specifically analyses the actors and relationships key to the functioning of each of the cluster, providing concrete findings about the arrangements and logistics sustaining the six **GAME-ER** clusters.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Overview

The Gaming Clusters Across Multiple European Regions (**GAME-ER**) project aims to explore the emergence, development, and sustainability of video game clusters, with a specific focus on local and regional clusters. The project will develop a comprehensive Interactive Methodological Toolkit, featuring policy and practical recommendations designed to assist local and national policymakers in establishing or enhancing Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) clusters within their regions or cities. Existing research often focuses on clusters outside Europe or within major metropolitan areas like Helsinki or Hamburg. However, **GAME-ER** addresses a critical gap by studying the dynamics of smaller, regional clusters, which play a significant role in driving innovation, growth, and regional cohesion. The project's core component involves a comparative analysis of six clusters in five European countries—France, the Czech Republic, Italy, Scotland, and Portugal. These clusters were chosen for their diverse levels of maturity and unique characteristics, including concentrations of creative talent and companies. In addition to this comparative study, **GAME-ER** will conduct a Europe-wide analysis of the spatial organization of the video games industry, specifically focusing on local and regional ecosystems. This research, conducted in collaboration with policymakers and industry stakeholders, will guide the formulation of actionable recommendations using a participatory approach. **GAME-ER** brings together 15 partners from 9 countries, encompassing expertise in social sciences, humanities, policymaking, business, and innovation.

1.2 Objectives of the Deliverable

D4.4 aims to provide a closer look at the actors (meaning developers, publishers, service providers as well as educational institutions, local governments, and cultural intermediaries) and their relationships within each of the six **GAME-ER** clusters. Building on previous WP4 tasks, **T4.4** both revisits previously collected empirical data for **D4.1** (De Paoli et al. 2025) and **D4.2** but also draws on new interview sessions with a goal to visualize each cluster as a map of actors and their main activities. Industrial cluster definitions often emphasise the geographical concentration of different types of actors, including “*specialised suppliers, service providers, firms in related industries, and associated institutions (e.g., universities, standards agencies, trade associations)*” (Porter 2000, 16).

The goals of the deliverable are thus twofold:

- First, we aim to identify the actors involved in the six **GAME-ER** clusters and to analyse their relationships both within the local ecosystems and with key external actors.
- Second, by understanding the types of actors present in the **GAME-ER** ecosystems, we also want to assess the relative position of a given cluster in the value chain. Both of these tasks are achieved through qualitative methods described in the next section.

2 MAPPING OF ACTORS: PURPOSE, METHOD, AND SCOPE

The contemporary video game industry features different types of actors from developers to publishers, distribution platforms, service providers, and outsourcing companies. Additionally, various cultural intermediaries, such as trade show organisers or journalists (Browne and Schram 2021; Gislam et al. 2025; Perks et al. 2019; Whitson et al. 2021), and educational institutions can be also considered part of the wider video game production ecosystem (Harvey 2019). Given the highly globalised nature of video game production (Kerr 2017), it is relevant to look at how these different actors are represented geographically in clusters or larger regions. Game scholars have in this regard pointed out the historical dominance of the United States (U.S) and Japan (Consalvo 2006) as well as the peripheral positions of other countries and regions, who often act as subcontractors or outsourcing partners to productions led by studios and publishers located in more central locations (Bulut 2020; Ozimek 2019; 2021; Švelch 2021; Wong 2024). In this regard, the mapping of actors can also expose the power dynamics in production networks and provide insights into the issue of value chains as illustrated in an example from literature shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Visualisation of production networks and the connections between various actors (Johns 2006, 164)

Value chain as a concept addresses how value is captured in the production network, highlighting the fact that only a portion of the revenue (or retail price) stays with the video game manufacturer; as little as 20% in the 2000s (Johns 2006) although value chains are always evolving due to the emergence of new distribution channels such as Steam (see Thorhaug 2023). Publishers, distributors, retailers as well as intellectual property owners extract value from video game products, contributing to complex production networks. Historically, work-for-hire and outsourcing take advantage of cheaper labour costs in the Global South and other peripheral locations, allowing companies in the centre to lower production costs, but still keep their profits if a game proves to be successful.

2.1 Methodological Framework

This task employs a qualitative methodology to provide a deeper understanding of the actors and their relationships in the six GAME-ER clusters. GAME-ER priority is to go beyond merely stating a connection between actors or their activities, but to provide additional detail about the nature and form of these relationships. In this regard, the T4.4 follows the previous tasks in this work package, especially T4.1 and partly also T4.2, which were based on qualitative analysis. Similar to T4.1, empirical data were collected in interview sessions. Compared to the semi-structured interviews from D4.1 (De Paoli et al. 2025), whose interview guides were based on the analytical grid as presented in D3.1 (Paris and De Paoli 2025), D4.4 uses a relatively novel methodology inspired by prior scholarship on video game ecosystems (Lehtonen et al. 2020; 2022), see also Figure 2.

Figure 2: Example of a map of actors from prior video game industry research (Lehtonen, Schilli, and Harviainen 2022, 628).

This approach consists of several mapping sessions for each cluster during which respondents visualise the cluster ecosystem and relevant external actors as a map. During map creation, which can be done by hand on paper or using software tools like Miro or Microsoft Whiteboard, we use key aspects of social network analysis (Wasserman and Faust 1994) as guiding principles for how the maps are organised. However, instead of calculating indicators like centrality based on ties

between nodes in a social network, we asked our respondents about their subjective perceptions of centrality within a given cluster. This subjectiveness is both a strength and a weakness of the approach, allowing researchers to highlight and analyse this perceived centrality, which might be more formative for a given cluster than centrality based on quantitative measurements. At the same time, this embedded subjectiveness can obscure actors with lower status or visibility within a cluster. We try to limit these risks by recruiting respondents from different parts of the ecosystems and with different backgrounds.

The novel aspect of our methodology lies in the creation of a comprehensive map, which synthesises several maps drawn by our respondents (c.f. Lehtonen et al. 2020; 2022). This additional step allows researchers to at least partially account for respondents' subjective perceptions of the cluster and its actors. The size and diversity of the sample of respondents still affects the representativeness of the comprehensive map. The comprehensive map is then further validated during a workshop session with representatives from the cluster. This step serves to align the map and researchers' interpretation of the interview data with the shared group opinions among the cluster representatives.

The map is only one of the outcomes of the qualitative analysis. A written analysis presented in conjunction with the comprehensive map is equally important and provides further details about the actors and relationships shown on the map. This written analysis again draws on the analytical grid from **D3.1** and presents the findings in a structure informed by the grid. Based on the feedback from the European Commission, we also discuss the notion of value chain.

Based on prior literature (Davies 2024; Lehtonen et al. 2022; Maiuga 2025a; 2025b; Young 2022) and findings from the previous **WP4** deliverables, we also pay attention to collective actions such as events in the maps. These are not actors in a strict sense, but events like conferences, festivals, or game jams which serve as important connecting points for the cluster actors, who might use the events as opportunities for meeting each other, to promote their games or who might come together to organise these events.

We organise the actors into three larger groups based on their involvement in game production: (1) video game industry, (2) educational institutions, and (3) cultural intermediaries. The first two groups are relatively easy to classify. The video game industry covers companies involved in making games across various parts of the value chain including development, publishing, distribution, or outsourcing. Educational institutions provide formalised training at various levels, including high schools and universities. Cultural intermediaries is a more diverse group of actors, which are connected to video games, but usually do not fall under the traditional definition of the video game industry and the aforementioned roles. Game scholars have recently drawn to these actors, which include trade fairs, co-working spaces, or the specialised press, and their undervalued contributions to the video game industry (Browne and Schram 2021; Gislam et al. 2025; Parker et al. 2018). In our analysis, we use this category to highlight the presence of actors outside of the main groups of developers and educators.

2.2 Order of Chapters

The remainder of this deliverable is organised into dedicated chapters. Each chapter provides an in-depth analysis of the actors and their relationships per cluster. Methodological aspects of the data collection performed in each cluster are also provided in each of the chapters, since they present differences related to the local context, and conduction of the interviewing work. Indeed, like for the previous **D4.1**, **D4.2**, and **D4.3**, each chapter was written independently by a different partner, and as such, elements of the narrative, as well as some of the reporting, may differ. However, each chapter presents a similar structure and methodology provided by the task leader. The order of presentation is the following:

- **Dundee** (Scotland, UK)
- **Turin** (Italy)
- **Brno** (Czechia)
- **Lyon** (France)
- **Bordeaux** (France)
- **Fundão** (Portugal)

3 DUNDEE

3.1 Overview of the Cluster

In common with the other **GAME-ER** clusters, Dundee has been explored in considerable detail in previous deliverables. Dundee’s prominence in the history and present of the United Kingdom’s game development industry is remarkable as it is a smaller regional city with a modest population. This history has contributed to the city’s designation as the UK’s only UNESCO City of Design. Key factors in the city’s history have contributed to the strength of this game development cluster, such as the presence of the Timex factory in the 1980s which manufactured the ZX Spectrum home computer, and the foundational demoscene related to this local infrastructure. A complex set of socio-technical and historical dynamics formed the environment in which studios such as DMX Design and Denki, along with worldwide hit games such as *Lemmings* (DMA Design 1991) and *Grand Theft Auto* (DMA Design 1997), could arise.

There is also however a sense that this history casts a long shadow: *“...it would be ‘Lemmings’, it would be ‘GTA’. Let’s get it to five or six instead of the same few from 20 years ago. There are some huge hits out of Scotland, like really great products that are built here. Studios doing really amazing work, but the press still talks about ‘Lemmings’ and ‘GTA’ so it’s a bit of a shame.”* (studio lead). Ongoing investment and support are needed to continue the strong record of game development in the city. Studios within the cluster range widely in size, from branches of major companies such as Rockstar Dundee, to SME mobile developers such as Ninja Kiwi and Outplay Entertainment, and independent collectives such as Biome and Very Evil Demons. **GAME-ER** research, specifically **D4.2** (De Paoli et al. 2025b) has identified emerging dynamics such as recent reinvestment in the city by game company founders (such as Chroma Ventures and the Water’s Edge building housing technology organisations and virtual production studios) and significant investment in cross-sector R&D (such as the CoSTAR Realtime Lab). Ongoing importance for many previously identified actors was reflected both in this research, and emerging developments demonstrate multiplier effects, such as a £20m UK Government Local Innovation Partnership Fund investment in the Tay Cities region including Dundee (with the bed being led by Abertay University) aimed at support for the local creative industries and design-led R&D.

A previous deliverable **D4.2** has described the high per capita concentration of game studios in the city through spatial mapping techniques, along with related ecosystemic factors such as the walkable ‘20-minute cluster’ that is used to describe the close proximity of many studios (De Paoli et al. 2025); in fact, the spatial mapping found that in reality the density of studios was even higher and that Dundee could be described as a ‘5-minute cluster’. The games industry in contemporary Dundee is characterised by high levels of informal activity afforded by this geographic distribution, as well as organised events such as the Arcadia festival, Game Talks Live and Hubworld meetups, and collaborative activities such as the Drop in and Play demonstrators. Emerging activity has sought to bridge formal and informal activity, such as the *Big Telly Jam* at Water’s Edge. Occurring in 2026 as a collaboration between Creative Scotland, CoSTAR, Immersive Arts UK, Biome Collective, UNESCO City of Design Dundee and Arcadia festival, the event brings CoSTAR R&D on games and virtual production into proximity with wider creative industries actors in the city through

approachable workshops and demonstrators. The goal is to demystify the technology and engage creatives across Scotland. These events show that there is an active mix of activities between industry, cultural and educational actors in the city, the description of which is a core goal of this task. Key educational institutions providing core and complementary skills teaching for digital games include Abertay University, which is often cited in this context due to offering some of the most well-established game production degrees in the world, Duncan of Jordanstone College of Art & Design (DJCAD) which has a history of creative computing offerings, and Dundee & Angus College which graduates and articulates students with game development skillsets and leads on esports education in the city.

3.2 Data Collection

The present task, focused on identifying key actors comprising the cluster, provided the opportunity to sample a wider sectoral composition of interviewees than in previous research. The subjective viewpoints on the cluster and its dynamics were visualised through mapping and analysis work that draws on actor-network concepts. The importance of informal networks and activities has been repeatedly emphasised in **GAME-ER** findings to date (De Paoli et al. 2025), and this actor mapping study design had significant potential to add complexity to the evolving picture of the Dundee games development cluster. Through identifying new modes of ‘clustering’ beyond the frame of the games industry itself, it became possible to address dimensions and emergent issues that were indicated in previous research but in need of more in-depth research to properly characterise. Digital games tend to sit between or across the areas of technology and creative arts or cultural production (Yodovich et al. 2025), and creating games requires collaboration between skilled workers from a wide range of disciplines. The industry itself is changing both due to new technologies and socio-economic transformations (Dubois and Weststar 2021; Whitson 2018). The role of creative intermediaries can be particularly important in this environment (Parker and Perks 2021), although in practice such activity can face challenges with funding and sustainability “...you get the big expos that are really commercial that are really easily funded. And then you get the ones that are more artistic that are really hard ‘cause they don’t appeal to arts funders, and they don’t appeal to games funders, and so – but they’re making a valuable contribution.” (educator) The team accordingly took a purposive approach to recruiting participants from cultural organisations, alongside game industry and education professionals within the city who have formed the mainstay of our samples in previous deliverables.

This work highlighted both opportunities and barriers to closer collaboration among actors in Dundee, and complex relations with cultural intermediaries emerged as an important element for understanding the full range of games-related activity in the city. For one respondent active within cultural institutions, but with a game development skillset, “a lot of people don’t see games as art... sometimes people who do other types of creative practice see it as a quite a... corporate economic field... historically it’s been siloed.” (independent developer). In spite of this view, the respondent was an example of dynamic games work across sectors. A self-taught game creator with an interest in social impact games, they currently work in the Scottish government and are involved in NGO Creative Dundee. Their practice includes a serious or applied game that involved close collaboration

with legal and policy experts at national and international levels and dealt with complex legal themes. This educational and career path indicates emerging links that complicate the concepts of formal and informal game economies that have previously guided analysis of the Dundee cluster. Here, there is a connection between a less formal educational pathway, and highly formalised policy and cultural sectors. While far from a typical career path, the presence of such an actor in the city speaks to some of Dundee's unique characteristics, and the expansion of game-related skillsets into wider parts of the economy. This individual is not an isolated case: Dundee has a number of studios and independent developers working in similar serious games spaces whilst also creating/supporting the production of entertainment focussed IP.

Another junior developer outlined informal engagement with game engines as an important set of stepping stones that led them to Abertay University and eventually their current employment, leading from early attendance at programming events like CoderDojo, then experimentation in *Minecraft*, Scratch, HTML and GameMaker. Individuals with such a range of capability and background have been a notable feature in previous deliverables, suggesting the adaptability of game industry creatives and professionals in the cluster across periods of significant change in prevailing economic, cultural and technological conditions.

Researchers conducted ten semi-structured mapping interviews between September 2025 and March 2026 to achieve the goals of **T4.4** of the project. A purposive sampling approach was used to supplement and enhance the extensive interview corpus gathered in previous research, and limited snowball sampling extended this approach. The sample included a broad cross-section of game and cultural workers including senior game studio leadership, members of independent game production collectives, junior professionals, cultural intermediaries, and educators. Interviews were conducted either in-person or online, and actor mapping was hand-drawn, or in most cases facilitated by the Miro platform. This enabled respondents to directly place actors in the map in relation to their own central position and dynamically move their relative proximity in response to the interview progression and emergent discussion. Towards the end of the sampling process, an interview was conducted with a representative of the Dundee & Angus College, a key educational institution in the city; while this data was gathered after the main mapping work took place, we have included key insights from the interview itself here. Interviews were then transcribed and the research materials stored in the secure institutional repository.

3.3 Actor Mapping

Researchers met to compile the individual maps into an initial draft comprehensive map, following the methodology in Lehtonen et al. (2020, 2022). This initial exercise was formalised by coding the corpus through social network analysis (Wasserman and Faust 1994), with the data visualised in Gephi Lite. A validation session, led by two researchers with domain-specific expertise, added precision to the nodes and edges, thereby comprehensively visualising the network across our data. Node types that were identified in this process included Company, Organisation, Event, Game, Platform, Technology, Educational Institution, Educational Organisation, Building, Person, Union, Financial Institution and Organisation (other). Edge types of indicative of uni- or bidirectional

3.3.1 Key Actors and Features

As noted, many of the key actors in the final map have been discussed in previous research, such as major games studios including Rockstar Dundee, Outplay Entertainment, 4J, Tag, Pocket Sized Hands, and others. In terms of educational institutions, for example, a senior game industry figure noted: *“Obviously Abertay’s fed into that in recent years by their courses and stuff, but back when I got started, everybody I knew had a knockoff Spectrum from Timex. They really did. My dad brought one home in a plastic bag from the pub. It was just a computer in a black plastic bag with a manual, and that was it. And I sat down and plugged it in and started learning to programme myself.”* (studio head). Experienced industry figures with established histories in the cluster described a formalising tendency (Keogh 2023; Švelch and Sotamaa 2021) in the educational pathways required for new and innovative games production to occur in Dundee – a story told in greater detail in the historical perspective of **D4.3**. This involved complex interplays between game companies (each with their own goals and requirements) and the local colleges and universities.

With this said, a greater breadth of formal and informal elements came into better focus through the work on **T4.4**, including a sense of tensions within the cluster articulated by the respondents. The mapping process demonstrated different ideas of proximity and distance, how various actors viewed the infrastructure enabling their work, and how the games industry is situated in relation to the wider creative industries activity in the city and cluster. One key set of actors are NGO, social enterprises and community organisations acting as cultural intermediaries, including Creative Dundee – an organisation that has been mentioned in previous work, but can be discussed in more detail here. Creative Dundee is a social enterprise and registered charity. The organisation’s name originates in a grassroots arts and culture blog highlighting local creative practitioners founded by current director Gillian Easson in 2008. The contemporary organisation consists of a small core team supported by wider community and partners within Dundee, including Creative Scotland and Dundee City Council.

Creative Dundee has been both active within the city, feeding into policy deliberations such as Dundee’s Creative Industries Strategy, and also able to scale to work with national partners such as the UK’s National Health Service (NHS). Creative Dundee’s activities include policy advocacy, cultural and social networking events, and addressing structural issues in the city for wider creative industries, such as the need for activity hubs and physical spaces that are still recovering after the COVID pandemic: *“we sit way more on the social creative excellence bit. That’s the emergent systems, the grassroots, the activists, the experimental, the collaborative. That’s where I often find the challenge is; how to straddle.”* (Creative Dundee board member) Creative Dundee has also engaged in research through collaborations with the Scottish Parliament and the NHS, contributing to Dundee’s engagement with UK-wide problems around social innovation R&D (The Audience Agency 2026). Creative Dundee respondents noted that in relation to formal aspects of the video game cluster there were significant gaps between sectors: *“I think that for video games, some of that is contained within the academic world that can be then quite separate from community and grassroots spaces or conversations. What research is happening in there, how that research is influenced by communities, and strengthening that relationship.”* (Creative Dundee board member).

This indicates that educational institutions are viewed as cultural intermediaries in their own right within the cluster, but also that there are issues with how this mediation happens in practice that could be addressed with more work towards effective communication and collaboration. Creative Dundee has made active steps to make academic work accessible to the city by platforming academics at their public engagement events, including their popular Pecha Kucha lightning talks event (32 events over 15 years) which are recorded and made available online for free.

Creative Scotland is a national public body which supports cultural and creative sectors across all parts of Scotland through distributing funds from the Scottish Government and National Lottery. Founded in 2010, the organisation's remit includes screen media, and support for games and immersive experiences has steadily increased as part of the portfolio. Creative Scotland supported the UK-wide Indielab Games accelerator, and in 2026 supported the development of *Grease Trap '99* (James Muirhead 2026) by Abertay graduate and independent developer James Muirhead. Creative Scotland support has also been important to Dundonian cultural venues that host games events: *"I remember Creative Scotland traditionally being very, very important here, especially for things like Drop in and Play where kind of Creative Scotland funding goes into the DCA and the DCA is feeding back in, is a big part of the ecosystem."* (independent Developer). Drop in and Play is a games showcase event that is hosted by Dundee Contemporary Arts gallery (DCA) three times a year, and sponsored by Ninja Kiwi, has, in recent years, become one of the city's main regular public facing games events. The event allows the public to engage directly with developers and their games through live play, play discussions and educational talks. More broadly, Creative Scotland joined with other cultural organisations across the four UK nations to support the Immersive Arts network, a research project and funding body which has supported the development of 17 Scottish projects in its latest round, including several based in Dundee such as Biome Collective's locative game project based on football culture *The Game* (Immersive Arts 2026).

A key educational actor in the cluster is Dundee & Angus College. The college is a further education institution formed in 2013 through the merger of Dundee College and Angus College. The institution offers vocational, technical and higher education pathways across two locations in Dundee and the neighbouring town of Arbroath, with a strong regional focus and orientation to widening educational access. Dundee & Angus offer a unified approach to digital games education under a computing and creative media banner, including a free 12-week learning programme called The Games Academy, certificates and diplomas in Computer Games Development (which have the opportunity to articulate into university degrees such as those offered by Abertay and Edinburgh Napier) and recently a BA (Hons) in Esports and Creative Industries.

The significance of platform developer YoYo Games, established in 2007, also emerged during mapping. YoYo Games is known for developing GameMaker (including its latest version GameMaker Studio 2), which uses visual and accessible scripting tools to facilitate the creation of games with a focus on 2D genres. This accessibility has been a success for the developer. Game Maker has been used in school and university curricula around the world, as well as being the engine behind high-profile games such as *Undertale*, *Deltarune*, *Hyper Light Drifter* and *Hotline Miami*: *"the overall philosophy of the company and like the tool has always been making games for everybody... anybody can pick this up, learn quickly or prototype quickly."* (junior developer).

Previous **GAME-ER** research has discussed game development collectives as part of an ‘ecosystemic push’ in Dundee (De Paoli et al. 2025), which bring together artistic and experimental digital media practices with game development. As discussed in previous work, Biome Collective is an established group bridging games and arts through creative practice and event organisation such as the Arcadia Festival and have been identified as part of the cluster’s historical sociotechnical evolution. Their position in the cluster was recognised by a senior commercial developer, albeit with a sense of distance conveyed between the profit-driven and creative aspects of game development: *“Those are the guys in the Biome Collective. And what I find really interesting about them is that whole art approach... even though it’s less commercial, it’s really interesting that they’ve taken that approach... those guys do really interesting stuff that I couldn’t. There’s no way I could do it, I don’t have that view on the world. But the stuff they do is really interesting and it’s great they’re doing it.”* (studio lead). The tension between commercial and cultural game development within the cluster is made clear here, whilst there is mutual recognition of the value of each approach, there remain barriers to cross-pollination between companies and organisations working in these two spaces.

Also emerging more recently in Dundee is another game development collective called Very Evil Demons which operates with an owner-worker flat hierarchical structure. Currently with a smaller membership, this collective grew from Abertay graduates with connections to studios such as Pocket Sized Hands (*“kind of our historical context”*), that has conducted work-for-hire activity for a range of clients and affirms pro-labour philosophy in their organisational structure and approach. Through interview and mapping processes, the two collectives evinced an aligned ethos (and some common membership), orienting themselves in close proximity in the mapping process: *“Biome is pretty close to us actually, we have a few members who go as – are members of Biome as well as being members of Very Evil Demons, so there’s definitely a lot of cross over between us.”* (independent developer).

3.3.2 Collective Actions

The Dundee cluster’s complex history has led to a network of key actors working across a range of sectors, which distinguishes it from the more recent and focused policy and governmental efforts evidenced in e.g. Fundão as there is a distinctive mix of formal and informal actors that have arisen over this time, including senior professionals and business leaders with strong influence over the cluster. Collective organisation for Dundee’s games industry has historically been routed through prominent studios or companies, such as the historical exemplars of DMA Design or Realtime Worlds: *“for the cluster of Dundee, maybe three, four steady ships that are always there, always doing stuff? Then outside of that, all of these people jumping off into lifeboats to go and form their own things? But these steady ships just keep people employed, right? So, we can’t just support new people starting new things. If we don’t have those bigger clusters – bigger companies, then there’s nothing to stabilise the industry round. If you lose them, you actually lose the industry; it will go and it’ll never recover from this location.”* (studio lead).

Connected to this point, in **D4.2** (De Paoli et al. 2025) evidence was presented to illustrate how the capacity of the local industry to “recover” after the closure of Real Time Worlds such as Ruffian

Games (since acquired to become Rockstar Dundee), its biggest company and most significant pole for attracting funding, allowed for the cluster to emerge. Since then, as the quote infers, some organisations have cemented themselves as key anchors for the cluster including Abertay University and some of the bigger companies outlined by the respondent (Gómez-Urrego and O'Regan, forthcoming). The mapping activity has also addressed this point, as several respondents described these organisations as playing a central role in the cluster even when their specific company or organisation may not be connected to them. The capacity for the cluster to recover from significant downturns would then be distributed among the different players in the field, both large companies-organisations that anchor the cluster across time, as well as smaller collectives, cooperatives and startups that allow the industry to diversify, expand, generate alternative business and relational models, and retain talent. In the contemporary cluster, respondents affirmed that companies such as 4J and Rockstar Dundee provide important centres of gravity for the games industry. This relation was however framed differently by independent developers when compared to the quote from the studio lead above, as more of a responsibility arising from historical roots in the cluster that all shared: *“the companies have a responsibility to the Dundee games space to feed into it. I feel like because they all benefit from it – Ninja Kiwi, Outplay, Hyper Luminal, Tag – all these names that everyone is familiar with and has heard for a long time, everybody has history here and it’s important that we maintain that history.”* (independent developer).

Links between industry and educational or cultural actors can create lasting value. Previous research has discussed Abertay’s DARE Academy, a central talent showcase that evolved from the earlier DARE to be Digital events. Dundee-based developers and Abertay lecturers often provide educational talks and discussions at the events. With support from industry actors, the event fosters direct connections between students and working developers. The event has key connections to Biome Collective, with the studio Bit Loom (themselves part of the collective) being previous DARE winners. Current and former DARE teams have exhibited at the Drop in and Play events held at the Dundee Contemporary Arts gallery and event space and supported by mobile studio Ninja Kiwi and the UK Games Fund.

Links between Abertay University and industry actors are also facilitated by a third-year capstone project module called Professional Projects that forms part of the university’s undergraduate game development programmes. Multidisciplinary student teams create game prototypes in response to broad creative briefs set by commercial game development studios from the cluster and beyond. The individual mentors who set the briefs and give feedback to the student teams are often, but not exclusively, Abertay alumni who frequently value this experience as a way to stay in touch with the institution.

Between 12 and 18 client studios participate annually; the composition of the group shifts over time but encompasses a core of diverse organisations with studios based in the cluster. This includes Rockstar Games, 4J Studios, Outplay Entertainment, Team Terrible, Ninja Kiwi, Stormcloud Games and Pocketsized Hands. Hyperluminal Games and Konglomerate Games have previously participated. Additionally, studios out with the cluster such as The Chinese Room, Climax Studios, Frontier Developments, FuturLab, Summer Eternal and SpiltMilk Studios are or have been involved. A similar relationship with development studio Sumo Digital exists at postgraduate level. This

relationship with developers provides a platform for industry professionals to deliver guest talks to the entire third year cohort. Student teams draw on a range of disciplinary and degree programmes including art, programming and design. Speakers come from established organisations including 4J, Very Evil Demons, The Scarlet Bureau and the UK Games Fund, a public funding body that offers funding for early-stage games.

Formal arrangements with industry have also benefitted Dundee & Angus College, for example with the studio Ninja Kiwi: *“They sponsor one of our classrooms. They come in and do motivational talks and workshops. They help us with a games jam, and they provide advisory support on some of our curriculum... Also Outplay and Hyper Luminal, but not as closely as Kiwi.”* (educator). The college delivers a unique contribution to the cluster through their esports educational offering and is also fostering connections with esports organisations as part of its move into the sector. Graduates are trained in broadcasting, live production, content creation and sound engineering disciplines for use in staging and disseminating esports events. The Gardyne campus hosts an esports club for young people (aged 10–14) that runs weekly, along with a collegiate esports team (D&A Dragons), an esports society, and a league that forms a hub for competitive play. This commitment from an educational institution can be placed in context with recent plans for a major esports’ venue in Dundee. Reports had indicated planning between civic and commercial entities for a major esports arena to be built in the city’s waterfront area which has seen considerable development over the last decade; however, recently the scale of this project has been downsized (Scottish Construction Now 2025), and the proposed development is multi-purpose rather than dedicated. This indicates that educational institutions, particularly in smaller cities such as Dundee, can provide anchor points for fostering emergent dimensions of a cluster where there are fluctuation and uncertainty in other forms of investment.

Informal aspects of the Dundee cluster were once again affirmed in the mapping and interviews research, with respondents discussing events and meetups such as Games Talks Live (a showcase of talks by game development professionals) and Hubworld (regular industry meetups). As one respondent explained, these events can be particularly important for practitioners who have more recently moved to Dundee: *“I take part in Hubworld Scotland stuff, so yeah, it’s mostly how I know people.”* (independent developer). Interviews further indicated that beyond social and networking opportunities, these informal spaces and networks could be critical for securing employment in the industry through hearing about or being recommended for roles, or for passing along B2B opportunities where a larger studio may be initially contacted by a client, but determine they were unsuited to the project. They would then play matchmaker by introducing other smaller studios in the cluster, who had proven successful in securing the contract: *“The market is big enough and actually hard enough for everybody without us fighting against one another. So, I think that my view of it is there is still a kind of an attitude of open understanding. If you would ask somebody for help... I don’t think anybody would say, ‘No, no, you’re on your own, that’s our trade secret.’ So, we might not get together as much as we used to, I think, but still, there’s still a willingness to help each other out, I think, and introduce people or point people in the right direction.”* (studio lead). These client introductions were described as often involving alumni of the larger studio, indicating a network of

informal connection and support that is active and supports development of new organisations in the cluster.

Events and meetups are also a critical connection between the games industry and the wider creative community in the city. This forms a core part of Creative Dundee's activity alongside strategic initiatives and policy work. *"I've been very inspired and interested in being around lots of creatives. Some of them are people from games, but for me it's one part – one piece of a bigger creative offering that the city provides."* (independent developer). The organisation runs regular Pecha Kucha nights in key cultural venues such as the Dundee Repertory Theatre that attract participation from across the city's creative sectors and are regularly sold out. Pecha Kucha are short-form presentations, run in the city by Creative Dundee since 2011, that have featured game industry professionals and educators alongside participants from a range of creative industries and community backgrounds. The format cycles through a wide range of presentations oriented to digestible introductions and thus facilitates cross-sector engagement.

Creative Dundee, through working with a range of community and funding partners, have fed into a very wide range of projects in the city. The Amps Network where pitches occur for a Community Ideas Fund which supports local grassroots social enterprise and creative activity. Respondents described important relations with initiatives such as the Young People's Collective and the Victoria and Albert Museum of Design in Dundee, which seeks to involve young people in co-design opportunities for developing and managing creative projects. Fabric (Creative Dundee 2025) is a related peer leadership programme, which brings together cross-sector creative workers in a series of workshops, site visits and discussion sessions that have fed into the city's creative industries strategy (Dundee Creates 2025). Focused through values such as community resilience, sustainability and social justice, play as a means to build collective imagination is a cornerstone of the community organising efforts. The project's original run has been renewed recently, in collaboration with the Dundee Changemakers Hub. Events ran in 2024 and 2025, with another round being announced this year. The project website quotes Bit Loom and Biome Collective member James Morwood, drawing attention to the links created between game industry and cultural workers, and the importance of proximity and space for connection: *"Since the final Fabric session I have been thinking about how connected I feel to other people in Dundee and that I can come together with others to make a difference in the community. This is something I have struggled with a lot in previous cities, partly because of their size and partly because I was always meeting people in passing. Having the time to slow down and connect with people to discuss things and get to know each other is something I really need and Fabric allowed for that."* (Creative Dundee 2025).

3.3.3 Cluster Perimeter

The boundaries of the cluster were perceived differently by respondents, but several identified the small scale to be a benefit for networking and production, reaffirming previous findings on the '5-minute cluster': *"Dundee is a games hotspot. We all have links and relationships with people who work in games companies locally. And yeah, I think it just feels like the right place to be. There's a lot of community here as well. We can go and we can talk to people."* (independent Developer).

Interpersonal links are cornerstones to collaborative efforts and indications of expertise can be critical to securing work for startup studios, or knowing where to turn if specific capability is required on a given project: *“I know the main designer and the main business guy so I’ve always had a very strong personal relationship with both of them. They’re almost like mentors to me, you know, it’s almost – so it’s a mentorship capacity actually.”* (independent Developer).

Abertay University’s ongoing relationships with industry and incorporation of team-based work with clients in the degree structure was also highlighted: *“it’s useful for people to see, a) what – who is out there in terms of – in the industry of like companies you may never have heard about, b) to realise you could be making games for people who aren’t even necessarily in the industry.”* (junior Developer). This was however also characterised as a complex exchange of value and a set of professional relationships that required maintenance from both parties: *“We enable the companies to hire new talent, and then, as a result, we ask for a lot back from the companies in terms of coming in and supporting us,”* (educator) with the previously described Professional Projects and DARE activities at Abertay University being key examples of this.

Dundee & Angus College are active at the cluster periphery through outreach work with youth and underserved communities, harmonising this activity with their move into esports. The college works with schools and seeks through esports to facilitate the understanding of games careers among young people considering higher education pathways. *“We offer senior phase programmes. So, they can come to us and do some games courses. They come to us for events. We have Esport studios on campus. So, they quite often come to tournaments and have a tour of the facilities. So, we offer taster sessions and things to help with their course choice.”* (educator). The college has also recently collaborated with the organization Into Games, a social mobility charity which provides educational resources, research, bursaries and other support to young people from under-resourced backgrounds who have an interest in entering the games industry. The college thus plays an important role in enabling new talent from a range of backgrounds to access opportunities to enter games and esports and forms a unique through-line across educational levels in the cluster.

However, interviews and mapping also revealed barriers to greater collective action and collaboration in the cluster – differing articulations among the actors about what constitutes centre and periphery relations, and areas in which additional action to connect efforts and build coalitions could be valuable. In the mapping work, these could manifest in the visualised distance between actors of different sectors with conflicting ideas or goals around games and play or be described through interviews in terms of competition for resources or market share within a given sector.

An example of this is the perceived distance between the educational systems in the cluster, and ideas about how better collaboration could benefit the cluster at large: *“It’s very fragmented, I think. We haven’t been working in collaboration as well as we could, I think. That’s purely down to competing for the same students. We do work closer with Abertay. We have articulation agreements in place for our HND graduates to progress on to qualifications. But I think communication could be better... If we maybe worked closer together, we would be able to differentiate that offering and be more focused.”* (educator). Respondents from both education and industry contexts identified difficulties that could be faced by graduates coming out of the education system in search of junior

roles in the industry, and studios looking for specific skillsets when games are in a period of rapid transformation: *“New people coming into the industry having to try and look for junior roles when bigger corporations are trying to find AI solutions to junior roles. It’s tough.”* (studio lead). Prevailing conditions in the wider industry and global media system were often discussed by respondents at various levels of seniority.

Creative Dundee articulated a sense of distance between the game-specific actors and the wider creative arts and industries communities within the city: *“there’s such a strong games community in Dundee that maybe [...] there’s a self-sufficient-ness in that...But maybe because it is so much bigger and more established here than other creative industries, that it is like there’s a self-sufficient-ness and that maybe crossover doesn’t happen as readily then.”* (Creative Dundee board member) The games industry was perceived as more directly concerned with commerce and return on investment than other creative industries active in the city.

In interviews with cultural intermediaries, this view was expressed partly as a perception of social distance, but it was also acutely articulated through concrete ideas around physical space. The lack of space for creative activities and cultural work has been a critical concern identified by Creative Dundee, and this was also articulated by other respondents in the sample. Creative Dundee has been active in addressing this issue from the perspective of cultural work through the Creative Space for Creative Communities project (Creative Communities 2025). Funded by the UK Arts and Humanities Research Council’s Creative Communities programme and in collaboration with the University of Northumbria and University of Dundee, this research project aims to rejuvenate neglected shopfronts in the city for urban regeneration and the formation of new creative hubs. A space for community arts meeting and practice called Hapworks was a recent project that sought to address this issue, although this itself was wound down in 2025, indicating that space for collective working is an ongoing issue in the city. Recent events included a collaboration with Hot Chocolate Trust, a youth work charity that has conducted research on young people’s digital lives and uses playful education to build community resilience and creative collaboration. Creative Dundee members were largely agreed that the lack of physical space for networking was a barrier preventing greater mixing between the commercial and creative sectors of the Dundee video game cluster.

Finding appropriate space in the city is also a difficulty expressed by respondents in senior levels of the Dundonian games industry and follows on from previous **GAME-ER** research findings. Game development, as it scales in scope and capital investment, can have demanding requirements for viable real estate. Tensions arising around occupancy of the Vision Building give an example in Dundee. The building, which is a short distance from the city centre, has often been leased to game and technology companies – including, at one point, Biome Collective. Currently, the Vision Building is host to several large game studios, such as Hyper Luminal, Ninja Kiwi, and Rockstar Dundee (following the acquisition of Ruffian Games). This led to tensions around the space, which has particular value to game companies because of the building’s existing security and location attributes: *“Outplay were planning to expand part of their office in the Vision Building but then Rockstar heard about it and intentionally outbid them on a unit so that they could expand themselves instead, which was not the most cooperative of attitudes.”* (independent developer).

3.3.4 Value Chain

Through the process of mapping key actors, respondents revealed a complex set of considerations around the notion of the value chain (González-Piñero 2017) in the cluster. Respondents reflected on how the Dundee cluster was sensitive to transformations in the global conditions for game production, the place of games in the broader attention economy characteristic of the contemporary media ecosystem, and the ownership structures of the technologies and platforms that underpin much game creation.

As mentioned above, respondents discussed the need for further links between educational actors and the industry as necessary to the quality of the labour market needed for game production. Studio leads described difficulties in encouraging talent to relocate to the city due to its geographical location, and part of the importance of local educational institutions was to help supply skilled labour who were more inclined to remain in the city, or in Scotland. Educators spoke of a greater need for industry to signal employment pathways to graduates from both the college and university systems, building further on current collaborations. However, these shifts also challenged existing business models in the games industry in ways that may advantage smaller cities such as Dundee which are competitive in cost of living terms, *“People like the publishers can’t justify Californian wages... the real great thing is that all of these big studios going pop, it should form all of these groups of super-talented people that can work in new ways, remote, using AI, using all this stuff to find cheaper places to work from... It will diversify the types of games that are made.”* (studio lead).

A key gap that was identified was a need for games-specific business education. This indicated the need both for further emphasis in formal education, but also the need for more incubators and startup support. One studio lead identified the presence of the Techscaler incubator as a benefit for technology startups in the city, but noted that this organisation was more oriented to discrete products rather than the games-as-a-service model of many cluster studios: *“people always want to make their own stuff, which I think is good and interesting, but those people aren’t necessarily business-minded, so they’re not necessarily going to monetise their tech as well as the other people would. But I feel like that’s a necessary tension in games development, of you know, tools making and collaboration.”* (independent developer).

Abertay University feeds into the value chain in various ways. It has provided estate to studios such as Pocket-Sized Hands and Puny Astronaut during their incubation periods. Facilities such as the Competitive Gaming Lab can be hired by studios for Player Research sessions. The CoSTAR Realtime and ViPRE (Virtual Production in Real Time) labs, along with Abertay’s postgraduate offerings, offer affordable access to state of the art virtual production and motion capture facilities to actors in the cluster and beyond, as well as being hubs for R&D bridging games with other creative industries. Abertay’s involvement in the CoSTAR RealTime Lab and CoSTAR National Lab creates opportunities for research and development support to companies nationally and through a range of funding calls targeted at specific industry issues, fund the development of innovative solutions and new IP (Bennett et al, 2026). However, the institution’s primary input is through the replenishment and maintenance of the labour pool within the cluster ecosystem.

One senior developer identified wide-ranging changes in the audience for digital games which necessitated new strategic issues for studios in the cluster: *“obviously the thing I think the industry is fighting for now is people’s attention, in that we no longer are this cool, exciting thing because technology’s pervaded everywhere, everything’s much more advanced now. But people’s time is the limiting factor; people might spend an hour doom scrolling on TikTok or something as opposed to an hour they might have played on a video game, you know. Or they’re busy watching Netflix, or they’re doing X, Y, and Z.”* (studio lead). Where games had traditionally been oriented to specific audiences through specific hardware and software requirements for play, large-scale transformations such as a general shift towards mobile play means that they are increasingly competing directly with other media industries.

In constructing their maps and in interview responses, participants also described considerations around developing new technology or IP, as opposed to building on established middleware platforms such as Unity and Unreal, and the dynamics these platforms had in engaging in B2B or work-for-hire activity. *“Unity and Unreal are really great pieces of tech. It allows studios to get up and running and start building things really fast and it’s great. I would never really go out of my way to hire someone that only knows how to use those tools, though. I would hire engineers that know how to code, and then if they happen to also use those tools, great.”* (studio head). In spite of this value, respondents at various levels of seniority and experience expressed caveats in using these tools. One such platform was described as having ‘aggressive terms’, in their approach to platform charges for developers, representing a broad move away from their founding orientation towards small and independent developers: *“I think where they started and where they are now is two very different companies”* (independent developer). Respondents described a feedback loop that influenced this situation: as a certain engine such as Unity or Unreal became more prominent, the demand from clients to use these engines increased as they perceived needs for compatibility and support beyond specific projects. Developers described the difficulties that could arise for local actors: *“I’m a big fan of owning your own destiny and that type of stuff. Sometimes you just – you can’t when you’re in the hands of those big organisations. If they decide to change the pricing model or cut out a feature – you’re stuck.”* (studio head).

The development of a game creation platform, Game Maker, in the cluster is thus significant. Created in 1999 by Mark Overmars as a freeware tool primarily oriented to 2D games, that later became a professional engine, Game Maker was acquired and further developed by current owner YoYo Games in 2007. The drag-and-drop functionality, ability to offer games across mobile, console and PC platforms, and approachable scripting language have been ongoing features of the platform and has made it an important component of global independent games production. While production has remained with a small team in the city, YoYo Games was acquired in 2020 by Norwegian software company Opera. As one developer described: *“We are owned by Opera browsing company which is sort of like a Scandinavian browser company... GameMaker recently became free, which is very cool ‘cause it makes it more accessible. But anyway, it just means that we have like that relationship where – not quite the same as like a studio publisher, but like we are owned by them.”* (junior developer).

Notably, industry veterans feature in the leadership of YoYo Games and the GameMaker property. *“Russell Kay is the head of GameMaker, he was one of the DMA Design group. He’s worked on Lemmings, the early original Rockstar among other things, you know, so he’s been kicking around. There’s also... Mike Rennie.”* (junior developer). Other companies in the cluster are also pursuing the development of their own engines and platforms, such as 4J’s Reforj, a voxel-based open world survival sandbox game. A respondent described YoYo Games as comprised of a large proportion of experienced staff, and as more of a software development house than a games studio, with a more measured pace of development and approach to the rollout of new features or products when compared to many game developers.

Work-for-hire was described as a core business model for many in the cluster, with studios working with international clients and academic institutions to develop games in line with their needs. An area that was identified for growth was applied or serious games (the use of games techniques and technology beyond entertainment purposes): *“people were talking about serious games as a monolith, but now...it’s so broad that there are very specific areas that are developing.”* (independent developer). Serious Games development has enabled studios such as Konglomerate Games and Pocket Sized Hands to grow their portfolios and establish themselves in the cluster. Pocket Sized Hands collaboration on the InGAME International project, for example, allowed them to fulfil research goals whilst producing their own IP for the first time. As a result, the studio was able to raise their international profile by pitching their own IP to publishers (McSwan et al. 2024). However, the work-for-hire model was also seen as contributing to a low rate of original IP development: *“I would say there’s a whole bunch of studios where they never own the IP; they just do the work... I don’t wanna work on any more games where I give it all away.”* (studio head). Funding for original IP is difficult to secure, positioning events such as Game Developers Conference, Gamescom and Develop:Brighton as important for Dundee developers to meet with publishers and investors to pitch their work. A strong work-for-hire portfolio can enhance the profile of these developers and enhance their potential for success in securing funding. Exposure to foreign direct investment and actors beyond the cluster came with risk, however, and the sense that decisions could be taken by remote ownership or partners with little at stake in the cluster or the city.

Larger, more established studios including Rockstar North, Scopely, Ninja Kiwi, and Hyper Luminal Games develop and publish their own IP across accessible platforms such as Steam, Apple app store and Google Play and also engage with platform providers publishing on Switch, Xbox and PlayStation. The success of Hyper Luminal in developing its own IP highlights the viability of its work-for-hire and service provision business models: it is one of the few studios owned and operated in Dundee to have created its own large-scale IP in recent years. The accessibility of the route to market of mobile platforms and Steam Store allow independent developers and collectives in the cluster to publish their own IP directly. The cluster has a robustness with regard to publisher relations as a result of the direct access to market via Steam Store and mobile platforms, heavy engagement with work-for-hire, and for a few of the larger developers, the success of their own IP enabling them to work directly with console platform holders.

Studios such as Hyper Luminal Games are developing a selection of services to support smaller studios with developing their games, such as access to quality assurance services and user experience design talent. This diversification of their business model demonstrates formalisation of the informal knowledge and expertise sharing evident across the cluster into a business model that aims to benefit studios across and beyond the cluster. The approach also benefits their clients who are provided with access to services and expertise that extends beyond their current workforce. Other studios are similarly exploring new ways of working, that push against work-for-hire and hierarchical power structures typically seen in commercial games development by connecting with groups such as Cooperatives UK and the Independent Workers of Great Britain (IWGB), aligning with global unionisation movement in the industry (Woodcock 2021): *“There are a handful of games co-ops already in the UK, but it is very few, a very small number. So yeah, that’s what we want to do. We want to show that this kind of democratic way of working can exist and it is viable. And we want to produce things, we want to make interesting games, and we want to work with people to make their interesting games as well for them and help them without having these kinds of antagonistic business relations.”* (independent developer). The name of the collective was described as a not-too-subtle reference to the sort of power relations that the group set out to challenge.

3.4 Conclusion

The mapping work conducted in this task showed Dundee as a long-established game development cluster, and this history has given time for a range of views to develop. Cultural actors, who may be relatively less interested in digital games, have strong views on the role of the industry in the city, the types of clustering activity that make most sense from their point of view (what is central and what is peripheral, who is involved, and how the value chain is composed), and the appropriate forms of resourcing for different kinds of work. In common with previous **GAME-ER** research, educational institutions, established studios, and informal networks were found to be critical to the functioning of the cluster and important to the ongoing viability of the games industry in the Dundee. Building on this work, new details were found around the role of cultural intermediaries, the importance of physical space for creative exchange in opportunities for transformative links between creative and commercial sectors, and the importance of the Dundee & Angus College and Creative Dundee to addressing these issues. Umbrella funding from Creative Scotland, and the complex relations to international platforms for game production such as Unity and Unreal engines deeply influence activity in the cluster. For actors across the sample, the presence of home-grown platforms such as Game Maker, and autonomous forms of organising game production labour (such as the Biome and Very Evil Demons collectives) have the potential to add robustness to the cluster’s previously exhibited capability to bounce back from exogenous shocks.

4 TURIN

4.1 Overview of the Cluster

The Turin cluster, as extensively analysed in previous deliverables (**D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3**), exhibits a high degree of relational complexity. The actors that compose and sustain it are highly heterogeneous, and their interactions collectively shape the local sectoral value chain. These actors include both long-established and newly founded development studios, professional training/educational institutions, formal and informal institutional organisations/associations, public and private bodies, and, above all, individual actors.

Individuals and development studios not only played a central role in the early phase of the ecosystem's semi-institutionalisation (see **D4.3**) but continue to constitute the core around which most cluster relationships revolve, albeit with slightly less centrality than in the initial phase. Within this landscape, the presence of a local IGDA (International Game Developers Association) chapter has contributed significantly to strengthening ecosystem cohesion, fostering closer relational ties among its members, while expanding opportunities for events and forms of collective interaction.

The cluster's persistent informality characterised by a strong voluntary component that simultaneously represents both a limitation and a strength of the ecosystem's operational dynamics – is further reinforced by the deliberately indie orientation of local development studios and B2C production practices. The city of Turin itself amplifies this productive orientation by providing a distinctive identity framework and nurturing the creative dimension of the video games developed within the ecosystem.

Finally, the inclusion of Officine Grandi Riparazioni (OGR) as both an institutional actor and a physical meeting space has added an additional layer of formal recognition to the environment. Its presence has introduced further spatial and relational complexity at the territorial level, while also establishing an important reference point for local and national visibility of Turin's gaming sector.

Building upon the analyses presented in previous deliverables, this chapter aims to examine more closely the composition of actors operating within the Turin cluster. It differentiates them according to their relevance and degree of participation in ecosystem dynamics, while highlighting the relationships among them, particularly in relation to the current configuration of the cluster.

4.2 Data Collection

This study is based on a series of semi-structured interviews (N=6) conducted with selected actors within the Turin video game development cluster between January and February 2026. Interviewees were identified among those previously involved in **D4.1** and selected according to their availability and their position within the ecosystem. Given the informal nature of the cluster and the overlapping roles commonly held by actors within it, the heterogeneity of the interview sample was necessarily limited, although still indicative of local operational dynamics and hierarchical structures. All participants were informed of the purpose of the mapping interviews and the objectives of **T4.4** and provided written informed consent in compliance with GDPR requirements.

As observed in previous deliverables, the gender distribution remained strongly male-dominated: only one of the six interviewees was female, confirming the persistent gender imbalance characterising the sector at local, national, and global levels. Most interviews were conducted in person (four out of six), with an average duration of approximately 30 minutes. Following a detailed explanation of the exercise, all interviews were audio-recorded, subsequently transcribed, and edited to remove transcription imperfections.¹ The maps produced during the interviews were predominantly produced using pen and paper, with the exception of one participant who preferred a digital format. In all cases, the maps were discussed collaboratively during their creation.

Prior to the interview phase, the research team independently developed an internal conceptual map based on the data synthesised in **D4.1** and **D4.2**. This preliminary exercise aimed to establish a shared analytical reference framework, facilitating comparison with participants' representations and supporting the management of subsequent research phases. Following the completion of the interviews, a summary map was produced based on the visual materials generated by participants (following the approach by Lehtonen et al. 2020; 2022), synthesising the various representations of cluster actors, dynamics and relationships. This comprehensive map was subsequently validated by a small group of respondents, serving both as a final analytical synthesis and as a basis for comparative analysis across the clusters examined within WP3.

From an operational perspective, the UNITO research team analysed the maps provided by participants using NVivo (version 15). The six individual maps were then synthesised into a single comprehensive representation through the online diagramming platform [draw.io/diagrams.net](https://draw.io). In accordance with the guidelines provided by the CUNI team, the comprehensive map was discussed and validated during a workshop held in March 2026 with four cluster representatives. These participants were selected partly from among those involved in previous mapping activities (one of the six original interviewees) and partly from additional actors possessing different degrees of familiarity with the cluster's dynamics. The latter group included two representatives from OGR and one member of the UNITO **GAME-ER** research team who, although involved in the project, was not directly engaged in its qualitative analysis. Compared with the original pool of interviewees, the workshop participants introduced a significant difference in terms of gender composition, as three of the four representatives were women, thereby contributing greater gender diversity to the final validation phase of the analysis. Again, after a detailed explanation of the study's objectives and methodological approach, participants were invited to reflect upon and validate the summary map. The workshop session was recorded, transcribed, edited, and subsequently analysed.

The final stage consisted of a further systematisation of the overall map, incorporating feedback provided by cluster representatives during the workshop. In this case, unlike the previous one, both the diagramming process and the subsequent adjustments to the map were carried out using Microsoft Visio to ensure greater accuracy. The finalised map was subsequently presented once more to several representatives for informal consultation and final validation of the analytical outcomes.

¹ The text also includes a series of excerpts from interviews, for which references have been partially anonymised, with only the interviewees' initials provided.

4.3 Actor Mapping

This task involved the production of a series of visual maps representing the Turin video game development cluster. The maps, created by six ecosystem actors during the interview process, enabled the visual identification of key stakeholders and the relationships structuring the cluster. Each map, however, differed substantially from the others. The individual representations reflected the diverse roles, professional positions, and institutional affiliations of the interviewees, resulting in heterogeneous visualisations of both actors and relational configurations. **Figures 6, 7, and 8** present three examples produced by participants, illustrating actors occupying different roles within the cluster.

Figure 6: Example of an individual actor map (Turin; institutional associations)

The combined analysis of the individual maps and the interview material enabled the construction of an intermediate summary map (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9: Draft version of the final map (Turin)

Finally, in response to the feedback received during the workshop, a fully developed and comprehensive final map was produced (**Figure 10**). This process involved several minor revisions to the map’s initial visual and relational structure, including adjustments to the positioning of certain elements, the correction of typographical errors, and the addition of a new actor that had not been previously considered. Given the heterogeneity of the original visualisations and the high degree of relational complexity articulated by participants, the final map should be understood as an analytical synthesis rather than a comprehensive reproduction of the empirical material. While this synthesis provides a significant advantage by organising and simplifying otherwise fragmented and difficult-to-integrate data, it inevitably entails a degree of representational reduction. Consequently, the summary map cannot fully capture either the entirety of the visual material produced by interviewees or the full complexity of actors and relationships constituting the Turin cluster. Despite these limitations, the resulting representation offers a coherent visual overview of the ecosystem, its principal actors, events, and relational dynamics. By translating complex qualitative findings into an accessible visual format, the map enhances the overall readability of the deliverable and supports engagement with a broad range of audiences, including academic researchers, policymakers, and sector stakeholders.

Figure 10: Final actor map (Turin)

4.3.1 Key Actors and Features

First and foremost, as extensively discussed in previous deliverables, the Turin video game development cluster should be understood as a relatively young ecosystem, whose formation can be traced back to the period between 2013 and 2014. Its emergence, and subsequent evolution into the current phase of semi-institutionalisation, resulted primarily from the initiative of individual actors – mainly developers – who chose to establish development companies in their city of origin rather than pursuing employment within larger firms located in Milan. Although the objective of the present analysis is to provide a synchronic representation of the ecosystem, the small scale and recent formation of the cluster inevitably introduce a diachronic dimension within the visual representations produced by interviewees.

A defining characteristic emerging from the mapping process is therefore the centrality of development studios. This element represents the most diachronically grounded aspect of participants' reconstructions and visual interpretations of the ecosystem: *"That is to say, Turin [cluster] was founded because there were development studios beforehand."* (studio head).

Alongside development studios, the current configuration places another key actor at the centre of the ecosystem: the Turin chapter of the International Game Developers Association (IGDA). Together with a core group of studios, IGDA appears as the primary relational hub, functioning simultaneously as connective infrastructure, collective reference point, and, to a certain extent, the organisational rationale underpinning the ecosystem itself.

Within this "dual-hearted" structure, the development studio component does not encompass all local developers but rather those commonly identified as the "old developers",² namely the founding studios of the cluster: 34BigThings, Tiny Bull Studios, Memorable Games (often referred to by interviewees by its former name, MixedBag), and Broken Arms Games, positioned slightly outside the spatial core due to its physical location in Acqui Terme, in the province of Alessandria (AL). Despite this geographical distance, the studio remains firmly recognised as central to both the historical construction and present functioning of the cluster.

This group forms part of a broader network of "Piedmont game developers" and is informally referred to by its members as "Gianduiotto Game Devs", a humorous reference to the traditional triangular prism-shaped gianduaia chocolate produced in Turin: *"And within that cluster, which we could call Piedmont game dev, or we sometimes call it Gianduiotto game dev, which is very funny."* (studio head).

These historically established studios maintain dense and long-standing relationships both among themselves and with almost all other ecosystem components. Their cooperation strengthens the collective identity of the cluster and enhances its recognisability both within and beyond the city: *"So, essentially, I place companies at the centre; therefore, in my opinion, companies are the core of the engine; they are the ones that generate products and GDP. Companies collaborate with each other; they are a sphere, a network of companies that are more or less connected to each other and cooperate in various ways. [...] Companies produce video games, video games are enjoyed by the public, which on the one hand serves as entertainment, but above all inspires the public to observe that this industry exists."* (headmaster of a private school).

A relatively clear distinction emerges between these founding studios and a broader category of "other developers". The latter tend to occupy more peripheral positions and include newly established studios actively participating in ecosystem activities (often closely connected to IGDA), studios that have not relocated to Turin but remain involved in local initiatives – frequently operating within B2B production – small independent developers and student collectives, as well as actors described as being "outside the loop" (*"fuori dal giro"*), namely developers present locally but less engaged in intra-cluster dynamics.

² The term "old developers", as used by some interviewees to refer to the four "founding" development studios, is therefore preferred over alternative labels such as "established developers".

A notable exception to this division is represented by FutuRats, widely regarded as an emerging studio with significant potential. It is perceived as closely aligned with the founding studios while simultaneously maintaining strong links with newer actors, playing a sort of hybrid role. Positioned at the intersection of old and new generations – a so-called new or second “wave” of developers – FutuRats connects development studios, IGDA, OGR, and Quickload, thereby functioning as a potential bridge facilitating generational transition within the local industry.

The newer studios identified through the mapping exercise include Volcanite Games, Unrelated, Deep Monolith, and Synesthesia.³ These studios are generally smaller in scale, some displaying a stronger orientation towards B2B activities, yet they actively contribute to the vitality of the ecosystem. Within this broader subset are also studios primarily engaged in the technological segment of the value chain – such as Febucci, 3×1010 (including its Fix-a-Bug B2C division), 906 Games (based in Como), and W4Games from Ireland, founded by veterans of the Godot Engine project. Their inclusion demonstrates that territorial origin is less decisive than active participation within ecosystem dynamics.

External studios choosing not to relocate to Turin or Piedmont nonetheless enrich the ecosystem, particularly through participation in IGDA-organised events. In many cases, their connection to the cluster originates from the Quickload acceleration programme, which has hosted studios from across Italy and Europe, enabling sustained relationships even after programme completion. The case of Slitherine, a British producer and publisher known for strategy video games (with an office in Milan), is relevant in a different way. While numerous similar actors are positioned outside the ecosystem yet loosely gravitate around it, Slitherine maintains a more active and significant relationship with the cluster, probably more so than in the rest of Italy. Although visually positioned at the periphery of the cluster, the company actively collaborates with several Turin-based development studios (including Volcanite Games and FutuRats), thereby strengthening the overall significance of the ecosystem.

Small-scale developers, including student collectives such as Level Up Lab (LUL), typically consist of students or recent graduates from the Polytechnic University of Turin or private video game development schools (Event Horizon School, Scuola Nash), experimenting with independent production. Their long-term sustainability depends largely on market conditions and the commercial success of initial projects.

A distinct category is represented by developers identified as being “outside the loop”. Although peripheral in operational terms, they remain integral components of the ecosystem. Examples include Tmesis Studio, True Colors, Studio Ortica, and the independent developer Zizou. Difficulties encountered during sampling in **D4.1** suggest that these actors may be underrepresented in participants’ perceptions despite their continued territorial presence.

A recent and still evolving element within the cluster is the arrival of Poncle, internationally recognised for their video game *Vampire Survivors* (Poncle 2022). Although it has been present

³ It should be noted that Synesthesia cannot be regarded as a wholly ‘new actor’ within the Turin ecosystem. Although the company has been active locally for many years, its operations were historically centred on B2B activities, with video game development representing a comparatively recent strategic expansion.

within the ecosystem for only a short period, and this information remains largely unknown outside industry circles, Poncle has already established a physical presence within OGR Tech. Its future role remains uncertain, but it is widely perceived as potentially transformative for the whole creative environment: *“Yes, it already has a physical space. I put it that way because, as you discovered yesterday, it may be something that I and those involved in the sector have known about for a long time, but, rightly, nothing is known externally for now, let’s put it that way. And so that’s how it is, I’m putting a question mark on it, because clearly these are things that have only just begun, and we need to understand where it’s going.”* (studio head). In fact, the presence of a highly successful studio is commonly interpreted as a decisive factor in the expansion of regional game development clusters, positioning Poncle as a potential systemic game changer.

The second “heart” of the ecosystem is represented by IGDA Turin. Acting alongside the cluster’s founding studios, IGDA performs an aggregative function that complements and partially absorbs earlier informal coordination roles while expanding them into broader social and community-building practices: *“That is, the IGDA issue, which is definitely the human aggregator... I call it the human aggregator because it basically brings people together. Before bringing companies together, before bringing... It’s really the aggregator of people... There is Tech & Tonic, which is, in part, the result of IGDA, but it is also open to the public, something that attracts external agents, people, and interested parties. Beer to Peer, for me, is fundamental, because, although I never participate, I know that in Turin it is the only event that has taken the form of something... a truly social gathering.”* (studio head).

IGDA Turin is therefore widely perceived as the primary driver of both formal and informal cluster activities. Its main recognised function lies in maintaining communication across ecosystem actors while mediating relationships and acting as a relational “bridge”: *“In my opinion, the point of IGDA is to try to talk to as many organisations in the area as possible. [...] So, in my opinion, what works and also makes sense is that developers have a bridge of communication, though not necessarily through IGDA. So, there can be different paths, right? That can be taken. So, you can talk to Quickload, which talks to IGDA, which talks to other developers. [...] A bridge, basically, of connection.”* (board member IGDA Italy).

Although development studios remain structurally central, interviewees emphasise that without IGDA, the relational dynamism characterising the ecosystem would be significantly reduced. Many interactions circulate through IGDA-organised initiatives, particularly Tech & Tonic – a structured (and formal) monthly networking event hosted at OGR Tech – and Beer to Peer (or Beer 2 Peer), an informal community gathering: *“Tech & Tonic is more structured for professionals, for those who want to understand something from a work perspective, from a job perspective. Whereas I like Beer to Peer for them, but I never go. Simply because it’s really the social aspect of gaming, our people...”* (studio head).

Composed of recognised individuals occupying multiple roles within the ecosystem, IGDA Turin operates as the principal organiser of local physical and digital events and as the main gateway connecting the cluster to national and international networks. The entirely voluntary nature of IGDA Turin further reinforces the informal character of the ecosystem. Participation in the network does

not require formal membership or registration, nor does it provide any financial remuneration to board members or chapter advisors.

These initiatives are complemented by the Global Game Jam (GGJ), a collaborative game development event bringing together developers, enthusiasts, and students in a 48-hour production “marathon” in which participants meet to develop a video game prototype together. Historically linked to the birth of the cluster itself – its first local edition taking place in January 2014 (see **D4.1, D4.2 and D4.3**) – it is currently organised by IGDA with the patronage of the Municipality of Settimo Torinese (since 2025). This municipality appears in the mappings as the only public institutional actor actively interacting with the ecosystem, albeit in a limited capacity:⁴ *“Personally, apart from the Municipality of Settimo for Game Jam, I don’t see any public institutions. So, the only public institution I see is the Municipality of Settimo, because I had never been there before, but this year there was Game Jam and I said, wow, what an incredible thing. I mean, it’s such a small provincial town, which lives off warehouses and little else, that it provides a space... that it gives such huge support, I found it incredible.”* (studio head).

The organisation of the Piedmont Global Game Jam outside the city of Turin contributes positively to the event’s development by providing larger and better-equipped spaces while strengthening connections with actors beyond the urban core (even from outside the Piedmont region). Conversely, public institutions such as the Municipality of Turin or the Chamber of Commerce appear only marginally and are generally perceived as absent from the cluster’s operational mechanisms: *“In my opinion, we have a bit of a problem in Turin at the moment with a lack of purely public actors to support the sector. In fact, I’m not putting anyone forward, because we don’t really have any real or tangible interest from the municipality, the region or anyone else at the moment.”* (studio head), and again: *“There is, perhaps, one last entity that we could consider, but it is still so vague at the moment, which is everything related to the Chamber of Commerce, the City Council of Turin, all these things, but in my opinion, they are still too far removed.”* (studio head).

The Officine Grandi Riparazioni are rarely represented as autonomous institutional actors and instead appear primarily as physical spaces endowed with strong aggregative value: *“For me, OGR is little more than a place. In the sense that it’s the physical space, which is fine and has value too, because in reality, if we didn’t have a beautiful space like OGR, I think all this enthusiasm would probably wane. I mean, the fact that you’re in such a beautiful space, so... it’s a space where when you walk in, you want to build something, it’s a very strong aspiration, in my opinion. But, on the other hand, I’m not a huge fan in the sense that I think they could do much more. They have the economic and structural strength, because often it’s not about money; in my opinion, it’s about doing things. They have such strength that they could build much more. But OGR has a role in that it is the space. And the space plays its part, because it exists, because it’s there.”* (studio head).

OGR therefore functions primarily as a container infrastructure – hosting Quickload, IGDA events, the VIEW Conference, and studio workspaces (as recently happened with Poncle) – rather than as an active organisational agent. As such, it is often reproduced laterally, shifted from the main axis

⁴ Without undermining its significance, as it temporarily transforms a town of 45,000 inhabitants into a small video game development hub for two days.

of the cluster’s key players. Its role is nonetheless crucial as a physical aggregator and symbolically recognisable locus of the ecosystem, even if it is somewhat dematerialised as an active player.

Among educational actors, the Polytechnic University of Turin occupies a central position. Unlike the University of Turin, it is the only public higher education institution consistently associated with ecosystem dynamics. Through initiatives such as Level Up Lab, founded in 2023, the Polytechnic acts both as an institutional actor and experimental hub for game development practices. LUL, visually represented as embedded within the Polytechnic structure, is recognised by interviewees as a structured initiative closely connected to development studios and IGDA Turin. It constitutes a key source of interns and emerging professionals, thereby representing the most immediate local talent pipeline. LUL also organised Press Start Game Jam, a 48-hour game jam open to the public, thereby establishing its own space for public and institutional engagement. In addition, in collaboration with IGDA, LUL organises the recurring event series *How To Level Up*, consisting of a programme of talks, masterclasses, and workshops broadly similar in format to the Tech & Tonic model.

Conversely, the University of Turin continues to occupy a marginal position within the ecosystem despite contributing graduates to the broader ICT sector from its computer science department. The Centre for Studies on Gaming and Playfulness (*Centro Studi sul Gioco e la Ludicità*) provides interdisciplinary academic engagement with games and play culture, yet it is not perceived by interviewees as sufficiently integrated into cluster dynamics and therefore appears only marginally in the mappings.

Among private training/educational institutions, International School of Comics (*Scuola Internazionale di Comics*) – historically significant alongside the now less-relevant Event Horizon School⁵ – is included but positioned at the margins of the ecosystem, partly due to its limited gaming-specific educational offer and the broader crisis affecting local private training/educational providers.

Nash School (*Scuola Nash*), by contrast, is perceived as a potential successor to Event Horizon School. It is a private training institution focused on video game development, closely embedded within the local ecosystem. Despite its recent establishment (2025–2026), the migration of teaching staff⁶ and the involvement of professionals connected to IGDA and local studios⁷ provide strong foundations for future integration: *“In fact, Nash is more valuable today. Because even though it is still small and in its infancy, it is something that will hopefully bring something in the future.”* (studio head).

Educational institutions collectively sustain the ecosystem’s talent pipeline, often producing more graduates than the local market can immediately absorb.⁸ They maintain bidirectional relationships

⁵ At the time of writing, the current status of the school’s activities remains uncertain.

⁶ Many of its instructors have prior teaching experience at Event Horizon School, reinforcing its professional grounding.

⁷ Nash School has established partnerships with 34BigThings, FutuRats, Dramatic Iceberg, and Lullabyte Games.

⁸ This problem is seen both locally and nationally. For example: *“And schools, of course, theoretically train professionals who then end up working in companies. The big problem, but this is a problem at the national level, is that there are too many schools training too many people. The gaming industry in Italy, let alone in Turin, is absolutely unable to absorb the 600-700 game designers who are churned out every year. In fact, the vast majority are unable to find work in the industry. Some, if they are lucky, create new teams, some are absorbed, rarely, by existing companies, others perhaps go abroad. But I imagine that a good 90% of those who end up in a gaming school in Italy and Turin end up doing*

with development studios, supplying trained students – frequently through internship programmes – while receiving industry feedback to adapt curricula and develop sector-specific competences: *“Schools have a two-way communication with individual companies, normally, so companies should provide feedback. I used the word “direct”, but in the sense of directing information, providing information, so they inform, OK? They inform the schools, and the schools provide feedback to the companies on training, in turn, right? That is, our students are able to, or is it possible to train this type of figure, so as to have a two-way communication, right?”* (headmaster of a private school).

Finally, the Italian Interactive Digital Entertainment Association (IIDEA), the national trade association headquartered in Milan, is recognised as a formally relevant institutional actor due to its role in national representation. Although generally considered external to the Turin ecosystem, it functions as a bridge connecting the cluster to the broader Italian industry. Through initiatives such as First Playable, the main international event for video game developers in Italy, organised with Tuscany Film Commission, IIDEA provides national visibility and institutional coordination. Its external positioning limits its direct operational influence within the cluster, yet it remains an important reference point within the wider national value chain. In fact, it is seen as a point of contact for the cluster’s most structured studios and as the main (and only) institutional representative at the central institutional/political level.

4.3.2 Collective Actions

IGDA Turin, in addition to constituting a key actor within the cluster, functions as the primary organiser of collective action, particularly through the coordination of targeted events. As the first Italian chapter of the International Game Developers Association established in the country,⁹ it brings together several figures recognised as central to the ecosystem, including Tiziano Giardini (President), Tommaso Verde and Gabriele Gallo as board members, and Valerio Di Donato (34BigThings) and Marco Mazzaglia (active across multiple development studios and the Polytechnic University of Turin) as chapter advisors.

These individuals simultaneously occupy multiple roles within the ecosystem – as studio founders and employees, educators in private schools and universities, and contributors to initiatives such as Quickload – thereby ensuring dense bidirectional connections across the entire local value chain, encompassing education, game development, and private institutional actors. By inheriting the legacy of the previous local developers’ association, T-Union (founded in 2013), IGDA Turin has also guaranteed organisational continuity with the cluster’s founding studios. As a branch of an international association, its presence further enables external relational expansion, linking the Turin ecosystem both to other Italian IGDA chapters and to the broader international network, thus widening the scope of opportunities available to local actors.

Nevertheless, IGDA Turin is primarily recognised by interviewees for its role as organiser of local events, most notably Tech & Tonic, Beer to Peer, and the Global Game Jam: *“IGDA plays a very*

something completely different, whether it’s waiting tables at McDonald’s or in a bar, or perhaps doing something vaguely related, such as working as a developer in a non-gaming company or as a designer or something similar.” (ML)

⁹ Currently, the Italian chapter of IGDA covers six cities/areas, namely Turin, Milan, Rome, Genoa, Sardinia, and Sicily.

important role at the moment. [...] We have Tech & Tonic, which is run by IGDA, and Beer to Peer, which is also run by IGDA.” (MF)

Although IGDA Turin participates in nearly all local initiatives related to video games and technology – including institutional events – these three recurring meet-ups (the first two monthly and the third annual) constitute the cornerstone of the cluster’s internal cohesion and external visibility. Tech & Tonic and Beer to Peer can be interpreted as complementary expressions of the same relational logic.

Tech & Tonic, held monthly at OGR Tech, directly targets developers while remaining open to students and enthusiasts. The event typically consists of technical or thematic talks delivered by invited speakers, followed by a collective networking moment centred on informal discussion, pitching opportunities, and social interaction. While the initial phase follows a relatively structured conference format, concluding with a Q&A session, the second phase becomes highly relational and community-oriented, reflecting the broader operational culture of the cluster. This duality is spatially embodied within OGR itself: the formal presentations take place within the equipped conference areas of OGR Tech, whereas the networking phase moves to OGR Snodo, the multifunctional social space combining restaurant, bar, indoor “social table” areas, and outdoor spaces designed for interaction.

Through this configuration, Tech & Tonic successfully merges professional formalisation with the informal interaction typical of creative communities, assuming a semi-institutional character widely recognised by interviewees. Moreover, the event operates at a micro-relational level by facilitating connections between individuals and development studios: *“The events organised by IGDA are interesting because, on the one hand, they bring developers together, which can also lead to the creation of informal teams, knowledge sharing, and so on. But they also bring companies together, because obviously, representatives of companies often participate in events such as Tech & Tonic. Because usually those who give talks, [...] it’s true that there are many people who may go and do it as individuals, but often they are representatives of a company, so they talk about their experience. So in a way, they bring individuals closer to companies.”* (studio head).

Beer to Peer represents the opposite pole of this organisational spectrum. Entirely devoid of formal structure, it is conceived exclusively as a social gathering dedicated to informal exchange and community building. Hosted monthly in a brewery in central Turin, it attracts both professionals and enthusiasts in a relaxed environment that strengthens offline networking beyond digital interactions. The event exemplifies not only the operational logic of the Turin cluster but also broader cultural practices within the Italian video game industry. It mirrors the long-standing informal meetings – lunches, barbecues, and other gatherings – that historically characterised relations among the cluster’s founding members. Although Beer to Peer remains connected to these companies, it has evolved into a significant networking event, particularly among members of the newer generation of development studios, reflecting the transformation and evolution of actors within the ecosystem. Participation levels in both events remain extremely high, with Tech & Tonic registrations frequently reaching full capacity shortly after opening.

Alongside physical meet-ups, IGDA Turin also organises digital initiatives dedicated to training and knowledge exchange among professionals. Coordination primarily occurs through Discord, further reinforcing the association's digitally mediated and participatory nature.

Additional evidence of the cluster's internal continuity – later extended nationally through IGDA – is represented by the local Global Game Jam. The “Year Zero” of the cluster's semi-institutionalised phase coincides with the first local GGJ held in January 2014, organised by founding developers together with T-Union. Although IGDA has progressively assumed institutional prominence, the symbolic centrality of the Global Game Jam remains universally recognised. Among all events, GGJ is perceived as the most direct and inclusive relational space, bringing together experienced developers and newcomers alike.

The relocation of the event from the City of Turin to Settimo Torinese has not diminished its perceived quality. On the contrary, it facilitated the involvement of the Municipality of Settimo Torinese – currently the only public institutional actor consistently recognised as actively engaged with the ecosystem. Unlike the Municipality of Turin, this local authority is perceived as demonstrating tangible interest and support for the sector.

Although the Global Game Jam is not formally exclusive to IGDA, the association provides its strongest organisational visibility. Interviewees consistently associate the event's identity with IGDA's visual and organisational presence, placing GGJ alongside Tech & Tonic and Beer to Peer as part of an informal “trptych” representing the cluster's principal mechanisms of collective action. To this configuration is added, albeit with a different functional role, the Quickload acceleration programme.

Despite the existence of OGR as a private institutional actor, interviewees encountered notable difficulties when positioning it within visual mappings. In most cases, OGR was stripped of agency and represented primarily as a physical and relational environment rather than as an active organisational player, perceived as only partially dedicated to video game development. Its most significant contribution to the sector derives from hosting Quickload (established in 2019), which appears alternately as an internal component of OGR or as an autonomous (and spatially separated) entity: *“Quickload, somehow, I don't even know whether to create an OGR entity, because, in reality, OGR without Quickload is more of a space than anything else.”* (studio head).

This ambiguity suggests a perceptual separation between OGR and Quickload. Now in its fifth edition, Quickload has enabled several studios – including FutuRats, Dramatic Iceberg, Volcanite Games, Febucci, 906 Games, and Deep Monolith – to become integral parts of the local ecosystem. Its impact operates along two complementary dimensions. Temporally, it supports the consolidation of new studios, linking past and present phases of cluster development. Spatially, it connects the ecosystem to external contexts by attracting companies from outside the region and occasionally from abroad. Through this dual function, Quickload enhances both the visibility of the cluster and the symbolic positioning of Turin within the industry.

Interestingly, Microsoft's involvement through Quickload and OGR appeared in only one visual map, effectively minimising the perceived presence of a major international actor. Instead, recognition tends to focus on individuals directly associated with programme operations, such as Tiziano

Giardini (Programme Director) and Valerio Di Donato. Furthermore, contrary to observations in **D4.2** – but consistent with interviews conducted for **D4.1** – the I3P incubator of the Polytechnic University of Turin was never mentioned by interviewees, indicating its limited relevance to the gaming sector specifically.

A significant event that regularly takes place at OGR is the VIEW Conference, an annual conference on computer graphics held in Turin between October and November. However, its inclusion in the visual representation of the ecosystem occurred only at a later stage, following the workshop. Despite its relevance to the industry – the event covers topics such as interactive techniques, digital cinema, 3D animation, gaming, and visual effects – it was not considered during the initial mapping phase. This omission may indicate a certain disconnect with the specific sector or, more likely, the attribution of a more peripheral role in relation to video game development. Alongside its direct interaction with OGR, the VIEW Conference has collaborated with almost all development studios in the cluster, although none of these collaborations has been permanent. In the final map, the decision was therefore to position it separately, somewhat to the side, while maintaining a direct connection to OGR, both as a physical venue and in terms of institutional relations.

Unlike the actors discussed above, IIDEA occupies a structurally different position, situated outside the formal boundaries of the cluster. As the principal trade association representing the Italian video game industry, it performs functions related primarily to institutional representation and sectoral coordination at the national level. Although frequently depicted in unique visual forms, it is almost always placed beyond the ecosystem's perimeter and described as a relational interface connecting local actors with the broader national (and international) industry.

The main contribution attributed to IIDEA is the annual organisation of First Playable in Florence, the leading international event for video game developers in Italy. Despite its geographical distance from Turin, the event is sometimes symbolically represented within ecosystem mappings, reflecting the high level of recognition attributed to it. First Playable functions as the principal national meeting point, enabling interaction among developers, publishers, and investors across the Italian value chain. This further confirms that the Italian video game production industry is experienced primarily as a national system before being articulated into local clusters.

IIDEA, therefore, operates as an institutional actor embodying a form of action fundamentally different from that represented by IGDA. While both organisations facilitate relations among development studios, IIDEA acts as a highly institutionalised body engaged in policy advocacy and political representation, positioned above/outside direct ecosystem practices. IGDA, by contrast, represents bottom-up collective action grounded in voluntary participation, community building, and social cohesion: *“Yes, I use the circle, and I would like to point out that, from this point of view, there is also a double mandate between companies, which I will put in a triangle, which is IIDEA. So I'll put IIDEA in the triangle, because it is institutionalised. Or it goes in the institutionalised direction and talks to companies, while I'll put IGDA in the circle, because it's voluntary, it's a community, they are two profoundly different things that touch on two different spheres.”* (headmaster of a private school).

4.3.3 Cluster Perimeter

As shown in the previous deliverables, the perimeter of the Turin cluster appears to be partially defined and sufficiently clear in the minds of our respondents. In visual representations, interviewees consistently draw explicit boundaries separating actors recognised as belonging to the ecosystem from those positioned outside it, even when external actors maintain dense relational ties with local participants, as in the case of IIDEA. At the same time, the cluster lacks clearly delimited spatial borders. It cannot be reduced either to the administrative boundaries of the city of Turin or to those of its metropolitan area; rather, it encompasses all actors, institutions, and organisations that actively participate in its relational dynamics, regardless of geographical location.

The most emblematic example is represented by Broken Arms Games, a studio physically located outside the province of Turin yet consistently perceived as part of the cluster's core. Its positioning illustrates how belonging is defined less by territorial proximity than by participation in shared practices and networks: *"I'll start by writing Turin. Um, this circle is obviously Turin. I would divide them into sections, so let's start writing down some names: 34BigThings, Memorable, Tiny Bull, and technically, halfway through there's Broken Arms, which is halfway between the circle and outside and inside, because they are Turin, but let's say Turin and province."* (board member of IGDA Italy).

A similar, although less central, dynamic can be observed in the case of non-Piedmontese development studios that participated in the Quickload acceleration programme and subsequently maintained ongoing relationships within the ecosystem. These studios frequently occupy an intermediate position, neither fully internal nor entirely external, reflecting the permeability of cluster boundaries: *"Quickload brings others into the ecosystem, and there are already studios in the ecosystem that have already gone through Quickload and either entered from outside, which is why I leave them a bit in limbo, or are entering, or are transferring in some way. Not everyone who has gone through Quickload has obviously stayed in or transferred in. So, let's make an addendum of other studios that have not been transferred."* (board member of IGDA Italy).

Beyond the ecosystem's perimeter, interviewees clearly situate the broader Italian video game development landscape, including publishers and other industry actors. A distinction, therefore, exists between what *"constitutes"* the cluster and what merely *"interacts"* with it. However, these external realities are never perceived as disconnected or alien. Instead, participants consistently emphasise that video game production in Italy functions primarily as a national industry, within which local clusters represent secondary articulations.

Within visual mappings, IIDEA represents the only systematic exception to the binary distinction between *"inside"* and *"outside."* Its headquarters in Milan leads interviewees to position it physically outside the cluster's boundaries, yet its national scope and coordinating function place it in a collectively recognised bridging role linking local actors to both national institutions and the wider industry ecosystem: *"Hum, one last thing. I would put you down because, obviously, there is, in terms of organisation, I would put you down as IIDEA. Because, anyway, it's obvious that, on the subject we were talking about earlier, it's not in the area, but it interacts with everyone, basically. I mean, anyone who has anything to do with IIDEA, so even though, obviously, the trade association*

is not based in Turin, it's in Milan, but it has a strong presence in Turin. I mean, all the firms are members, and all the firms interact heavily with it.” (studio head).

The annual First Playable event, organised by IIDEA itself, further complicates the distinction between internal and external spaces. Although geographically located outside Turin, the event symbolically approaches the cluster's boundaries by creating a shared arena in which local developers engage with publishers, investors, and international actors. In this sense, First Playable blurs the divide between “local” and “national,” reinforcing the perception of the Italian industry as structurally integrated at the national level: *“Developers at First Playable can still get in touch with each other in some way. Then, with companies, even if it's not the right place, obviously, to get in touch with companies, or, simply, with international organisations. However, this thing unites us, in some way, with publishers and investors, let's call them WC, who are totally external, obviously, to the Turin cluster. If we want to... give a boundary to this thing here, I would say that, if this is the Turin cluster, publishers and WCs are completely outside, IIDEA is outside, but there is a tangentiality.” (studio head).*

Within this configuration, IGDA plays a fundamental – though only partially visualised – role in mediating relationships across scales. By linking its international organisational structure with local and national activities, IGDA provides the most comprehensive mechanism connecting the ecosystem's internal dynamics to external opportunities, extending beyond the scope offered by programmes such as Quickload. Together with IIDEA, it facilitates participation in national and international events, representing the principal gateway through which studios – particularly smaller teams with limited financial or infrastructural resources – can transcend the physical perimeter of the cluster. The provision of digital communication infrastructures, especially through IGDA's online channels, further amplifies this outward relational capacity.

At the institutional level, IIDEA's lobbying activities, including engagement with central political institutions, have become a crucial channel of dialogue for the national video game industry as a whole, effectively bypassing local territorial differences. Conversely, the absence of stable, continuous, and structured mechanisms of interaction with local public institutions in Turin has reinforced IIDEA's role as the primary formal representative of the sector, responsible not only for national advocacy but also for articulating issues emerging from individual regional ecosystems.

4.3.4 Value Chain

The value chain of video game development and production (Johns 2006; Kerr 2017), as represented in the case of Turin, appears both relatively complete and largely self-sufficient within the visual mappings produced by interviewees. All the components required for the cluster's active participation in the global video game industry are present: development studios ranging from highly structured companies to small independent teams; private (and public) training/educational institutions aimed at sustaining a local talent pipeline; and a set of predominantly private organisations that facilitate connections between internal and external actors, foster professional relationships, create both physical and digital spaces for interaction, provide infrastructural support, and organise networking and industry events.

The absence of locally based publishers – at both regional and national levels – may represent a potential structural constraint for the cluster. However, it is not widely perceived as such by interviewees, who tend to emphasise the centrality of digital distribution platforms as the dominant market standard. At the same time, the role of publishers remains significant, particularly in the context of the increasing oversaturation of the indie market, where they can provide visibility, funding, and strategic support. The presence of studios operating primarily within technological and B2B segments, together with specialised internal divisions within development studios devoted exclusively to service-oriented production (such as Game Thinkers at Tiny Bull Studios), expands the value chain beyond strictly creative production. This diversification broadens the ecosystem’s market reach while simultaneously strengthening mechanisms for talent attraction and retention within the wider cluster environment.

Despite this apparent completeness, neither the individual maps nor the final summary representation depicts a clearly structured or linear value chain. The cluster itself is not perceived by participants as an organised production sequence but rather as a relational ecosystem characterised by overlapping roles, informal exchanges, and multi-directional interactions. In a similar vein, the external acquisition of some major Turin-based studios by national or international companies¹⁰ is largely absent from the visual representations. While such acquisitions constitute indicators of industrial success and signal deeper integration into transnational markets – linking local studios to global networks operating under multinational holding structures – interviewees continue to perceive historic companies primarily as foundational actors of the ecosystem. These studios remain symbolically positioned at the “heart” of the cluster – or as half of it –, recognised for their role in its emergence, consolidation, and ongoing functioning, and are therefore represented as autonomous entities maintaining distinct organisational identities.

Within this configuration, IGDA Turin – together with IIDEA at the national level – operates as the principal relational infrastructure of the ecosystem. Through the interaction of long-established companies, community organisations, and individuals simultaneously active across multiple institutional contexts, these organisations enable the effective functioning of the local value chain despite its limited formalisation. A final element deserving attention concerns the recent inclusion of Poncle within the ecosystem. Although not explicitly confirmed by interviewees, its emergence raises questions regarding the cluster’s future trajectory, particularly in relation to its potential capacity for breakthrough success and its increasing attractiveness to institutions, investors, and external recognition. Nevertheless, as reflected in the visual mappings, the prominence attributed to this actor does not yet correspond to a consolidated or stabilised structural role within the cluster, remaining instead an indicator of possible future developments rather than an established transformation of the ecosystem.

¹⁰ External acquisitions within the cluster currently include: the acquisition of 34BigThings by Embracer Group in 2020; the acquisition of Dead Pixels by TPS Group in 2019; and the acquisition of a 49% stake in Memorable Games by uBroker in 2024.

4.4 Conclusions

The mapping exercise conducted within this task reveals a relatively young yet complex ecosystem, whose main components and relational dynamics are broadly shared and recognised by the interviewees. At the same time, the cluster remains in an ongoing phase of consolidation, shaped both by its relatively recent formation and by the volatility of market conditions that directly affect some of its most fragile components, particularly private training/educational institutions and smaller development studios. Consistent with the findings presented in **D4.1**, the core actors of the cluster and its operational mechanisms are largely reconfirmed, a continuity partly explained by the substantial overlap between the pools of respondents involved in the two deliverables. The resulting summary map therefore represents a coherent synthesis of an ecosystem characterised by clearly identifiable reference points, widely recognised by both founding and current actors and embedded within an increasingly consolidated process of collective identity formation. Although the value chain reconstructed through the analysis is not visually represented as a linear or formally structured system, it nevertheless confirms the cluster's present condition as functionally complete and largely self-sufficient. Compared with the analysis presented in **D4.1**, training/educational institutions – particularly private schools – appear to occupy a less prominent position in the visual representations. This reduced visibility can likely be attributed to recent sectoral uncertainties, including the crisis affecting Event Horizon School and the still recent establishment of Nash School. Despite this transitional phase, the latter appears to offer positive prospects in terms of educational continuity and qualitative stability, supported by the strong continuity of teaching staff and their close relationships with IGDA Turin and the development studios operating within the ecosystem. A key interpretative outcome of the mapping concerns the representation of the ecosystem's centre as a dual nucleus composed of historic development studios on the one hand and IGDA Turin on the other, collectively defined as the cluster's "double heart". This interpretation reinforces the recognised centrality of the four historic studios whose presence proved decisive in enabling the emergence and consolidation of the cluster's structure, which remains partially institutionalised and only semi-formalised. All these reflections reveal what can be defined as a "development studios-centric" cluster, with video game companies representing the past, present, and future of the ecosystem. Their sudden disappearance would probably mean the end of the entire local industry.

The subsequent emergence of IGDA Turin, occurring only a few years after the cluster's initial formation and building upon the foundations previously established by T-Union, can therefore be interpreted as a natural evolutionary step. The association introduced an internationally formalised organisational framework while simultaneously preserving the strong informal and community-oriented practices that have characterised the Turin ecosystem since its origins. Ultimately, the defining feature of the Turin video game development cluster lies in its actors themselves both organisations, development studios and individuals whose multiple and overlapping roles sustain the broader ecosystem and its value chain. Development studios, community organisations/events, training/educational institutions, and initiatives such as IGDA Turin and Quickload collectively form a relational infrastructure in which personal networks, shared practices, and long-standing community ties constitute the cluster's primary resource and its most distinctive structural characteristic.

5 BRNO

5.1 Overview of the Cluster

In the previous **WP4** deliverables, we have already observed that the Brno video game industry brings together various actors, including developers (in various sectors of video game production), educators, community organisers, and local government representatives. Brno game development community is considered relatively tight knit. This is, to an extent, the outcome of the studios' histories. Many of the local developers first connected by working on the same projects, facilitated by the success of Illusion Softworks and their partner studios. The founding of the Game Cluster organisation in 2020 formalised the existing developer community, which has coalesced around industry meet-ups and other events. The formal representation of the ecosystem helped secure government support and brings together various actors from companies to educators. Despite the formalisation through the founding of the Game Cluster organisation, the Brno game development community is still characterised by informal governance and volunteer labour. This can be seen in the structure of the Game Cluster organisation, which prioritises individual membership and does not require mandatory membership fees. This chapter builds on these previous findings by looking deeper at the relationships between key actors in the Brno video game ecosystem.

5.2 Data Collection

For the Brno video game industry cluster, we conducted 6 mapping interviews between June and October 2025. All of the sessions were done remotely and on average took 90 minutes. The interviews were recorded and transcribed for further analysis. Individual maps for each of the sessions were created using the collaborative digital whiteboard software Miro. All respondents were informed about the purpose of the mapping interviews and they signed consent forms.

When selecting the respondents, we were aiming to represent the diverse backgrounds of key stakeholders in the Brno video game industry ecosystem, including developers, educators, as well as community organizers. Out of the 6 respondents, 4 identified as men and 2 as women. This composition was caused by the gender disbalance within the ecosystem (and also the video game industry globally), which we had already noted in previous deliverables.

The CUNI team synthesised the six maps into one comprehensive map using the diagramming software Microsoft Visio and following the methodology outlined in chapter 2.1. The comprehensive map was further discussed during a workshop session with three representatives of the Brno video game industry ecosystem in December 2025. The three representatives also participated as respondents for the mapping sessions. As such, they were informed about the process behind the map's creation and understood its goals as well as its limitations. After the workshop, we remade the map in draw.io (also known as diagrams.net), which proved as a more practical and flexible tool given the complexity of the comprehensive map and the need for frequent adjustments, and implemented changes suggested during the workshop. The final map was confirmed in January via email correspondence with the three representatives. Overall, the mapping

of actors was an iterative process, and the Brno comprehensive map went through numerous versions before finally reaching the state presented in this chapter.

5.3 Actor Mapping

As outlined in the introduction to this report, the goal of actor mapping is to identify the main actors and projects within the cluster and highlight key relationships between them. The six respondents all brought their own subjective understanding of the personal and professional networks that connect together the various stakeholders and their activities. Based on the respondent's background, their individual maps highlighted their respective areas of interest and expertise. Based on these individual maps (see an example below, Figure 11) and interview transcripts, we created the comprehensive map.

Figure 11: Example of an individual actor map (Brno)

To achieve clarity and accessibility, the comprehensive map is inevitably a simplification of the many actors and the connections between them as can be also seen of Figure 11, which is, in some respects, more granular than the final comprehensive map (see Figure 12). Our goal was to highlight the important aspects of the Brno video game industry ecosystem, such as the key role of individuals over video game companies in facilitating many of the relationships, without losing the main features in an overly complex diagram. This is, for example, communicated through the node “key developers” instead of drawing a connection directly from the companies themselves. At the same time, to protect the privacy of our respondents as well as other individuals in the cluster, the map intentionally omits any names of individuals.

The map itself provides a quick glance at the actors in Brno as well as important events and collective actions, but additional explanation is provided in the following sections as to the nature of these actors and their relationships.

Figure 12: Final actor map (Brno)

5.3.1 Key Actors and Features

Meetups have a central position on our map of the Brno cluster and include regular meetups organized by GameDev Area. Under GDA.Network brand and platform, GameDev Area organises GameDev Area Meetups, two other ongoing meetups (GameDev Area Beer & Talk, Morning Restart by Game Access), and two conferences (Game Access, GameDev Connect; GameDev Area 2025). All these events take place in Brno. The limited liability company GameDev Area is owned and managed by Jakub Bedecs as the key cultural intermediary in the Brno community. GameDev Area Meetups are the longest-running regular meetups in the Brno community, taking place since 2014. These meetups are organised by Jakub Bedecs from GameDev Area and Zdeněk Záhora from MUNI, both being the founders of the Game Cluster organisation.

Such events are in the centre of the map due to their role of bringing together cultural intermediaries, educators, and game developers. Effectively, meetups and similar events are located at the intersection of these three groups, serving as their common meeting points. Key

cultural intermediaries who are the main organisers of regular meetups and conferences in Brno are also official members of the Game Cluster organisation. Nevertheless, conferences and meetups are also attended by individuals who are not members of the Game Cluster, and conferences are often co-organised by student volunteers outside of the Game Cluster organisation. Meetups and conferences thus function largely independently of the Game Cluster organisation and represent the core of the Brno game ecosystem. One of our respondents further underscored the importance of meetups for the local community: *“Some people attend the meetups and are much more active in the cluster than others who are formally listed as Game Cluster members. If someone wants to get involved, they simply come, participate, and it does not really matter whether they are officially part of the Game Cluster or not [...] If you go to the meetups, you’ll often pick up important information there anyway.”* Also, many of these meetups and conferences existed already for a few years before the Game Cluster’s establishment in 2020.

In fact, discussions about founding the Game Cluster organisation that would represent the interests of the Brno game community started at GameDev Area Meetups. Importantly, meetup discussions about launching the Game Cluster were joined not only by game developers and educators but also by employees of JIC (South Moravian Innovation Agency), which is the regional innovation agency. In the previous deliverable **D4.1**, we also described how non-profit and informal governance of GameDev Area Meetups is mirrored in Game Cluster governance and in its core values (De Paoli et al. 2025).

Other events organised by GameDev Area include Game Access and its game music concert spinoff. Game Access is an international game development conference that has been organised regularly since 2016, and it is largely held in English. Further, Game Access Music, which often takes place concurrently with the Game Access conference, is a live music performance of video game soundtracks, with some concerts played by the Brno Philharmonic Orchestra (GameDev Area 2026). GameDev Connect, as another conference organised by GameDev Area, is described together with educational institutions below due to its educational focus.

Another key game event in Brno is the Gamer Pie festival, which has been organised since 2016 and is aimed at the general public, bringing together *“gaming enthusiasts, developers, academics, and others interested in the medium of (not only) digital games”* (Gamer Pie, 2026). Gamer Pie was founded to popularise and promote games among the general public. Several respondents have noted how Gamer Pie helps in presenting video games as a “mainstream industry”, attracting the attention of people outside of the gaming industry or not acquainted with games. Gamer Pie is reportedly often attended by students or junior game developers. Notably, it was students from MU Game Studies who originally founded the Gamer Pie festival.

MU Game Studies is an NGO founded in 2009 and run by graduates and students of various disciplines of Masaryk University in Brno (MUNI), including the Faculty of Arts (FF), Faculty of Social Studies (FSS), and Faculty of Informatics (FI). In 2024, MU Game Studies experienced its revival, and a new wave of members started organising meetups. However, Gamer Pie is currently being organized independently of MU Game Studies (Gamestudies.cz 2025; MUNI 2025). MU Game Studies and Zdeněk Záhora were also initial points of contact for JIC when mapping the Brno game

industry for the Ministry of Culture. This led to subsequent discussions at GameDev Area Meetups between JIC and the Brno game community to establish the Game Cluster organisation (see also above).

Other events that bring together the Brno game development community are game quizzes co-organised by the main Gamer Pie organizers and Xzone employees. Xzone itself can be considered a cultural intermediary: a retailer (and also publisher) of game-related merchandise, video games, and board games. VisionGame is another important cultural intermediary. Its main project is a web archive and database of Czech and Slovak games and game makers. Xzone partners with Gamer Pie festival and VisionGame with Lektvar festival – these joint activities are described in Collective actions section below. It is important to note, however, that both Xzone and VisionGame are at the periphery of the Brno cluster perimeter, as they are rather nationwide actors and their activities are connected to the territories of foreign countries. In this regard, VisionGame collects data on both Czech and Slovak games and game makers as an archive that maps Czech and Slovak game history, and Xzone has stores in Austria, Germany, Hungary, Poland, and Slovakia (Mančář 2025; Xzone.cz 2024). Both Xzone and VisionGame representatives are, nonetheless, official members of the Game Cluster. Our respondents also described VisionGame as an important intermediary that collects data about the Brno game industry, which can be used by regional and city officials or JIC.

While meetups and events are meeting points for the Brno game development community and general public, the Game Cluster as an institution is a more formalised body that serves as a bridge between cultural intermediaries, educators and game developers, and which represents the interests of these actors. As one of our respondents said, *“People from these different areas are closer to one another in Brno. Whether it’s thanks to the Cluster, the GameDev Area, collaborations with universities, or developers actually taking part – coming to events or supporting them as partners. And these events include student initiatives, festivals, and cultural events; it’s all pretty interconnected.”* These connections also materialise during the Brno Game Jam, a 48-hour hackathon for making games organised by the Game Cluster, which has been held in the KUMST building every year since 2022. Local game developers and educators provide mentorship and feedback during the Brno Game Jam (Game Cluster 2022). The Brno Game Jam thus benefits from connections of Game Cluster with the Brno video game industry and educational institutions.

Within the video game industry, our respondents mapped key developers: CEOs or key employees of prominent game studios in Brno who are active within the Brno game community. Participants predominantly linked game studios to their CEOs, who were founding members of the Game Cluster, and to their employees, who are members of the Game Cluster. This way, participants highlighted that individuals are more important for the Game Cluster organisation than the companies they are employed by. The Game Cluster members participating in the mapping sessions thus reiterated the common values of the Game Cluster previously noted in **D4.1**, namely that its members do not represent the interests of the companies they work for, and do not push their companies’ interests in the Game Cluster (De Paoli et al. 2025).

Respondents mapped the major studios active in the Brno community, which range from larger studios to indie and small-sized studios. The oft-mentioned studios include mobile game companies

(i.e., Alda Games and Noxgames), Czech-owned companies (i.e., Bohemia Interactive, Madfinger Games), foreign-owned companies (i.e., Ashborne Games, GIANTS Software, Hangar 13, Ingame studios, Warhorse studios), the digital branch of a board game company (i.e., CGE Digital), and indie studios and developers, which include solo game developers (e.g., Jan Zelený and Mashinky) or small-sized studios (Brocap Studio, CBE Software). All studios are integral parts of the Brno game development community, as their employees participate in local meetups, game jams, and conferences, and as employees of some of those studios, who are usually members of Game Cluster, mentor teams in Gamebaze, and deliver lectures at the Gamebaze_course.

The third sphere of the Brno game community is represented by educational institutions, which include universities such as FFA BUT (Faculty of Fine Arts, Brno University of Technology), and MUNI (Masaryk University), and high schools such as SŠUD (Secondary School of Art and Design). Here, respondents mapped key educators who are leading the courses or game development programmes at FFA BUT, MUNI, and SŠUD and who are among the founders and members of the Game Cluster. These key educators also help in organising school game jams, student groups, festivals, and showcases of student games. Through membership of these key educators within the Game Cluster, the organisation includes educational institutions among its members, and game developers from the Game Cluster have better and direct access to events organised by schools, at which they usually act as mentors. However, before describing the activities of the educators and their students, it is worth introducing GameDev Connect and Lektvar as events that are closely tied to educational institutions.

GameDev Connect (formerly Game Access Connect) is a spin-off of the Game Access conference and is also organized by GameDev Area. GameDev Connect conference has existed since 2022 and, in contrast to Game Access, the majority of its programme is in Czech. Rather than being aimed at game developers like Game Access, GameDev Connect is aimed at the general public and especially students. The event is regularly attended by parents and their primary-school-aged children. As such, it is also visited by secondary school teachers looking for talented primary school students interested in game-making. For example, SŠUD regularly presents its Game Art programme and showcases its student projects at GameDev Connect. As one of our respondents puts it when describing GameDev Connect: *“When the event was first created, its subtitle would be ‘a gateway into the world of game development.’ The aim was to show people, in a popularising way, that you can make games here, and ideally also point them to schools where you can study game development.”*

Lektvar is a festival of student-made games that aims to document and showcase student game production and connect it with the art and creative industries (Žák 2025). Lektvar festival is organised by FFA BUT and Ateliér duchů. Students and graduates of the bachelor’s and master’s study program Game Media Studio at FFA BUT formed the collective Ateliér duchů to continue their authorial projects beyond semester assignments (VisionGame 2025). FFA BUT organises not only the Lektvar festival, but also Kompas, which is an exhibition of student games. The games presented at Kompas are not limited to those made by students from the Ateliér duchů collective at FFA BUT, but also include student games from other high schools and universities in Brno (Žák 2022). The scope of the Lektvar festival is even broader as it covers schools across the Czech Republic.

At MUNI, game-related courses are available at the Faculty of Arts (FF MUNI) and the Faculty of Informatics (FI MUNI). Faculty of Arts offers bachelor's and master's study programme Theory of Interactive Media and PhD study program Digital Culture and Creative Industries. The Faculty of Informatics offers a master's study program Visual Informatics. Zdeněk Záhora as one of the founding members of the Game Cluster was teaching at FF MUNI. His former students established the abovementioned association MU Game Studies and founded the Gamer Pie festival.

SŠUD Brno is a high school established by the South Moravian region (JMK), offering a study programme Game Art since 2021. Head of the Game Art program, Filip Dufka, is also a member of the Game Cluster, and he actively collaborated with game developers and regional officials when founding the programme. Initially, Filip Dufka received contact information on regional officials from JIC. As our respondent said: *“Game Art was the first real collaboration between JIC and the cluster – back when the Game Cluster didn’t formally exist yet. But within the working group focused on education, there was support for a secondary school to launch a new study program. And we pushed that with the help of the education department of the South Moravian Region. That was really the point where JIC became significantly involved.”*

The regional action plan, which funded the Game Art programme, aimed to connect schools with local employers to contribute to the education of teachers in the South Moravian region. Given this strategy, secondary school teachers from the later-established Game Art program were interns in local game studios such as Ashborne Games, GIANTS Software, or Hangar 13. After establishing the Game Art programme, local game studios provided internships for Game Art students. Game developers (often members of the Game Cluster) also mentor Game Art students in making their game projects. According to our respondent, the collaboration of SŠUD and local game studios under Game Cluster has been highly praised by regional officials: *“From what I’ve heard, regional officials see the Game Cluster as a good example of how schools and game studios can work together. We even came up in the ministry’s internal meetings as a model of how to do it right.”*

School game jams are also held at SŠUD, FFA BUT, and FI MUNI. Furthermore, showcases of student games or presentations of final games made by student teams are organized by all three schools. These showcases often take place at KUMST, where Gamebaze is located. Game Cluster members are usually present and give feedback to students from the three schools. Specifically, students from SŠUD present different games every half a year.

5.3.2 Collective Actions

One prominent joint activity in the Brno cluster is Gamebaze, located in the KUMST building in Brno. Currently consisting of co-work, courses, and an incubator, Gamebaze connects the Game Cluster, GameDev Area, and JIC (South Moravian Innovation Centre). Originally, Gamebaze was a project designed by Jakub Bedecs from GameDev Area. Jakub Bedecs also financed the first two years of Gamebaze’s operation during the project’s pilot phase. GameDev Area with its small team, which already organizes conferences and meetups, could, however, not sustain Gamebaze long-term. Bedecs thus decided to cooperate with partners from the Game Cluster and JIC. The three parties signed a memorandum of cooperation in 2023, and from that point, Gamebaze exists as a joint

project of the Game Cluster organisation, GameDev Area, and JIC. One of our respondents also stressed the link between establishing Game Cluster and Gamebaze: *“The start of Game Cluster went hand in hand with founding Gamebaze, because we wanted to have a partner to launch Gamebaze, and it would not be ideal if it were one game company.”*

Currently, JIC is the only actor that finances the Gamebaze space. Roman Hladík, as the chairman of Game Cluster, Jakub Bedecs, as the head of GameDev Area, and Radim Kocourek, as a deputy director of JIC, also meet every six months at strategic board meetings, during which they discuss whether the strategic vision of Gamebaze projects is being met, what the existing limits of Gamebaze are, and how to improve them.

The other connections between the actors can be traced to the internal functioning of Gamebaze itself. Specifically, members of the Game Cluster and game developers provide game production-related mentoring, and employees of JIC provide business-related mentoring to teams in the Gamebaze incubator. In 2025, Gamebaze_course was established as a third Gamebaze branch. Gamebaze_course is focused on roles and responsibilities in game development outside of the core triad (see Whitson et al. 2021), such as marketing, QA, finance, porting, or localisation. Gamebaze_course is a series of paid lectures given by Game Cluster members and game developers, and also by JIC employees. For example, the 2025 iteration of the Gamebaze_course hosted a lecture on accounting by a startup business consultant from JIC (Gamebaze 2025).

Lastly, the connections between JIC, the Game Cluster, and Gamebaze are in human resources. In fact, JIC formerly employed two members of the Game Cluster organisation in Gamebaze, and currently JIC employs the Game Cluster founder Zdeněk Záhora in Gamebaze. As mentioned above, the Game Cluster organisation was also launched with the help of JIC employees. As JIC employees are not official members of the Game Cluster organization, the connection between Game Cluster and JIC is rather loose.

JIC itself is represented on the perimeter of our Brno cluster map, in the sphere of local government with Brno City and JMK (South Moravian Region), as this is the area where JIC usually appears in six individual maps. JIC is a regional innovation agency founded by the City of Brno, the South Moravian Region, and Brno universities (including BUT and MUNI). Both Brno city and JMK fund JIC under a public service obligation. Since the Game Cluster members mostly communicate with JIC employees, JIC often acts as an intermediary in communication with the regional offices of JMK. The intermediary positions of JIC, both within local government and in communication with Game Cluster, are shown on our map.

Apart from connections between JIC, Game Cluster, and GameDev Area which formed Gamebaze, there are existing connections between Gamebaze, high schools such as SŠUD, and universities such as FI MUNI and FFA BUT. Student teams from the three schools that joined Gamebaze co-work or incubator include, for example:

- Liquid Squid, a student team from SŠUD, which developed Mourning Tide, and joined the Gamebaze co-work.
- Ateliér Duchů, a team of graduates from FFA BUT, which developed Repeat, and joined the Gamebaze incubator.

- Arbitrary Combination, a team of graduates from FI MUNI, which developed Omnibullet, and joined the Gamebaze incubator.

Although Gamebaze hosted more teams of university students, high school students from SŠUD are also encouraged to do individual internships at Gamebaze or join Gamebaze with their team. According to our respondent, both SŠUD and Gamebaze have a common aim to foster the growth of smaller game studios in Brno: *“Without Gamebaze, education at Game Art wouldn’t make nearly as much sense. And I say that because supporting the local game industry isn’t about feeding the local game studios with people but about creating the ecosystem for small companies as well – something we’re missing here in Brno. And that’s exactly why Gamebaze is such an important piece of the puzzle.”* However, Gamebaze has already hosted the developer from outside Brno – David Konečný, who commutes to Brno from Olomouc to consult his upcoming game Deadline Express at Gamebaze incubator. Gamebaze also has a Discord server, where game makers from across the Czech Republic share game development tips. In this sense, the Gamebaze community also extends beyond the cluster perimeter.

Finally, our respondents highlighted the specific importance of Gamebaze co-work. As a space where game developers of different levels of experience sit together, it facilitates regular encounters and potential long-term collaborations between game makers. In contrast with the Game Access conference, which takes place every year over a span of a few days, the Gamebaze co-work provides game makers with the opportunity to work next to each other over a longer period. Apart from Gamebaze, other collective actions include game development conferences such as GameDev Connect and Game Access. Both conferences receive funding from Brno City and JMK. Municipal and regional funding of both conferences is tied to Brno Creative Days, a series of events related to creative industries. According to our respondents, funding from game companies and personal connections of local game developers and cultural intermediaries with city and regional officials are important in supporting both the Game Access and the GameDev Connect conference. Kompas as an exhibition of student games organized by FFA BUT was also funded by Brno-city in 2022. The municipal funding covered two events. The first event was the Kompas exhibition itself in May 2022, which was covered by a subsidy program called Pro Kreativní Brno. The second event was a panel at the GameDev Connect conference in October 2022 on game development education, accompanied by a showcase of student games and an introduction to the Lektvar festival. The second event was funded under the Brno Creative Days program. The administration behind funding both Kompas events was done by individual members of Game Cluster.

Other events, such as Gamer Pie and Lektvar, rely on support from partners who help with organisation or provide conference spaces. Kino Art is thus both a partner and a venue for Gamer Pie, and the same can be said of KUMST for Lektvar. A notable partner for the Gamer Pie festival is Xzone, which makes Gamer Pie merchandise and provides prizes for the raffle. The close connection between Gamer Pie and Xzone is aided by the fact that a spouse of the main Gamer Pie organiser works at Xzone. Moreover, Gamer Pie is often sponsored by local game studios. In 2025, Gamer Pie was for example sponsored by Hangar 13. Lektvar is not sponsored by game studios as it is fully funded by BUT. A notable partner for the Lektvar festival is VisionGame which provides

organizational support. Lektvar is promoted at VisionGame websites, and the founder of VisionGame is often present in person at the Lektvar festival. VisionGame helps evaluate and archive student games showcased during the festival, aligning with Lektvar's aim of documenting student games made across Czechia (see Key actors' section above).

5.3.3 Cluster Perimeter

Outside of the cluster perimeter, the respondents mentioned local accelerators (i.e., Prague Game Accelerator) and foreign incubators and catalysts (i.e., SpielFabrique and Dutch Game Garden) related to Gamebaze, local developer association in the city of Ostrava called Game Devs Ostrava, and a nationwide game industry association called GDACZ. Further, we connected Prague Game Accelerator to GDACZ as one of its founders, and linked GDACZ with the Czech Audiovisual Fund (SFA), given the cooperation of GDACZ and Game Cluster on the law concerning the fund.

Within Czechia, Gamebaze is connected to the Prague Game Accelerator, a programme launched in August 2025 by the Prague Innovation Institute, the City of Prague, and GDACZ. Its goal is to foster young game developers, offering mentorship, funding, legal support, and business training (FEE CTU 2025). Gamebaze organisers communicate with Prague Game Accelerator organisers, exchange know-how, and keep track of their supported projects. Similar exchange of know-how happens between Gamebaze and Game Devs Ostrava, since Game Devs Ostrava plan to open an accelerator in Ostrava, also supported by the local innovation agency (see below).

Internationally, Gamebaze is connected to SpielFabrique and Dutch Game Garden. SpielFabrique is a Franco-German initiative that acts as a video-game ecosystem catalyst supporting indie game studios by providing business and management mentoring. They help local game ecosystems become international by incentivising cross-border co-productions and act as an accelerator/incubator for game start-ups (SpielFabrique 2025). Dutch Game Garden was an incubation programme located in Utrecht, Netherlands. Its mission was to support the Dutch games industry by providing affordable workspace, business mentoring, and networking opportunities to facilitate the growth of local studios. Dutch Game Garden discontinued its operations as of January 2025 (Dutch Game Garden 2024, 2025). Gamebaze sent its student teams to SpielFabrique accelerator and consulted its future plans with both Dutch Game Garden and SpielFabrique.

The Brno community is also connected with GameDevs Ostrava, a group representing the game development community in Ostrava. Specifically, there are existing connections between SŠUD, Gamebaze, and GameDevs Ostrava. As one of the requirements from JMK when establishing the Game Art programme, Filip Dufka was asked to map high schools offering game development courses across Czechia and make this mapping public. They called this mapping "Centrum herního vzdělávání" (Centre of Game Education). Dufka established a website related to this mapping, and even though funding from JMK covering the Center of Game Education ended after the first three years, the mapping continues. As part of this mapping, Game Cluster members Filip Dufka and Roman Hladík visited high schools and universities in Ostrava. Filip Dufka shared his experiences in leading the Game Art program in Brno with high school teachers in Ostrava, and both Dufka and Hladík visited the Technical University of Ostrava (VSB-TUO), where game development courses are

taught. They also got in touch with Game Devs Ostrava, since its founder worked as a deputy director at a private high school in Ostrava. As one of our respondents summarised these visits of Game Cluster members to other Czech cities: *“If any mapping or communication is taking place, it’s only at the level of basic community-building. And to me, that’s part of the Game cluster’s role – it has the responsibility to keep that overview [...] We need to be able to say that Brno is a game-development city – that’s kind of the Game cluster’s motto. So, we’ve got to know where you can study it and at what level.”* Due to time and financial constraints after the end of funding from JMK, Dufka started to cooperate with VisionGame. Dufka asked Miroslav Žák from VisionGame to put high schools with game development programs across Czechia on the VisionGame website.

Moreover, Game Devs Ostrava is trying to establish a video game cluster and launch an accelerator in Ostrava, with the help of Moravian-Silesian Innovation Centre as a regional innovation agency. Game Devs Ostrava attended Game Access, asking for guidance in establishing this accelerator. They were provided with contact information to Prague Game Accelerator and Gamebaze, with Gamebaze actively providing their know-how.

Finally, Game Cluster members are in contact with GDACZ as an organisation representing the Czech game industry. GDACZ is based in Prague and focuses on macro issues of the entire game industry in Czechia, while the Game Cluster organization is tied to the game development community, mostly based in the South Moravian region. While GDACZ is a more nation-wide actor, there is ongoing cooperation between GDACZ and the Game Cluster, as GDACZ communicates the needs of the Game Cluster to the Czech government. GDACZ and the Game Cluster also cooperated on transforming the Czech Film Fund into the Czech Audiovisual Fund (SFA), which came into effect in 2025 and was restructured to accommodate the newly introduced state support for animation and video games. In fact, many Game Cluster members are represented on the SFA boards. Jarek Kolář is on the managing board, David Šemík and Zdeněk Záhora are on the board for animation and video games, and Zdeňka Hubáček Kujová is on the board of infrastructure (ARAS, 2025). As one of our respondents pointed out about the high representation of Game Cluster members on SFA boards: *“That was the moment when the cluster’s strength really became visible – probably more than ever. We had a group of people representing different segments, and in the final vote, all the board members representing games were from Brno. We were able to bring real variety in the people involved.”*

5.3.4 Value Chain

In terms of the video game industry value chain (Johns 2006), the map shows the absence of publishers within the Brno cluster. Most of the companies focus on production or act as service providers as we have previously noted in **D4.2** (De Paoli et al. 2025b). IP ownership is a more complex question. Many studios operating in Brno are owned by larger companies and corporations headquartered outside the cluster (Ashborne, Bohemia Interactive, CGE Digital, GIANTS, Hangar 13, Warhorse). Several studios, however, currently self-publish their games based on their IP – Alda Games, Madfinger, or Noxgames. Smaller indie teams and solo developers also tend to produce their own games.

Additionally, the Brno cluster features important cultural intermediaries, which are located outside of core video game production, but contribute to the local system through other activities, such as by organising events or otherwise participating in them. These cultural intermediaries include the retailer Xzone, which also publishes merchandise, database of Czech and Slovak video games VisionGame, or GameDev Area, which hosts important conferences in Brno as mentioned in the previous sections of this chapter.

5.4 Conclusions

The mapping of actors confirmed some of the earlier observations about the informal governance within the Brno video game ecosystem from **D4.1** (De Paoli et al. 2025). The local ecosystem is characterised by the collaborations between video game developers, educators, students, and cultural intermediaries. Much of this interaction and networking happens out of individual interest and enthusiasm as evidenced also in the map – this nature of relationships is visualised by the three groups (key developers, key educators, and key cultural intermediaries), whose collaboration has been formalized in the Game Cluster organisation and is maintained through regular meetups, which according to our respondent represent the centre of the cluster. The links to local companies and institutions are often implied, but not always officially established in many cases; sometimes they are formalised through partnership in event organisation, including both international events like Game Access or festivals like Gamer Pie. Brno video game industry cluster actors are also connected to organisations outside this geographical location, this often happens through projects, such as the various accelerator and incubator programmes and their links to both national and international counterparts.

6 LYON

6.1 Overview of the Cluster

The Lyon video game cluster, explored in depth through previous deliverables (**D4.1**, **D4.2**, **D4.3**) (De Paoli et al. 2025; De Paoli et al. 2025b; Costalunga et al. 2026), constitutes one of the most structured regional game development ecosystems in Europe outside of national capitals. Its industrial legacy, robust educational infrastructure, and sustained public investment have positioned it as one of the most professional and best-funded regional video game development hubs in France. Located in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (AURA) region of France, the cluster’s distinctive trajectory is shaped by the legacy of Infogrames – once one of Europe’s largest video game publishers, headquartered in Lyon from 1983 until its effective dissolution in the mid-2000s. As documented in **D4.3** (Costalunga et al. 2026), the collapse of this anchor firm paradoxically generated conditions for what has been termed the “*creative diaspora*”: a wave of studio creation by former Infogrames employees that seeded the diversified ecosystem visible today.

The contemporary cluster is characterised by a structured density. It encompasses approximately +120 member entities within the Game Only association, the sector’s principal local professional association. The ecosystem includes several subsidiaries of global AAA publishers, a constellation of mid-size independent studios, and a substantial base of micro-studios and pre-revenue startups. The educational infrastructure is exceptionally dense, comprising public university programmes, private schools, and cross-sector institutional actors. Game Only, which succeeded the defunct Imaginove association in 2019, provides the institutional connective platform that links these actors across size, type, and genres.

D4.2 (De Paoli et al. 2025b) demonstrated a concentration of activity across the Lyon Métropole with particular density in the Villeurbanne and central Lyon arrondissements. **D4.3** (Costalunga et al. 2026) traced the institutional evolution from Lyon Infocité and Lyon Games (the original associations) through Imaginove (a broader creative industries cluster that failed to serve the video game sector specifically) to Game Only (a deliberately gaming-specific association whose statutes were designed to avoid its predecessors’ failures). This trajectory of institutional learning through failure is a defining feature of the Lyon cluster and informs many of the dynamics observed in the present actor mapping exercise.

6.2 Data Collection & analysis

The present task provided an opportunity to expand the sample of actors significantly beyond those interviewed for **D4.1**, with a particular focus on capturing the full range of actor types present in the cluster, including educational institutions, cross-sector cultural intermediaries, and micro-studios at the earliest stages of development.

In line with the proposed methodology outlined in the introductory chapter, researchers conducted semi-structured mapping interviews using four tailored interview guides for (a) studios, (b) public

fundere and institutions, (c) training and education actors, (d) and professional associations. Prior to the interview phase, the research team developed an initial conceptual map of the Lyon cluster informed by D4.1 and D4.2 and considering actor centrality and inter-actor relationships. This map served as an initial framework enabling comparison with individual interviewee maps.

Table 1: Interview corpus for Lyon/AURA cluster

#	Entity	Type	Informant	Role	Duration	Notes
1	Studio A	Micro-studio (pre-revenue, mobile)	GF	Cofounder/CEO	~45 min	3 non-gaming cofounders
2	Studio B	Services & international production	CC	Director/founder	~50 min	~140 employees, two continents
3	Studio C + School C	Indie studio + private school	BA, AB	Director (studio), Director (school)	~55 min	School-studio integration model
4	Studio D	Indie studio (serious games, mobile)	SB	Founder/consultant	~48 min	30-year career, ex-Infogrames era
5	Studio E	AAA subsidiary (racing)	EO, JR	Cofounding director, HR manager	~60 min	283 employees, founding Game Only member
6	Studio F	Micro-studio (pre-revenue, indie)	AG	Cofounder/producer	~50 min	3 cofounders, all employed elsewhere
7	Studio G	AAA subsidiary (action/immersive sim)	AZ	VP / Dir. of Operations	~48 min	~200 employees. 2nd interview
8	Studio H	Indie studio (game for change, SCOP)	JC	Artistic Dir. / Cofounder	~56 min	Worker cooperative. 2nd interview
9	Studio I	Publisher + internal studio	MS	HR Director (sole HR, Lyon + Paris)	~47 min	Paris publishing, Lyon production
10	Institution J	Public university (game formation)	DP	Professor / Head of formation	~50 min	~65 students/year, <€200/year
11	Institution K	Private school (multi-campus)	NV	Corporate Relations Dir.	~57 min	~1,600 students, 3 campuses

12	Institution L	Cross-sector ICC hub	GFa	Director	~44 min	Cinema, animation, JV, hybrid arts
13	Institution M	Animation ICC / international market	YE, TC, LW	Director, Programme Dir., Video Games Lead	~55 min	Annecy. MIFA market

Informants were identified through Game Only referrals, snowball sampling from initial contacts, and purposive targeting of actor types underrepresented in previous deliverable samples. The final contact list included 29 people, of whom 17 were interviewed between March and April 2026.

The final sample encompassed: 7 studio spanning from pre-revenue micro-startups (3 cofounders, all employed elsewhere) to AAA subsidiaries of global publishers (200+ employees); 3 educational institutions representing the full spectrum from public university to large private multi-campus school; and 2 cross-sector institutional actors (a cross-ICC hub and an animation-anchored institution engaging with the video game sector).

From the sample mobilized during **D4.1**, only three companies are redundant. However, the three informants encountered during this second round of interviews are different from those encountered during the first round of interviews, thus helping to capture complementary perspectives within their organisations: for a major studio a first interview with a founder covered creative identity and history, while a second interview with a VP/Director of Operations covered institutional engagement and financial dynamics. For a smaller studio, a first interview with the former HR director covered HR operations, while a second with the artistic director and co-founder covered the studio’s governance, cluster solidarity, and social dialogue. For a third mid-size studio, combining subcontracting with the development of its own games, we encountered different cofounders. This report triangulates findings from 17 distinct informants spanning the full spectrum of the Lyon/AURA video game cluster. To preserve informant anonymity while enabling traceable citation, each entity is assigned a number, and each informant is identified by their initials. Citations follow the format: initials, entity number, and a short descriptor in parentheses, e.g., (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary).

Individual maps were created for each informant using SVG-based digital mapping, following guide conventions. Each map placed the informant at the centre and positioned other actors across three concentric zones (centre, periphery, outside the cluster). The individual maps were then triangulated through an iterative process. Researchers first compiled the individual maps into a draft synthesis, identifying recurring actors and relationships. This draft was refined through analytical discussion within the research team, cross-checking actor positions and relationship types against the full interview corpus. In the final map, line thickness reflects the frequency of independent confirmation across informants: thus, actors which were discussed more frequently appear with thicker connecting lines and more central positioning. The triangulation follows the rule of number: findings reported by multiple independent informants across different actor types carry the highest evidentiary weight. Findings specific to one category of actor are contextualised as such.

6.3 Actor Mapping

The comprehensive cluster_map (**Figure 15**) synthesises the subjective centrality assessments of all 17 informants into a single visual representation. **Figures 13 and 14** present two examples of individual maps produced during the mapping sessions, illustrating actors occupying different roles within the cluster – a studio founder and an institutional actor, respectively. These examples demonstrate how different positions within the ecosystem generate different perceptions of centrality and relational proximity: the studio founder places Game Only at the centre of their relational world, while the institutional actor emphasises the connections between meta-organisations, governmental bodies, and cross-sector actors.

Figure 13: Example of an individual map (Lyon; studio perspective)

Mapping of Pôle Pixel's relational network – Lyon/AURA cluster

Ego-network reconstructed from G. Farage interview (30/03/2026) – GAME-ER T4.4

Figure 14: Example of an individual map (Lyon; institutional perspective)

The comprehensive map, presented in **Figure 15**, reveals a strongly hub-centred topology. Game Only emerged as the single most central actor – mentioned by all informants as essential to the ecosystem's functioning. The map is organised according to the three concentric zones (Centre, Periphery, Outside the cluster) established in the general methodological guide, with shapes following the established conventions (squares for studios, rounded rectangles for professional associations, hexagons for governmental institutions, ellipses for events/programmes).

Figure 15: Final actor map (Lyon)

Despite the inevitable representational reduction inherent in any synthesis of heterogeneous individual perspectives, the comprehensive map offers a coherent visual overview of the ecosystem, its principal actors, and their relational dynamics. The written analysis below provides further detail about the actors and relationships shown on the map. **Table 2** summarises also the main categories and subcategories of actors included in the map.

Table 2: Categorization of Lyon cluster actors

Category	Sub-category	Actors	Sub-category description
Video Game Industry	<i>AAA anchor tenants (Studios & Developers)</i>	Ivory Tower (Ubisoft), Arkane Lyon, Ubisoft Annecy	Large studios integrated into major international groups (Ubisoft, Microsoft/Bethesda). They provide stability, international visibility, and a senior-talent anchor for the cluster.
Video Game Industry	<i>Mid-size independent studios</i>	Old Skull Games, Ocellus, Million Victories, Artifact Studio, Eden Games, New Tale	Independent mid-size studios – the productive ‘engines’ of the cluster. They combine console/PC, tactical and serious-games production. Most are “heirs” of the Infogrames creative diaspora.
Video Game Industry	<i>Micro-studios & indie developers</i>	Dowino, Tiny D.F., Gaméléon, çapartenprod, From the French, and other indie studios & freelancers	Small studios, freelancers and service providers. Central to the cluster by involvement, main beneficiaries of the big-small solidarity mechanism structured by Game Only.
Video Game Industry	<i>Editors (extra-cluster)</i>	Nacon, Microïds, Plug-In Digital	National-scale publishers located outside the AURA perimeter but structurally connected to Lyon studios through co-production and financing relationships. --Not members of Game Only but key stakeholders.
Cultural Intermediaries	<i>Regional cluster association (central meta-org)</i>	Game Only	Successor of Imaginove (2019). Central professional association of the AURA video games cluster: +120 members, 8 structured functions (training, export, HR, finance, governance). Unanimous centrality in interviews.
Cultural Intermediaries	<i>Game Only programmes & events</i>	GO Day, Club Fin., Club RH, Let’s Go Incubator, Bertie (training)	Programmes and flagship initiatives structured by Game Only: annual flagship event (GO Day), finance and HR peer-clubs, the “Let’s Go” incubator, and Bertie — the in-house training structure (~€1.9 M budget) illustrating institutional entrepreneurship.
Cultural Intermediaries	<i>Grassroots developer community</i>	Lyon Game Dev	Community-led association (~22 paying members, 700+ sympathisers). Monthly meetups, symbolic budget sustained by volunteer work – illustrative of the benevolent economy underpinning associative life in the cluster.
Cultural Intermediaries	<i>Cross-sector creative & innovation hubs (CCI)</i>	Minalogic, Pôle Pixel, CITIA / MIFA (Annecy), Le Damier (Clermont-Ferrand)	Cross-sector creative-industries and deep-tech hubs inside the AURA perimeter (image, VFX, animation, digital innovation). Peripheral relays of Game Only Asymmetric complementarity rather than dual hubs
Cultural Intermediaries	<i>Regional professional associations / programmes</i>	Game In, Capital Games, So Games, Push Start, Spielfabrique, France Clusters	Peer regional / national cluster organisations (Bordeaux, Paris, Montpellier, France-wide and European programmes). -They connect Game Only to the wider French and EU VG cluster network for knowledge exchange, joint actions and advocacy.
Educational institutions	<i>VG-specialised public programmes</i>	Gamagora (Université Lumière Lyon 2)	-Public university with track dedicated to VG. -Long-standing talent pipeline, close to studios via internships, student showcases and game jams. -Key stabilising element of the public training offer.
Educational institutions	<i>Private VG schools</i>	Gaming Campus, Game Sup, Ynov Lyon	-Private higher-education schools dedicated to VG design, development, business and e-sport.

			-They provide talent supply – but also fuel the ‘school overproduction’ tension documented in interviews.
Educational institutions	<i>Art, animation & computer graphics</i>	École Émile Cohl	-Complementary talent pipeline from graphics, illustration and animation -It feeds the broader AURA VG and animation industries (art roles, character design, 2D/3D).
Educational institutions	<i>Student–industry bridging events</i>	Game Jams, Student showcases	-Recurring cross-school events (game jams, end-of-year showcases) that articulate the talent pipeline with studios and Game Only. -It constitutes a structured interface between education and industry.
Local & Regional Government	<i>Regional / metropolitan authorities</i>	Région Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, Métropole de Lyon	-Main public funders and institutional supporters. -Regional dedicated fund (~€800 K, grants €30–80 K per project); Métropole active since the Lyon Infocité era. -Strong operational alignment with Game Only.
Local & Regional Government	<i>Municipal authority (blocked relationship)</i>	Mairie de Lyon (Blocked 6 yrs)	-Documented 6-year blockage with the city of Lyon in the working relationship with the cluster — marked as a red ‘blockage’ arrow on the map. A notable exception to otherwise supportive local-government dynamics.
Local & Regional Government	<i>Regional employment & social partners</i>	ATLAS / AFDAS, DREETS	-Sector skills-fund operators (ATLAS, AFDAS) and deconcentrated state labour administration (DREETS). -Partners of Bertie and Game Only on training-plan financing and sector skills observation.
National Government	<i>National funding agencies</i>	CNC / CIJV, BPI / CDC	-National public funders: CNC (FAJV, CIJV tax credit – Lyon’s FAVJ success rate reaches 40% vs 15% nationally); -BPI France and Caisse des Dépôts (equity, loans, innovation grants, guarantees).
National Government	<i>National programmes & skills coordination</i>	France 2030, COEF Numérique	-France 2030: national innovation and infrastructure plan (supports R&D and deep-tech projects). -COEF Numérique: regional skills contract aligning training supply with industry needs.
National / International Syndicates	<i>National industry unions</i>	SNJV, SELL	-National professional unions: SNJV (French VG companies), SELL (French VG publishers). -Relationship with Game Only sometimes tense.
National / International Syndicates	<i>Employee union</i>	STJV (Pandora’s box)	-National VG workers’ union. -Limited formal integration into the cluster – illustrates a social-dialogue deficit. -Referred to by several interviewees as a ‘Pandora’s box’ for cluster governance.
National / International Syndicates	<i>European federation</i>	EGDF	-European Games Developer Federation. Supra-national advocacy and policy-coordination body; indirect connection to Lyon studios mostly mediated by SNJV.

The map and the summarising table confirmed several findings from previous deliverables while revealing new dimensions. Game Only’s centrality, first identified in **D4.1** as the cluster’s institutional core with a service portfolio organised around four strategic axes (financing, export, recruitment, training), is reconfirmed and enriched with relational detail.

The three-tier studio taxonomy, the educational infrastructure density, and the cross-sector connections through Pôle Pixel and CITIA all emerge as structural features visible across most individual maps. A key feature distinguishing the Lyon map is the density of institutional mechanisms layered beneath the studio-level ecosystem. Game Only's service architecture – Let's Go incubation, Club RH, Club Finance, CNC dossier peer review, Slack/Discord mutual aid, international delegations – creates a multi-channel support system that smaller studios cannot generate independently. This infrastructure is further extended through Game Only's relationships with peripheral institutional actors such as Pôle Pixel (cross-sector ICC hub), Minalogic (technology cluster), and Le Damier (Clermont-Ferrand ICC hub), which provide complementary services without diluting Game Only's gaming-specific focus.

From a historical point of view, five independent informants confirm the Infogrames spin-offs as the foundational resources of the Lyon cluster – one that not only seeded the contemporary studio landscape but also laid the relational foundations that continue to sustain the ecosystem today. An indie studio manager (SB- #4, indie studio) whose 30-year career began inside Infogrames, confirms: *"Everything started from Infogrames"*. An AAA subsidiary director (Dir., #5) traced a direct genealogy: *"The first 35 employees of [the studio] came from Eden Games,"* while the HR manager from the same company (JR, #5) observed that *"as everyone comes from Infogrames and there has been a lot of spin-offs we are several studios making racing games."* A studio director (BA, #3, studio-school) began his career by selling scenarios to Infogrames in 1996–97. A cofounder of a studio (AG, #6, micro-studio) summarised the legacy from a newcomer's perspective: *"You can't say Lyon without Arkane, Ivory Tower, Artifact, Old Skull Games. Before that, there's Infogrames, now Atari. Other studios came from those."* Even the educational infrastructure bears the imprint: A professor (DP, #10, public university) described how his programme's original industry connector – a former Professeur Associé who was *"old guard from Infogrames"* – had provided the address book that linked the university to the studio world. The creative diaspora thesis documented in D4.3 (Costalunga et al. 2026) is thus confirmed through first-person triangulation. The racing game specialisation cluster-within-the-cluster (Eden Games → Ivory Tower → Tiny Digital Factory → Kylotonn → Artifact/motorbike) demonstrates thematic continuity – competence DNA propagating across independent entities. More importantly, the personal relationships forged inside Infogrames and its successors constitute the relational substrate upon which Game Only and the cluster's solidarity culture were later built: people who worked together across multiple companies over decades created the *"small world"* in which *"everyone knows everyone with one degree of separation"* (JC, #8, SCOP studio).

6.3.1 Key Actors and Features

The Lyon cluster brings together diverse actors whose interactions collectively define the ecosystem's structure and dynamics. Understanding not only who these actors are but how they interact is essential to grasping the cluster's relational architecture. The actor census established through **D4.1** and **D4.2** identified six main categories and +120 member companies; the **T4.4** mapping both confirms this composition and adds relational depth to the categories through subjective centrality assessments.

6.3.1.1 Video game studios

The studio landscape exhibits a three-tier structure that was independently described by informants across different categories and confirmed through triangulation.

Tier 1 – International subsidiaries (stabilisers): At the apex, two AAA subsidiaries of international publishers – Arkane Studios (#7, Microsoft/Bethesda/ZeniMax, approximately 200 employees, average age 36–37) and Ivory Tower (#5, Ubisoft, 283 employees including approximately 100 external contractors) – serve as anchor firms. Satellite offices of Electronic Arts and Bandai Namco also operate in Lyon. Ubisoft established also a studio in Annecy, which is part of the AURA region. These studios are productively hermetic: their value chains operate entirely within their respective publisher groups, and they do not engage in local co-production, publishing, or distribution partnerships. As one studio executive explained: *“We are a development studio. We have a publisher who handles the publishing, commercial, and marketing. We remain a studio – we are a cost centre, we create a product.”* (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary) Despite this productive hermeticism, these anchor firms are deeply engaged institutionally: Arkane’s VP sits on the Game Only board and participates in SNJV subsidy commissions; Ivory Tower is a founding member of Game Only, hosts the annual Faculty Night for educational institutions, and its HR team actively participates in the Club RH. Ubisoft Annecy is also member of Game Only.

The logic underpinning this institutional engagement was articulated with clarity: *“If we have many studios or schools in our region, that assures us a pipeline of well-trained resources who can eventually come to the two big Lyon actors.”* (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary) This framing – talent pipeline as strategic self-interest – distinguishes the anchor studios’ engagement from the solidarity narrative prevalent among smaller studios. A founding member described it differently: *“We pay the membership and don’t expect ROI [return on investment]. For conferences and summits, we go via Ubisoft, not via Game Only. It’s better that small studios benefit from this. We give more than we receive.”* (Dir., #5, AAA subsidiary). The behaviour is identical; the framing reveals different organisational cultures. Through their global networks, anchor studios provide resources and knowledge for local talent and indirectly set standards within the ecosystem. The **D4.1** analysis identified this asymmetry as a structural feature of the cluster and the **T4.4** interviews confirm it while revealing that the asymmetry is experienced not as domination but as a functional division of roles

Tier 2 – Mid-size independents (engines):

The second tier comprises mid-size independent studios, described by one institutional actor as *“the engines of our structures, because our boards are composed of leaders of this calibre”* (GFa, #12, ICC hub). These studios – including Old Skull Games (70–90 employees), Million Victories (significant mobile studio with a major fundraising round), DOWINO (approximately 15–20 employees, organised as a worker cooperative), Artifact (17 years of operation), Ocellus (approximately 140 employees across two continents), and Eden Games – are the principal drivers of employment, R&D, and governance participation. Their engagement in collective action is bidirectional: they both contribute to and benefit from Game Only’s services. Several are represented on the Game Only board, and their directors provide expertise in HR, finance, artistic, and legal matters. Mature

creative studios maintain collaborations and partnerships with publishers in other clusters such as Bordeaux, Montpellier, and Paris (Arte, Plugin Digital), creating inter-cluster productive links. As an example, the **D4.1** involvement centrality analysis identified DOWINO as an actor whose collective action engagement significantly exceeds its economic weight – a finding that the **T4.4** interviews confirm through concrete evidence of unpaid mentorship, CNC dossier review, and school teaching. A distinctive organisational form within this tier is its SCOP (Société coopérative et participative) model (employees can request to become cooperative shareholders with equal voting rights regardless of capital contribution). Another specific case is New Tales/Emeteria, a publisher-developer hybrid which combines Paris publishing (400–700 studio applications/year) with Lyon production – a rare local publishing function.

Tier 3 – Young/fragile studios and micro-startups: such as çapartenprod (cofounders all employed elsewhere), Gameleon (cross-subsidised by Game Sup), and Let’s Go cohort studios. They are the primary beneficiaries of Let’s Go, the local incubator dedicated to video games companies, Slack/Discord mutual aid, subsidised event access, and mentorship. The **D4.1** analysis noted the Let’s Go incubator’s role in ensuring a continuous pipeline of new entrants with performance metrics; the **T4.4** mapping adds the relational dimension – Let’s Go generates lasting social bonds (friendships, document exchange, mutual feedback) that persist well beyond the programme’s formal duration.

Inter-studio relationships in the Lyon cluster are characterised by a productive paradox: dense social connectivity and strong mutual solidarity coexist with an almost complete absence of productive collaboration. Studios do not co-produce games, co-develop technologies, or share IP. As one CA member observed: *“in video games, it’s more closed than in animation cinema, where on a feature film there are several studios, producers, countries. In gaming, at the big studios, lots of secrets – it happens under the surface.”* (JC, #8, SCOP studio). What studios do share intensively is operational knowledge – production management methods, subsidy application strategies, HR practices, financial management tools – everything except the game itself: *“We can’t share our projects because of IP/NDA, but we share a lot about how we manage our projects, how we find subsidies, how to do the documentation.”* (AG, #6, micro-studio). This sharing occurs primarily through Game Only’s channels (Slack, clubs, events, Let’s Go) rather than through bilateral studio-to-studio relationships. The **D4.1** analysis characterised this as the *“coopetition paradox”* – collective action among competing firms – and traced its roots to the Digital Worlds project failure (2003), which revealed firms’ reluctance to invest in initiatives that simultaneously promote their competitors. The **T4.4** evidence shows that Game Only’s pragmatic service orientation (focusing on non-competitive collective goods) has largely resolved this paradox at the operational level.

The primary competitive arena between studios is the labour market, not the product market. Four informants independently converge on this finding: *“The competition between studios is not about games – it’s about labour.”* (BA, #3, studio-school) *“We are competitors on the employment market, not on products.”* (Dir., #5, AAA subsidiary) The salary gap is a structural barrier for attracting non-creative profiles (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary). One studio’s exceptionally low attrition (~1-2% over 15 years) is attributed to project diversity and creative autonomy rather than compensation (CC, #2, services studio). However, this labour market competition is tempered by a norm of inter-studio

mobility experienced as natural rather than adversarial: people move between studios across their careers, creating a tightknit relational web. In the most generous expression of this norm, Old Skull Games actively helps its own employee (a co-founder of a micor studio, #6) create a competing studio – facilitating employee entrepreneurship as part of the cluster’s social contract rather than treating it as a competitive threat. The **D4.1** analysis had identified talent pipeline pressures and the Club RH/QVT (Human resources / Quality of Working life Club) initiatives as responses; the **T4.4** evidence reveals the depth of the underlying cultural norm that makes this cooperation possible despite competitive pressures.

Beneath this competitive-cooperative tension lies a cross-subsidisation mechanism that four informants from different positions describe independently. *“The majority of actions benefit small studios – organising a delegation, fighting at CNC for subsidies. I don’t know if it’s because people in big studios worked in small studios, or because they love video games and know it’s alive in its creative plurality, probably both.”* (JC, #8, SCOP studio) From the large studios’ perspective, the framing varies but the behaviour is consistent: *“It’s better that small studios benefit. We give more than we receive.”* (Dir., #5, AAA subsidiary) Another respondent offered the most strategically candid framing: *“If we have many studios or schools in our region, that assures us a pipeline of well-trained resources.”* (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary) From the receiving end: *“When they say something, we attach to it because they know a lot.”* (AG, #6, micro-studio) The mechanism is neither contractual nor explicit – it is a cultural norm sustained by a mixture of enlightened self-interest, professional empathy (many leaders of large studios built their careers in small ones), and a shared conviction that creative diversity is intrinsically valuable.

A notable refinement of this solidarity picture concerns the inverse relationship between financial contribution and voluntary engagement. Large studios pay the highest Game Only membership fees – *“it’s thanks to the fees of the big studios that Game Only makes ends meet,”* (JC, #8, SCOP studio) – yet it is the smaller and mid-size studios that are the most active on a voluntary basis in collective action. Let’s Go mentorship is provided by indie founders: JC (#8) has mentored for 3–4 years unpaid; CC (#2) hosts incubated teams in studio space and provides free mentorship. CNC dossier review, Slack mutual aid, and school interventions are mainly driven by smaller actors who give their time freely. Large studios contribute legitimacy, financial weight, and political credibility – *“if it’s a big studio, it carries weight in front of politicians,”* (JC, #8) – while smaller studios contribute the operational volunteerism that makes the collective action machinery run day to day. This complementary duality – financial contribution from above, voluntary labour from below – is the engine of the cluster’s solidarity model.

This duality rests on a broader cultural foundation: a pervasive economy of freely given professional help that several informants described as *“bénévolat”* (voluntary and benevolent work): *“There’s a lot of “bénévolat” – at Let’s Go, interventions are always free. It’s our time that we give.”* (AG, #6, micro-studio) *“I’ve never had someone say no.”* (GF, #1, micro-studio) *“Without the HR Club, I’d have to pay lawyers. Now I just call another HR and they give me the information.”* (MS, #9, publisher-studio) The *“bénévolat”* economy is not a programme but a cultural norm reproduced through participation. It is sustainable because it is reciprocal – everyone gives and receives at different moments – and because the cluster’s critical mass absorbs individual variation: when one studio is

too busy to contribute, others fill the gap. Studios share production management knowledge, subsidy application know-how, and HR practices despite IP/NDA restrictions on game content.

6.3.1.2 Educational institutions

The Lyon cluster’s educational infrastructure is exceptionally dense and typologically diverse, comprising three distinct models plus a key arts school. Educators are professionals from video game development studios, publishers, and other companies in the sector. Educational institutions update their offerings according to the needs of the video game industry. The **D4.1** analysis identified the education–industry interface as being increasingly institutionalised through Game Only partnerships with structured pathways for internships, curriculum input, and graduate recruitment; the **T4.4** interviews provide granular detail on how these pathways function in practice.

The public university model is represented by Gamagora, a training program within the University Lyon 2, offering three tracks (M2 programming, L3 level design, L3 infographie 3D) to approximately 65 students per year at fewer than 200 euros annually. Embedded in a research laboratory, Gamagora provides technically rigorous and affordable training but operates under institutional constraints: no alumni tracking system, limited direct industry contacts following the departure of a key intermediary, and a location in the ex-centred campus of Bron.

The private school-studio integration model is represented by Game Sup, whose co-location with a production studio (Gameleon) creates a circular pipeline in which students, graduates, practitioners, and teachers rotate through interconnected roles. *“Every day, if we have a question or a problem, there’s someone at the studio we can ask.”* (AG, #6, micro-studio/teacher)

The multi-campus private school model is represented by Gaming Campus, the largest educational actor locally with approximately 1,600 students across three campuses (Lyon headquarters, Paris, Bordeaux). Founded specifically to address the gaming business employment gap, Gaming Campus operates 100% project-based learning with approximately 120 studio professionals rotating annually as instructors, each delivering real studio briefs. Annual programme development committees of 10–12 industry experts per campus provide formalised curriculum adaptation.

Arts school and notably École Émile Cohl serve as a key feeder for art profiles. Multiple studios mention Émile Cohl alumni as a primary source of artistic talent. Several informants teach there: DOWINO, for example, supports Émile Cohl by providing experts for teaching, updating video game curricula, and supporting final academic projects.

The school-studio relationship is bidirectional: studios provide practitioner-teachers, real project briefs, internships, alternance placements, and advisory input through committees or informal feedback; schools provide trained graduates for recruitment. The geographic reach of graduate placement extends beyond the Lyon cluster: Gamagora places approximately 40–50% of graduates in the region, with the remainder distributed nationally and, occasionally, internationally (Canada, Japan). Gaming Campus’s three-campus model creates inter-cluster placement flows to Paris and Bordeaux. The **D4.1** analysis noted that Bertie – a training programme developed jointly by Game Only (Lyon) and Capital Games (Paris) – demonstrates inter-cluster collaboration in human capital development; the **T4.4** mapping adds further examples of such cross-cluster educational flows. Ivory

Tower’s Faculty Night – an annual event inviting all schools to discuss needs and run workshops – is also a structured mechanism for aligning training supply with industry demand.

All educational actors share one concern: school overproduction. *“Too many schools, too many young people on the market. Many young people are indebted, graduated, and can’t find work.”* (GFa, #12, ICC hub) *“Lots of schools open just for the money.”* (CC, #2, services studio). The training pipeline produces more graduates than the industry can absorb, with disproportionate impact on non-programming specialisations. The CNC president’s call for school regulation is endorsed by institutional actors. The **D4.1** analysis noted the SNJV’s training labelling program (established 2010) as an attempt to standardise educational quality; the **T4.4** evidence suggests that this labelling has had limited impact on the proliferation of low-quality programmes.

6.3.1.3 Cultural intermediaries and cross-sector actors

The category of cultural and institutional intermediaries encompasses, in our analytical framework, a set of meta-organisations whose common function is to mediate between video game actors and adjacent fields – regardless of their legal status (association, publicly-owned company, mixed-economy entity, State-labelled cluster) or financing structure (public subsidies, members’ fees, rental income, competitive R&D funding). We have deliberately grouped these actors together because their functional contribution to the cluster – matchmaking, cross-sector bridging, political access, event-based visibility, innovation brokering – matters more, from the video game actors’ perspective, than the juridical form through which they operate.

Apart from Game Only, one active intermediary is Pôle Pixel, a dual-identity organisation (physical site since 2001, association since 2015) based in Villeurbanne. It operates as a cross-sector hub for cinema, animation, video games, hybrid/digital arts, and web creation. Pôle Pixel’s three core missions – matchmaking, skills development, and workspace provision – complement Game Only’s gaming-specific services. The relationship is described as integrated: *“As soon as there’s a video game subject, I consult Mathilde because she has to be OK with what we do and how we do it. For me, we work together”* (GFa, #12, ICC hub). Pôle Pixel also positions itself as a mediating infrastructure facilitating the development of collaborative relationships – *“I make fishing nets, not cathedrals”* (GFa, #12, ICC hub).

However, Pôle Pixel’s role within the JV ecosystem must be nuanced. From the video game actors’ perspective, it remains peripheral relative to Game Only – most studio-level informants do not mention it spontaneously, and its salience varies sharply depending on the type of actor: it is more visible to hybrid creative-industry firms, cross-media professionals, and institutional partners than to pure JV studios. The relationship with Game Only is one of asymmetric complementarity: Game Only is the cluster’s operational hub; Pôle Pixel is a useful institutional relay for specific, well-delimited needs – political access to the Métropole de Lyon, participation in the France 2030 consortium, and involvement in the COEF. Its contribution is therefore real but selectively mobilised rather than structurally central.

Alongside Pôle Pixel, Game Only also collaborates with Minalogic, a State-labelled “*pôle de compétitivité*” (competitiveness hub) operating across the AURA region. Minalogic’s mandate covers the broader digital and deep-tech ecosystem (microelectronics, software, photonics), within which video game is a peripheral segment. Its logic of action differs from Pôle Pixel’s: where Pôle Pixel operates through co-location and local animation, Minalogic operates through collaborative R&D projects and competitive innovation funding (BPI, FUI, European programmes). For video games studios, Minalogic is relevant principally when projects involve technological innovation components and remains distant from day-to-day cluster life. Its role, though structurally important within the regional innovation system, is rarely cited by studio informants.

CITIA (Annecy), which operates the MIFA international animation market, constitutes a third type of intermediary – a “*Société Publique Locale*” (Local public company) fully owned by territorial authorities, whose logic rests on event-based visibility and international matchmaking. CITIA is increasingly engaging with the video game sector through cross-IP convergence and matchmaking programmes connecting video games and animation studios. This interaction is institutional (meta-organisation to meta-organisation) rather than studio-to-studio. More anecdotally, two additional entities were cited in some interviews. The first is Lyon Game Dev, presented as an association for students and solo developers – “*more like devs meeting at a bar*” (AG, #6, micro-studio). Despite being peripheral, historically it remains significant as a space where individual developers gather outside studio-mediated structures. The second is Gamaste, a training organisation running the “*Évolution*” project (mapping video games jobs and competences) and which operates a national Discord with specialisation channels providing peer support for isolated professionals.

Taken together, these intermediaries illustrate the functional plurality of the Lyon cluster’s institutional infrastructure: a dominant gaming-specific association (Game Only), a cross-sector ICC hub (Pôle Pixel), a regional innovation cluster (Minalogic), a para-public event operator (CITIA), and a handful of training and community-based entities. Their juridical heterogeneity – association, SEM, State-labelled pôle, SPL – reflects the layered nature of French cultural and industrial policy, but from the actors’ standpoint, what matters is less the statute than the specific brokering function each performs.

6.3.1.4 Other key Actors: governmental and public institutions and national

Beyond the three core categories of actors (video game industry, educational institutions, cultural intermediaries), the cluster’s dynamics are shaped by two additional categories whose interactions are primarily mediated through Game Only.

Governmental and public institutions

- The AURA region is the primary funder of Game Only and was a founding partner of Gamagora. The **D4.1** analysis documented the Region’s financial support in detail, including the €800,000 regional fund that supported studio projects with grants. The Region is formalised within Game Only’s “*Collège des Financeurs Publics*” (Committee of Public Funders).

- The CNC (National Center of Cinema), through its CIJV (Video Game Tax Credit), constitutes the principal national subsidy channel for studios. A bias against mobile gaming within the CNC’s evaluation criteria was identified by two mobile-focused informants (see Value Chain section). The **D4.1** analysis noted that the CNC’s institutional embedding of video game support within cultural production frameworks has been strategically valuable; the **T4.4** evidence reveals, however, that these framing disadvantages studios whose products are perceived as less “artistic” (particularly mobile gaming).
- The Mairie (Municipality) and Métropole (Metropole) de Lyon was described by one founding member studio as having maintained zero relationship with the gaming industry for six years, reportedly due to concerns about electricity consumption (Dir., #5, AAA subsidiary). This claim is unconfirmed by other informants but is consistent with the informant’s institutional position. The **D4.1** analysis noted the historical role of Grand Lyon/Métropole as an institutional leader whose financial support multiplied tenfold during the foundational period (2001–2002) and noted a significant regression in municipal engagement.
- DREETS, France Travail, and DRAC participate in the COEF – a governmental working group that is the most significant institutional channel for employment and training policy but is invisible to all studio-level informants.

The dominant pattern in government-cluster interactions is mediated engagement: studios rarely interact with governmental institutions directly. Game Only serves as the “*transmission belt*” (Dir., #5, AAA subsidiary) between the industry and public authorities. The COEF – bringing together the prefecture, DREETS, OPCO (AFDAS, ATLAS), France Travail, DRAC, and the Region — is the mechanism through which Game Only’s executive director negotiated a Region-funded training programme, the QVT charter, and environmental training financing. One of the informants (GFa, #12, ICC hub) described this mechanism in detail.

National meta-organisations and inter-cluster actors

- The SNJV (National Syndicate for Video Games) is the principal national industry association. Relations with Game Only were described by many informants as tense with identification of common interests not always obvious. Nicolas Brière (Old Skull Games), who sits on both the Game Only board and the SNJV, serves as one of the primary bridging figures between the two organisations. The **D4.1** analysis described the SNJV’s federal coordination model - monthly board meetings bringing together regional cluster representatives – as a mechanism for knowledge exchange, coordination, and shared services. The **T4.4** evidence suggests that this model functions imperfectly from Lyon’s perspective: four informants converge on the assessment that regional structuration works while national coordination is less efficient.
- The SELL (Association of Leisure Software Publishers) is a publisher-oriented syndicate. The informants mention it as a component of the relational national ecosystem in the industry without however having direct interactions with it.

- The STJV (Video Game Workers' Union), a national worker union, operates with a deliberately “*combative*” posture. Its emergence reflects a growing cleavage between employer-representative structures (Game Only, SNJV) and worker-representative ones. This cleavage has historical roots – Lyon Game Dev already represented a space where individual developers gathered outside employer-dominated structures (see **D4.1**) but has become more pronounced and more confrontational at the national level. One informant framed it as structural: “*the gaming industry is paying for years of social dialogue that was neither supported nor sincere.*” (JC, #8, SCOP studio) The absence of a sector-specific convention collective compounds this: the SNJV’s advocacy for an independent framework is supported by AZ (#7, AAA subsidiary) but progress is described as extremely slow due to resource constraints.
- Capital Games (Paris) and SO Games (Bordeaux) are peer professional association operating in other regional clusters (Paris and IDF region for Capital Games and Aquitaine Region for So Games). Lyon studios with operations in those cities are members in these clusters.
- The AFJV (French Video Game Agency) was highlighted as an alternative to the SNJV for school-industry interface (NV, #11, multi-campus school).
- France Clusters, of which Pôle Pixel is a member, was also cited as an organization which enables European-level ICC cluster representation.

Game Only is the main gateway connecting the Lyon cluster with national and international networks. The SNJV relationship involves formal channels (Arkane’s Game Director sits on subsidy validation commissions and collaborates on lobbying for an independent convention collective) and informal bridges (Nicolas Brière’s dual membership). Inter-cluster cooperation is primarily event-mediated: at Gamescom, “*there’s a big French flag where every French cluster is aligned, so we meet every studio.*” (AG, #6, micro-studio) When local expertise is insufficient, Game Only routes requests to peer clusters: “*if we don’t have the experts here, they contact other clusters to help us.*” (AG, #6, micro-studio) Mature creative studios also maintain direct collaborations with publishers and studios in Bordeaux, Montpellier, and Paris (Arte, Plugin Digital), creating inter-cluster productive links that supplement the institutional connections. The **D4.1** analysis identified several as concrete mechanisms for pooled inter-cluster resource sharing; the **T4.4** evidence confirms that these institutional channels coexist with studio-level commercial networks that operate independently.

6.3.2 Collective Actions

6.3.2.1 Facilitating networking, collaboration, and inter-organisational relationships

The Lyon cluster’s collective actions are organised primarily through Game Only, which functions as the institutional platform for almost all forms of organised collaboration. The association’s collective action repertoire encompasses several distinct domains, each confirmed by multiple independent informants. Beyond providing discrete services, Game Only’s foundational role is to create the conditions for networking and collaboration, both formal and informal, that cement inter-organisational relationships across the cluster. Many interactions take place through Game Only

events and initiatives – a dynamic confirmed unanimously across the sample, from micro-studio founders to AAA subsidiary executives to educational institution directors.

The most universally described collective action is event organisation and international delegation facilitation. Game Only organises the annual Game Only Day (one-day professional conference), seasonal afterwork parties, and subsidised delegations to international events including Gamescom, GDC, and Paris Games Week. Game Only's event programme – Game Only Day (annual one-day professional conference), Summer and Winter Parties (seasonal networking), afterwork meetups (regular informal socialising), and game jams – constitutes the primary mechanism through which the inter-organisational network is developed and maintained. Afterworks and parties during the year serve a complementary function: informal socialising in which new studios, new partners, and specialised service providers (lawyers, consultants, investors) meet potential collaborators. These events are not ancillary to the cluster's functioning; they are its connective tissue. For newcomers, events provide the first point of contact: *"When we go to Gamescom, we go with everybody through Game Only."* (AG, #6, micro-studio) For established actors, events sustain relationships that production pressures would otherwise erode: *"In the reunions, you see that everyone has known each other for 10, 20, 30 years."* (DP, #10, public university) For the HR professional, afterworks provide access to former colleagues at Arkane, Old Skull Games, and Kylotonn – *"you see there that everyone knows each other."* (MS, #9, publisher-studio)

Game Only's subsidised delegations to international events – Gamescom, GDC, Nordic Games, Paris Games Week – serve a dual function. First, they provide micro-studios with international market access they could never afford independently: a PDI (International Development Programme) covers up to 50% of travel expenses. Second, the collective French presence at these events generates inter-cluster encounters and positions Lyon within the national and European gaming landscape. *"At Gamescom, there's a big French flag where every French cluster is aligned, so we meet every studio."* (AG, #6, micro-studio) All three international publisher contacts described by one micro-studio founder (Plugin Digital/Montpellier, Parko Games/Japan, Assembly Entertainment/Germany) were made at Game Only-facilitated events. The **D4.1** analysis described Game Connection – originally created in Lyon in 2001 – as the foundational model for structuring developer–publisher relationships through curated B2B meetings. While Game Connection itself has become international, its organisational DNA (structured meetings, curated participant selection, combined networking and business formats) remains an institutional legacy that informs Game Only's contemporary delegation model.

In terms of tools, the informal collaboration occurs also through the Slack/Discord channels. The real-time communication channel functions as daily operational infrastructure for knowledge sharing. Described by several informants as omnidirectional – any member can post a question and receive help – the channel substitutes for formal advisory services that small studios cannot afford. One newcomer described the culture: *"I've never had someone say no on the Slack."* (GF, #1, micro-studio). One micro-studio founder confirmed: *"if you need help, you can ask and you will get help – without money in return. You can ask anybody on the Slack and find what you need."* (AG, #6, micro-

studio). The channel’s effectiveness depends on the trust generated by Game Only membership: being part of the association provides the social credential that opens the door to mutual aid.

Game Only acts also as the main gateway to national and international networks. It connects the Lyon cluster with national bodies (SNJV, CNC, SELL), peer regional clusters (Capital Games/Paris, SO Games/Bordeaux), and international markets. It engages with public institutions related to the cultural and creative industries such as CITIA, supports events like MIFA, and secures funding from local, regional, and national governments.

The relationship between Lyon and other French clusters operates at several levels. Formally, Game Only connects to Capital Games, SO Games, and through Pôle Pixel to France Clusters. On the ground, inter-cluster cooperation is event-mediated: at Gamescom, collective French presence generates inter-cluster encounters. Game Only routes requests to peer clusters when local expertise is insufficient. Mature studios maintain direct collaborations with publishers in Bordeaux (Arte, Plugin Digital) and Montpellier, creating productive inter-cluster links.

6.3.2.2 Structured functions: the pillars of Game Only’s service architecture

Beyond relational facilitation, Game Only performs structured services confirmed by multiple sources:

- Institutional intermediation and political representation: Game Only acts as the “transmission belt” (Dir., #5, AAA subsidiary) between studios and public institutions – Région AURA, CNC, DREETS, France Travail. The COEF mechanism shows how Game Only negotiates formation budgets, QVT charters, and environmental training through a governmental working group invisible to most studio-level informants (COEF). The association plays a critical role in serving as the main representative of the cluster in political discussions and lobbying efforts. *“When Mathilde must go see the SNJV or the CNC, she asks a CA member to come – if it’s a big studio, it carries weight.”* (JC, #8, SCOP studio).
- The Club RH emerged as the most operationally detailed collective action mechanism. Meeting monthly or bimonthly, it brings together HR professionals for new law updates, thematic workshops, and a co-development format in which one participant presents a concrete HR problem, the group votes on priorities and collectively develops solutions. *“The HR Club is super precious for me. Without it I’d have to pay lawyers. Now I just call another HR and they give me the information. I clearly see why I pay for the Game Only membership”* (MS, #9, publisher-studio). The **D4.1** analysis identified the Club RH and QVT initiatives as distinctive forms of non-competitive exchange; the **T4.4** evidence reveals the operational mechanics that make these exchanges effective, particularly the co-development format.
- The Let’s Go incubation programme is Game Only’s primary mechanism for supporting studio creation. Described by six informants, the programme generates lasting relational bonds beyond its formal outputs: former cohort members maintain friendships, exchange documents, and provide mutual feedback years after graduation. One micro-studio founder met his closest professional ally through Let’s Go; a senior studio cofounder has served as a mentor for three to four years.

- Financial expertise & help for funding: this goes through mechanisms such as the “Club Finance” (2/14) which contributes sessions on financial management and project cost tracking (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary) and peer-review of CNC dossiers where experienced studios advise newcomers on artistic and financial gaps in subsidy applications. This mechanism improves the cluster’s aggregate funding success rate. CNC officials visit Lyon regularly for dossier quality discussions. This service involves also investor facilitation where Game Only organizes visits by investors to tour studios and showcase the region (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary). This benefits smaller studios seeking funding or publishers and makes the region credible to visiting investors.

6.3.2.3 Resources

In terms of resources, informants cited the person-dependence on the general director as both a strength and vulnerability. Game Only executive director was named by every informant. “[She] is a superhero. Before her, there was distrust, ego. If tomorrow she were replaced by someone full of fear and distrust, it would become very complicated.” (GFa, #12, ICC hub) Other explicit references included: YE (#13, “we speak several times a month”), GF (#1, “Game Only was the first email I sent”), JC (#8, “it’s often she who solicits us”). This is simultaneously the cluster’s greatest strength and its most critical vulnerability. The vulnerability extends broadly: GF noted that across AURA, several ICC directors share similar values, but “unfortunately and fortunately, it depends on the persons.” The **D4.1** analysis identified several individuals as holding bridging positions with high involvement centrality suggesting that person-dependence is a recurring structural feature of the Lyon cluster across its successive institutional incarnations, not a contingent characteristic of the current phase alone.

Several informants have also flagged Game Only’s financial vulnerability: the association depends on Région AURA funding that is “not always guaranteed.” (SB, #4, indie studio). The **D4.1** analysis raised the same concern, noting the association’s modest staffing relative to its large member base and questioning operational sustainability as the ecosystem grows. The France 2030 consortium (7 entities, Pôle Pixel lead, Game Only included, Phase 1 won) represents a structural attempt to diversify funding.

6.3.2.4 Governance structure based on inter-organizational collaboration and promoting it

Four informants sit on the Game Only board, while two are founding members not on the board. The governance model is consistently described as:

- **Participatory:** Meetings open to all who want to participate, and decisions are made by unanimity. “They organise meetings, we discuss, they summarise, and we decide what to push.” (AG, #6, micro-studio)
- **Flexible:** “Each studio comes and goes according to their availability – it’s a great strength.” (JC, #8, SCOP studio). Engagement fluctuates with production cycles, and this is normalised.

- **Expertise-based influence, not size-based:** Contributions are domain-specific (finance, artistic/social topics, RSE, ...). *“It’s linked to the persons more than the studios represented.”* (JC, #8, SCOP studio)
- **Informal hierarchy within formal equality:** the *“big four”* (Arkane, Ivory Tower, Artifact, Old Skull Games) have outsized influence because *“they know the ecosystem and politics well – when they say something, we attach to it.”* (AG, #6, micro-studio) This is experienced as legitimate expertise, not domination.

The **D4.1** analysis described Game Only’s governance structure in detail – including the Collège des Financeurs Publics – Committee of Public Funders, the Members Partners category, and three-year board mandates – providing the institutional framework that the **T4.4** interviews populate with relational dynamics. A notable difference: while the **D4.1** analysis emphasised the formal governance architecture, the **T4.4** evidence reveals that the informal dynamics – expertise-based deference, flexible engagement, and the complementary duality between large studios’ financial weight and smaller studios’ voluntary labour – matter as much as the formal structures for the cluster’s day-to-day functioning.

6.3.3 Cluster Perimeter

The perimeter of the Lyon cluster is defined through institutional membership, geographic concentration, and relational density. The mapping exercise revealed that this perimeter is porous in specific directions and rigid in others.

- **Geographic perimeter:** The cluster’s relational density is concentrated in the Lyon Métropole, and notably in Villeurbanne and central Lyon arrondissements – consistent with the spatial mapping findings of **D4.2**, which demonstrated a ‘5-to-10-minute cluster’ effect. Beyond this core, density drops rapidly. Annecy, despite hosting approximately 6-7 game studios including a major Ubisoft office of approximately 300 employees, operates as a structurally separate satellite. The critical mass threshold for cluster dynamics is not met there: *“Studios that recently set up have trouble retaining people long-term – if there’s no other studio and the project stops, you can’t bounce back in Annecy.”* (YE, #13, animation ICC) According to the same informant, the Ubisoft Annecy office has been institutionally opaque – *“I’ve been at CITIA 12 years, and I know Ubisoft’s staff very poorly.”* (YE) Other AURA cities (Clermont-Ferrand, Saint-Étienne, Valence) are mentioned peripherally but do not feature in any informant’s core relational map.
- **Institutional perimeter:** Game Only’s approximately 120 members constitute the *de facto* cluster institutional boundary. The association’s representativeness is high, but not exhaustive: *“I imagine there are people who aren’t in it.”* (GFa, #12) No informant could name a significant studio operating entirely outside Game Only’s orbit.
- **National perimeter:** The national perimeter is mediated through Game Only’s relationships with the SNJV, Capital Games, and SO Games. Four informants converge on the diagnosis that regional structuration works better than national coordination: *“At the national level,*

[...] communication is difficult, coordination is difficult. The main reason is probably the lack of resources and means.” (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary).

- **International perimeter:** The international perimeter is event-mediated for most studios: contacts are overwhelmingly made at Gamescom, GDC, or Nordic Games through Game Only delegations. The two major anchor studios operate within their publisher groups’ global networks but do not function as gateways for other studios: *“I am not here to do business or connect small studios with publishers. That is not my role at all.”* (AZ, #7, AAA subsidiary). A few studios maintain independent international networks: CC (#2, services across two continents), MS (#9, ex-Blizzard founders’ network), NV (#11, partnerships in South Korea, Canada, and Japan).
- **Political perimeter:** Two distinct political barriers affect specific actors. The Green party Métropole administration (until 2026) was described by one founding member studio as having maintained zero relationship with the gaming industry for six years (Dir., #5). At the regional level, political tensions between the Région AURA and the Université Lyon 2 affect the public university’s access to regional support. Game Only mediates between both through collective representation, but individual actors are directly constrained.

6.3.4 Value Chain

The value chain dynamics of the Lyon cluster reflect a tension between local productive capacity and global market integration. The cluster is functionally complete in creative production – encompassing the full range of development roles – but remains structurally dependent on external actors for publishing, distribution, and market access. The **D4.1** analysis noted that commercial transactions within the cluster are limited (De Paoli et al. 2025); the **T4.4** evidence confirms this pattern while adding nuance through the emergence of local publishing capacity.

The two anchor studios operate within fully integrated global value chains controlled by their parent publishers. Arkane’s entire commercial apparatus is handled by Bethesda/Microsoft; Ivory Tower’s by Ubisoft. Neither engages in significant local value chain activities beyond production. Their outsourcing practices, however, create value chain connections: Arkane uses primarily French subcontractors selected for competence rather than cost maintaining long-term relationships and onboarding contractors into the studio’s artistic DNA through a two-to-three-week process.

For independent studios, the value chain is fragmented and individually negotiated. Most studios described publisher relationships as their primary gap: they develop games but lack the marketing, distribution, and financing capacity to bring them to market independently. Publisher contacts – Plugin Digital (Montpellier), Microids, Nacon, Arte, and international publishers met at events – are pursued through Game Only’s delegation infrastructure. The establishment of New Tales/Emeteria (#9) introduces a local publishing function: the entity publishes third-party studios (including Artifact in Lyon, a deal secured through the personal network of the studio director) and can provide full publishing or short-term marketing accompaniment. This represents a structural evolution from the **D4.1** analysis, which characterised the cluster’s commercial relationships as predominantly publisher-dependent with limited intra-cluster transactions.

A financing gap was identified by several informants. The CNC’s subsidy architecture was described as biased against mobile gaming – perceived as less prestigious and less “artistic” than PC/console production – creating an institutional orphan status for an entire market segment. More broadly, the cluster lacks a venture capital culture: business angel and VC models remain unfamiliar to most gaming actors. The absence of a local breakout success story constrains the cluster’s capacity for growth trajectories that would elevate studios from survival to scale. The **D4.1** analysis identified the portfolio effect (€746 million distributed across 131 companies, preventing reconcentration in any single firm) as a structural strength; the **T4.4** evidence suggests this diversification, while resilient, comes at the cost of limited individual-studio scale.

The cross-sector porosity dimension of the value chain creates distinctive opportunities and operates at multiple levels. Four informants describe cross-sector dynamics, primarily from institutional positions, revealing multi-layered porosity between video games and adjacent creative industries.

- **Institutional porosity:** Pôle Pixel’s scope (cinema, animation, JV, hybrid arts) creates a shared institutional space. As previously noted, GFa (#12) frames this as territorial necessity due to the cluster’s position outside of the main region: *“We need to gather to create employment opportunities. There are many competences that are porous, notably around virtual production.”* However, this porosity is asymmetric: Pôle Pixel is important from a cross-sector perspective but remains peripheral to the JV-specific ecosystem. Game Only leverages Pôle Pixel as an institutional relay for specific needs (political access, France 2030, COEF participation) without diluting its gaming-specific focus.
- **IP-level porosity:** CITIA (#13) describes growing game-to-animation convergence: the MIFA market includes video game studios seeking animation partners for cross-media IP exploitation. A specific matchmaking programme connects sectors. However: *“we are at the beginning of understanding each other’s production workflows.”* (TC, #13, animation ICC)
- **Individual-level porosity:** JC (#8) worked 10 years in animation cinema before cofounding his studio. BA (#3) began selling scenarios to Infogrames before building cross-sector connections. DP (#10) integrates MAV (audiovisual master) students into game projects. These bridges demonstrate that porosity is embedded in career paths.
- **Practical limits:** Different employment regimes (intermittents vs. CDI), different production temporalities, different funding architectures, and limited skill overlap beyond the technical layer constrain cross-sector collaboration in daily practice.
- **Gaming skills beyond gaming:** NV (#11) described projects for RATP (recruitment game), the French Tennis Federation (Roland-Garros), a Nice hospital (mental health gamification), and NATO (airbase emulators). Gaming competences – real-time 3D, interactive design, gamification – have value far beyond the gaming industry and are increasingly demanded by non-gaming clients.

6.4 Conclusion

The actor mapping exercise conducted for **T4.4** reveals a Lyon video game cluster characterised by strong institutional mediation, a culture of norm-based solidarity operating alongside competitive labour market dynamics, and a distinctive complementary duality between large studios' financial contributions and smaller studios' voluntary engagement.

The single most robust finding is the centrality of Game Only: every informant described the meta-organisation as essential to the ecosystem's functioning. Its eight identified functions – gateway and entry point, event organisation, institutional intermediation, HR mutual aid, financial expertise sharing, incubation, digital mutual aid, and political representation – constitute an integrated service architecture that no other single actor replicates. Game Only is not only the cluster's institutional hub but its primary relational bridge: many inter-actor interactions take place through its events and initiatives rather than through bilateral relationships. This centrality is simultaneously the cluster's greatest strength and its primary vulnerability, given the substantial person-dependence on a single executive director – a pattern that the **D4.1** analysis identified as recurring across the cluster's successive institutional incarnations.

The three-tier studio taxonomy (international subsidiaries as stabilisers, mid-size independents as engines, young/fragile studios as beneficiaries of collective support) emerged consistently across informant types. The cross-subsidisation mechanism that sustains the ecosystem operates through a complementary duality: large studios contribute financially and politically while smaller studios contribute the operational volunteerism (mentorship, peer review, mutual aid) that makes collective action machinery run. This solidarity is sustained by a pervasive "*bénévolat*" economy – a cultural norm of freely given professional help reproduced through participation.

The cluster's educational infrastructure is exceptionally dense and typologically diverse, but a shared concern over school overproduction signals a structural imbalance between training supply and employment demand. Cross-sector porosity with animation, cinema, and virtual production creates opportunities facilitated primarily through institutional actors (Pôle Pixel, CITIA) rather than through direct studio-to-studio collaboration.

The cluster perimeter is concentrated in the Lyon Métropole, with Annecy functioning as a satellite with insufficient critical mass for independent cluster dynamics. The national perimeter is constrained by a structuration deficit – regional effectiveness does not scale nationally through the SNJV/SELL system. The international perimeter is event-mediated for most studios, with anchor tenants' global networks remaining hermetically sealed from the local ecosystem.

Several vulnerabilities warrant attention: the person-dependence on Game Only's executive director; the association's financial fragility vis-à-vis regional funding; the emerging employer-employee cleavage reflected in the STJV's national posture; the national coordination difficulties; and the school overproduction crisis. These vulnerabilities coexist with distinctive strengths: a mature ecosystem with institutional memory shaped by learning from predecessor organisations' failures; the capacity to leverage peripheral ICC actors for cross-sector connections without diluting gaming-specific focus; and a relational fabric – rooted in the Infogrames-era creative diaspora – in which "*everyone knows everyone with one degree of separation.*" (JC, #8, SCOP studio)

The comprehensive map produced through this exercise provides a visual synthesis of these dynamics: a strongly hub-centred topology with Game Only at the absolute centre, anchor studios flanking the core, and a rich periphery of educational institutions, small studios, and cross-sector actors connected through event-mediated, knowledge-sharing, and institutional intermediation relationships. The convergence between the **T4.4** actor mapping findings and the structural analysis developed across **D4.1**, **D4.2**, and **D4.3** confirmed on the Infogrames diaspora, Game Only's centrality, the multi-scalar governance architecture, and the education–industry integration – validates the robustness of the overall analytical picture while adding the subjective, relational, and experiential dimensions that quantitative and documentary analyses cannot capture alone.

7 BORDEAUX

7.1 Overview of the cluster

The Bordeaux video game cluster, explored in depth through previous deliverables (**D4.1**, **D4.2**, **D4.3**) (De Paoli et al. 2025; De Paoli et al. 2025b; Costalunga et al. 2026), constitutes a distinctive case within the French and European landscape: a bipolar regional ecosystem spanning Bordeaux and Angoulême, structured across the full Nouvelle-Aquitaine territory, and shaped by a sequence of industrial ruptures that have repeatedly reorganized its membership and governance. Bordeaux’s ecosystem can be described as a binary star: two sub-poles of unequal mass but mutual dependence, held together institutionally by SO Games and relationally by a long-standing community of independents whose members circulate fluidly across both sites.

Kalisto’s dispersion during the 2000 provided the foundational relational substrate of the contemporary cluster, which is structurally asymmetric:

- Two anchor studios dominate in headcount: Asobo Studio and Ubisoft Bordeaux.
- Beneath this apex sits a constellation of mid-size independents – Shiro Games, Motion Twin (creators of *Dead Cells*), Evil Empire (spun off from Motion Twin), Big Bad Wolf, Dotemu.
- The Bordeaux ecosystem has a long tail of micro-studios, cooperatives, and freelancers concentrated particularly in Angoulême. The Angoulême sub-pole is anchored by the ENJMIN (National School of Gaming and Digital Interactive Media), France’s principal public video game school, and by the Pôle Image Magelis – a hybrid syndicate of unusual institutional density with no equivalent on the Bordeaux side.

The institutional evolution of the cluster was marked by three phases: the Kalisto-era mono-enterprise model (1990–2002); the reconstruction phase (2002–2016) in which Bordeaux Games was founded by five post-Kalisto studios (Asobo, AtOnce Technologies, BeTomorrow, SC2X/Mad Monkey, SolidGame); and the regional integration phase (2021–present) in which Bordeaux Games merged with Angoulême Jeux Vidéo to form SO Games, expanding the cluster’s scope across the entire Nouvelle-Aquitaine region – one of France’s largest, stretching from Poitiers to the Spanish border.

By 2021, SO Games represented approximately +110 companies and independents making Nouvelle-Aquitaine one of France’s three principal video game regions alongside Île-de-France and Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes. The association’s governance architecture reflects the challenge of coordinating a territorially dispersed cluster: two permanent staff members, one covering the northern and eastern departments (Deux-Sèvres, Vienne, Haute-Vienne, Charente, Charente-Maritime, Creuse, Corrèze), the other the southwestern departments (Dordogne, Gironde, Landes, Lot-et-Garonne, Pyrénées-Atlantiques), with differentiated thematic portfolios.

The **T4.4** mapping populates this institutional frame with subjective centrality assessments and relational textures that documentary analysis alone cannot capture.

7.2 Data collection & analysis

The present chapter draws on a focused sub-sample of six mapping interviews conducted between March and April 2026, each with an informant occupying a structurally distinct vantage point on the cluster. It also mobilises the documentary base and interview corpus produced through **D4.1-D4.3**. The sampling strategy was designed to triangulate across the cluster’s principal axes of differentiation: geographic sub-pole (Bordeaux vs. Angoulême), studio size (micro/indie vs. Triple-I vs. AAA subsidiary), position in the governance architecture (current and former SO Games board members, current SNJV board members), and organisational form (classic SARL, SCOP/cooperative, micro-entrepreneur, public institution). Informants were identified through snowball sampling from initial contacts, and purposive targeting of actor types underrepresented in earlier tasks – notably the ENJMIN/Angoulême side of the cluster, the service-provider category, and the Triple-I mid-size segment.

Consistent with **D4.1**’s categorisation, the **T4.4** sample retained the four principal actor types (game development studios, public funders and institutional actors, training and educational institutions, and meta-organisations) but deliberately sought different individual representatives, so that the mapping could triangulate across a broader set of subjective centrality assessments than those already documented in earlier tasks. Citations follow an anonymised format (initials, entity number, descriptor) – e.g. (DE, #2, indie cofounder) – so that quotations cannot be reverse-identified to specific studios.) The interview corpus for the present **T4.4** analysis is summarised in the table below.

Table 3: Interview corpus for Bordeaux / Nouvelle-Aquitaine cluster

#	Entity	Type	Informant (code)	Role	Duration	Notes
1	Studio α	Indie studio – Angoulême (cooperative, SCIC)	JN	Cofounder / publishing initiative	~60 min	Ex-SO Games board; Wiz expert
2	Studio β	Indie studio – Angoulême	DE	Cofounder; ex-President SO Games; Pedagogical engineer ENJMIN	~44 min	2nd interview
3	Studio γ	Mid-size ‘Triple-I’ studio – Bordeaux	AO	Director; SNJV board	~32 min	Post-Kalisto senior pool
4	Service provider δ	Marketing & publishing micro-entity – Corrèze	ML	Cofounder; ex-SO Games board; STJV member	~41 min	Cross-cluster reach
5	Institution ε	Regional technopole & incubator – Angoulême	LB	ICC mission lead; international referent; Wiz program lead	~51 min	Eurekatech / Wiz incubator

6	Institution ζ	Regional public authority – Nouvelle-Aquitaine	MP	Digital delegation ; ICC portfolio	~30 min	Region-side institutional perspective
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Researchers conducted semi-structured mapping interviews using four tailored interview guides: Version A for studios, Version B for public funders and institutions, Version C for training and education actors, and Version D for meta-organisations.

The interviews were conducted remotely via Zoom, using the appropriate guide version and typically lasting around one hour, with durations ranging from 30 to 60+ minutes (see Table 3). Wherever possible, interviews were conducted in pairs combining senior and junior researchers, with cross-team pairings deliberately favoured to maximise interpretive plurality. Interviews were conducted in French or English, according to informant preference; verbatim extracts used in the present chapter have been translated into English where the original was in French, with original-language wording retained in footnotes only where translation nuance could alter interpretive weight. Prior to the interview phase, the research team developed an initial conceptual map informed by **D4.1-D4.3**, used as an analytical frame for comparison with individual interviewee maps. Individual maps were created for each informant using SVG-based digital mapping, following guide conventions. The mapping approach builds on prior cluster research on video game ecosystems (Lehtonen et al., 2020, 2022) while adapting it to the **T4.4** design: rather than aggregating a single ecosystem representation, the research team developed one individual map per informant, reflecting that informant’s subjective perspective on the cluster at the time of the interview – identifying key actors and their relationships as seen from that vantage point. Each map placed the informant at the centre and positioned other actors across three concentric zones (Centre, Periphery, Outside the cluster).

The individual maps were then triangulated into a comprehensive global map in which line thickness reflects the frequency of independent confirmation across informants: an actor or relationship mentioned by multiple independent informants appears as a thicker element; those mentioned only once appear as thin or dashed lines. The analytical principles underlying this exercise – actor centrality, relational density, tie strength – draw on classical network analysis (Wasserman and Faust, 1994), adapted for a qualitative-cartographic rather than quantitative-sociometric treatment.

7.3 Actor mapping

The six individual maps, read against the **T4.1** corpus and **D4.3** synthesis, were aggregated into the comprehensive map through an iterative team discussion cross-checking actor positions and relationship types. **Figures 16 and 17** present two examples of individual maps produced during the mapping sessions, illustrating actors occupying different roles within the cluster – an indie cofounder with ecosystem-wide governance experience (DE, #2) and an institutional incubation manager with strong cross-border and training partnerships (LB, #5). These examples demonstrate how different positions generate sharply different perceptions of centrality: the indie cofounder places SO Games, the Angoulême community, the ENJMIN, and Magelis at the centre and articulates a three-pole structuring logic; the institutional informant, by contrast, foregrounds Magelis, the

Region, the ENJMIN partnership, and the Wiz cohort, with a distinctive international layer (Mexico, Germany) that other informants rarely mention.

Individual map — Studio Manager (DE, #2) / Ex-president SO Games

Triple-role perspective: indie cofounder + meta-org governance + pedagogical engineer — analytical synthesizer of the cluster

GAME-ER. D4.4 - Bordeaux/Nouvelle-Aquitaine — Individual map DE (#2). Triple-role informant: indie + ENJMIN + ex-SO Games. Actors and edges shown only when DE-confirmed.

Figure 16: Example of an individual actor map (Bordeaux; indie/ex-governance)

Individual map — ICC Mission Lead (LB, #5) / Wiz programme manager

Institutional incubation perspective from Angoulême — cross-sector ICC framing & international cooperation

GAME-ER D4.4 Bordeaux/Nouvelle-Aquitaine — Individual map LB (W5). Actors and edges shown only when LB-confirmed.

Figure 17: Example of an individual actor map (Bordeaux; institutional incubation)

The comprehensive map, presented in **Figure 18**, exhibits a bipolar architecture with two sub-centres of unequal density — a Bordeaux pole dominated by large studios and relatively sparse in micro-studios, and an Angoulême pole with high micro-studio density anchored by the ENJMIN and Magelis. SO Games operates as the institutional bridge between both, but its centrality is contested and partial: central to the indie segment and to political representation, peripheral to the operational world of the anchor studios. SO Games’ operational function can be framed as harmonising divergent cultures within a unified associational framework – bridging the industrialising logic of the anchor studios, the commercial-creative logic of the Triple-I studios, and the combative-political culture of the indie pole. This harmonisation is partial and effortful – and is distinctive to the Bordeaux video games ecosystem. The map is organised according to three concentric zones (Centre, Periphery, Outside the cluster) established in the general methodological guide, with shapes following the established conventions (squares for studios, rounded rectangles for meta-organisations, hexagons for governmental institutions, ellipses for events/programmes, stars for educational institutions).

Mapping of the videogame cluster - Bordeaux/Nouvelle-Aquitaine

Figure 18: Final actor map (Bordeaux)

Table 4: Categorization of Bordeaux cluster actors

Category	Sub-category	Actors	Sub-category description
Video Game Industry	<i>Anchor studios (gros / industrialisers)</i>	Ubisoft Bordeaux, Asobo Studio, Shiro Games	Two AAA-scale anchors and one large independent, all based in Bordeaux. Provide cluster-wide legitimacy, financial weight and political credibility, but limited operational coordination.
Video Game Industry	<i>Triple-I / mid-size studios (motors)</i>	Motion Twin, Evil Empire, Dotemu (Paris-Bordeaux)	Mid-size independents that have achieved commercial success (<i>Dead Cells, Streets of Rage 4</i>) without industrial rationalisation. Local engagement uneven: some sustain the indie community culturally, others articulate frustration with thin local value chain and delocalise specialised services to Paris/London.
Video Game Industry	<i>Indie pole / micro-studios & cooperatives</i>	HeadBang Club, Seed by Seed, La Poule Noire, Les Pancakes Délicieux, Ribang, Sylvan Studios, Graphite Lab	Dense population of micro-studios concentrated on the Angoulême side, with cooperative and SCOP organisational forms. Sustained through Slack/Discord mutual aid, Wiz incubation, and the volunteering economy. Includes service-niche providers (porting, marketing, publishing).
Video Game Industry	<i>Wiz cohort & Eurekatech-incubated studios</i>	Wiz cohort (~6 studios/year, ~13 created since 2018)	Studios emerging from the Wiz incubation programme operated by Eurekatech in Angoulême. Each cohort receives 100h support over six months, expert pool access (marketing, IP, accounting), free SO Games membership and subsidised event stands. Pipeline of new entrants for the indie pole.
Video Game Industry	<i>Historical lineage (extinct anchors)</i>	Kalisto Entertainment † 2002, Bordeaux Games † 2021, Angoulême Jeux Vidéo † 2021	Defunct entities still structurally present. Kalisto's 2002 spin-off seeded the contemporary studio population Bordeaux Games and Angoulême Jeux Vidéo merged in 2021 to form SO Games, expanding the cluster's scope across the full Nouvelle-Aquitaine region.
Cultural Intermediaries & Meta-organisation	<i>Regional meta-organisation (cluster association)</i>	SO Games (post-fusion 2021), ~110 members 2 permanent staff	Principal cluster meta-organisation operating across the full Nouvelle-Aquitaine territory. The single most central institutional actor.
Cultural Intermediaries & Meta-organisation	<i>Hub CCI (Angoulême institutional plurality)</i>	Pôle Image Magelis · Eurekatech, Wiz incubator, Pépinière Images, Chrysalide Fab Lab	Five-actor institutional density unique to the Angoulême sub-pole. Magelis is a syndicat mixte (Conseil Départemental Charente, Grand Angoulême, Région NA) with dedicated real estate, regional video-game fund, and CNAM-ENJMIN partnership. Eurekatech is one of 11 NA technopoles, operating Wiz incubation co-located with Pépinière Images and Chrysalide Fab Lab.
Cultural Intermediaries & Meta-organisation	<i>SO Games operational infrastructure</i>	Slack (~800 members, open access), Discord ecosystem (15+ rooms), After-works (Add-on, Game Camp, Game Biz)	Sociotechnical infrastructure sustaining the indie pole's day-to-day cohesion (the open-access Slack, Discord ecosystem, after-works function ...).
Cultural Intermediaries & Meta-organisation	<i>Cluster events & flagship programmes</i>	GameConf, Horizon, Spawn, Annual game jam, France 2030 plan (with CNAM-ENJMIN)	Recurring SO Games events (GameConf as the annual professional showcase, Horizon, focused on studio-business operations, Spawn the public-facing event with stronger indie orientation).

			France 2030 plan, jointly developed with the ENJMIN, established a four-engineer pedagogical team.
Educational Institutions	<i>Public dominant anchor (national reach)</i>	CNAM-ENJMIN (École Nationale du Jeu et des Médias Interactifs)	Single dominant educational anchor, located in Angoulême — France's principal public video-game school. Partners structurally with Wiz incubation; placements span anchors, Triple-I and indés. France 2030 pedagogical-engineer team brings industry inside the institution.
Educational Institutions	<i>Private offerings (Bordeaux + Angoulême)</i>	Gaming Campus Bordeaux (since 2018), Rubika, ~15 image schools (Angoulême)	Private sector universally described as problematic. SO Games maintains arm's-length relationships: works primarily with the publicly validated CNAM-ENJMIN, deals with private schools via individual practitioner-teachers rather than institutional partnership.
Local & Regional Government	<i>Regional & territorial authorities</i>	Région Nouvelle-Aquitaine, Bordeaux Métropole, Grand Angoulême, Grand Cognac, Conseil Départemental de la Charente	Multi-scalar territorial layer matching the cluster's bipolar geography. Région NA is principal funder. Grand Angoulême and the Conseil Départemental de la Charente co-fund Magelis. Bordeaux Métropole and Grand Angoulême operate on differentiated logics (international visibility vs image-cluster ecosystem) Source of recurring programmatic tensions.
Local & Regional Government	<i>Sectoral banking</i>	Crédit Agricole Charente-Périgord (sector-dedicated officer)	Distinctive Bordeaux feature: a sector-dedicated banking officer assigned to the Angoulême image cluster. Not a formal cluster-funder but a structural relay between studios and the banking system, particularly for indie pole operating-capital needs.
National Bodies & External Actors	<i>National funder & national agency</i>	CNC (Centre National du Cinéma) — CIJV (Crédit d'Impôt Jeu Vidéo), DGE (Direction Générale des Entreprises)	Principal national funders and policy interfaces. CNC operates the CIJV tax credit and direct video-game subsidies — the principal national project-financing channel. DGE (national level) manages the CIJV interface; smaller studios reach CIJV via accountancy firms and tax-credit consultants rather than directly.
National Bodies & External Actors	<i>National syndicates</i>	SNJV (Syndicat National du Jeu Vidéo), STJV (Syndicat des Travailleurs du Jeu Vidéo), SELL (Syndicat des Éditeurs de Logiciels de Loisirs), Pégases	Three national syndicates triangulated. SNJV (employer side) — institutionalised SO Games seat; bridging individuals. STJV (worker side) — present in Bordeaux through individual memberships and creates structural tension with SO Games board mandate (employer role). SELL (publisher side) — less prominent given the relative scarcity of traditional publishers in NA. Pégases referenced as awards body.
National Bodies & External Actors	<i>Peer regional clusters</i>	Capital Games (Paris), Game Only (Lyon), Atlangames (Nantes), JYROS, France Clusters	Horizontal cross-cluster coordination operating in parallel with the SNJV's federal role.
National Bodies & External Actors	<i>International cooperation (LB-distinctive)</i>	Mexique-Zapopan / Guadalajara, Sénégal, AFD, Spielfabrique, Nordic Game, Develop Brighton, Reboot, Japan / Canada	Distinctive Bordeaux/Angoulême international layer. Anchored by EurekaTech's company-exchange programmes (Mexique via Grand Angoulême's Zapopan cooperation; Sénégal via emerging AFD partnership; Spielfabrique acceleration in Germany). SO Games-led delegations to Nordic Game and Develop Brighton. Individual studio-level engagement to Japan and Canada.

The map confirms several findings from previous deliverables while revealing new dimensions. The bipolar geography documented in **D4.3** is confirmed relationally: informants describe the two poles as functionally complementary and institutionally bridged, not as competing sub-clusters. SO Games’ position as the principal meta-organisation is confirmed, with nuances around large-studio disengagement and small-studio investment. The institutional layer is distributed across several actors with overlapping competences:

- SO Games for regional collective action;
- Magelis for the Angoulême image sector;
- EurekaTech/Wiz for incubation;
- the ENJMIN as the talent pipeline;
- the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region as primary funder;
- and Bordeaux Métropole, Grand Angoulême, and Grand Cognac as territorial partners.

This plurality creates redundancy and flexibility but complicates coordination. It reflects both the cluster’s bipolar geography and the historical reality that the ecosystem was constructed without institutional tutelage. One indie informant with governance experience (DE, #2) captures this history: the cluster *“first built a production tool before building an institutional exchange tool, because the institutional work was delegated to people who already knew how to do it very well.”*

From a historical point of view, the Kalisto spin-offs function as the foundational event of the Bordeaux cluster. A mid-size studio informant (AO, #3) provides the most explicit articulation: the contemporary cluster is *“still riding the long tail of the Kalisto studio explosion in the early 2000s. A large majority of the very senior people now working in the studios are former Kalisto employees or former Kalisto collaborators. There is a genuine dynamic in which a certain know-how and a set of technological tools remained in place – and legitimised the aggregation of skills around them.”* The Kalisto lineage is not historical residue but an ongoing legitimizing resource that anchors senior talent and shapes several studios’ founding rationales.

7.3.1 Key Actors and Features

7.3.1.1 Video game studios

The studio landscape exhibits a three-pole structure defined by size, “ideological” orientation, and location on the Bordeaux–Angoulême axis. DE (#2) articulates it most explicitly: *“There are really three poles. The indés – an environment closer to the left, even the combative left, with politically engaged people. The large structures – operating in a logic of industrialisation and rationalisation. [...] And then the institutionals, with their own prerogatives.”*

Pole 1 — International anchors (industrialisers)

At the apex, two anchor studios dominate in headcount and economic weight: Ubisoft Bordeaux (approximately 400 employees, Assassin’s Creed Mirage contributor, opened 2017) and Asobo Studio (approximately 270 employees, €29 million revenue as of 2022, creator of A Plague Tale and

Microsoft Flight Simulator, under a twenty-year Microsoft partnership). These studios operate on industrial logics – productive rationalisation, internal recruitment machinery, confidentiality-intensive project regimes – creating a sharp structural distinction from the rest of the cluster. Their value chains operate within their publisher or platform-partner networks, and they engage selectively with local subcontractors. As one indie informant observes, *“the large studios don’t work much with local actors. They tend to go to firms like Keywords or Virtuos – very large, twice as expensive, but in terms of insurance and quality assurance, they feel more reassured”* (DE, #2). Shiro Games (approximately 40 employees), while smaller, is described by several informants as functionally belonging to this pole in operational regime; it has received local public funding while declining SO Games membership – a pattern that a service-provider informant (ML, #4) cites as symptomatic of broader anchor-studio detachment from collective infrastructure.

Anchor-studio engagement can be described as legitimacy-by-representation: political presence without operational participation. For example, Ubisoft stood for election to the SO Games board but was not elected because, in the words of one informant, *“they were never at the events”* (ML, #4); the association nevertheless continued to invite Ubisoft in a non-voting capacity for political legitimacy vis-à-vis the local authority.

Pole 2 — Mid-size independents and Triple-I studios (Engines)

The second pole comprises mid-size studios that have achieved commercial success without adopting the industrial rationalisation of the anchor studios. One Triple-I director (AO, #3) describes his own category as *“neither AAA nor pure indie, because we have teams of fewer than 100 people but a commercial success completely out of proportion with the market’s norms.”* Other studios include Motion Twin (cooperative, Dead Cells), Big Bad Wolf (narrative adventure, Nacon investment), and Dotemu. Several operate within international networks – the same Triple-I director reports organising private peer-studio gatherings at GDC San Francisco *“without cameras and without journalists.”* This pole’s local engagement is uneven: some have provided the cultural substrate of the indie community; others articulate a frustrated diagnosis of the local value chain (see Value Chain section below).

Pole 3 — Micro-studios, coopératives, and freelances (indies)

The third pole comprises the dense population of micro-studios concentrated particularly in Angoulême: among them, Seed by Seed (cooperative, now in insolvency proceedings), HeadBang Club, La Poule Noire, Les Pancakes Délicieux (Bordeaux, creator of Shotgun King), and the Wiz cohort of roughly six studios per year at Eurekatech as well as Rubika graduates. One cooperative cofounder (JN, #1) describes Angoulême’s tight integration: *“in Angoulême, everything is very interwoven.”* DE (#2) characterises the pole as ideologically distinctive: *“the indés are an environment closer to the left, even the combative left, made up of politically engaged people. On the business side, the Bordeaux actors didn’t talk to each other much because they’re very large and represent themselves. Where there are the small ones, we are obliged to talk together to convince the institutionnels. We quickly organised ourselves into voluntary working groups.”*

This pole comprises organisations with cooperative status. One service-provider informant (ML, #4) describes her own micro-structure as two-person, explicitly rejecting the employer model – *“I see it a bit as exploitation.”*

How studios interact with each other: inter-studio relationships and solidarity dynamics

Inter-studio relationships exhibit a specific pattern: relational density is high within each of the three poles and weak across them. Within the indie pole, relationships are dense, operational, and sustained through informal infrastructure – a 700–800-member Slack inherited from the Bordeaux Games / Angoulême Jeux Vidéo fusion, roughly fifteen overlapping Discords (JN, #1), and the signature open-channel philosophy established under a previous governance cycle at SO Games: *“the Slack is open, we invite everyone – employees, freelancers, students. There are private channels for members, though”* (DE, #2). This deliberate openness – contrasted by the same informant with member-only clusters that are *“a bit less dynamic”* – is a distinctive Bordeaux design choice with consequences for cluster vitality.

Between the indie pole and the anchor studios, operational collaboration is almost absent. Anchor studios internalise production and subcontract to large-scale specialised providers outside the cluster (Keywords, Virtuos). One mid-size studio director (AO, #3) articulates the view from a position intermediate between Poles 1 and 2: *“one of the big problems I’ve been able to observe is that there is a confidentiality issue that is very, very present, and that means collaborations between studios do not happen naturally.”*

The primary cross-pole circulation mechanism is labour mobility, not commercial relationships. DE describes the ecosystem as *“a kind of water cycle around people and their position across the different poles”*: workers circulate between indies, Triple-I, and anchors; layoffs at Ubisoft or Asobo generate spin-off indies; successful indies scale up.

In Bordeaux, the dominant dynamic is large-studio disengagement – polite but structural. One cooperative cofounder (JN, #1) articulates the tension: *“why and how to keep the few large ones that pay high fees but bring nothing. The large studios keep the industry running, represent the industry, create jobs, and must be present – but they are not interested in our events. The large ones have often wanted to withdraw. They stay out of representational obligation.”* The Horizon event crystallised the resulting governance tension: Bordeaux Métropole wanted *“international visibility,”* the anchors wanted to showcase creative talents, the indie community wanted programming on how to run a small studio. The service-provider informant (ML, #4) summarises: *“we had an event that was incredibly useful for the ecosystem but did not meet the Région’s needs. We couldn’t fit all the needs together into one coherent whole.”*

Despite these frictions, the cluster exhibits an equilibrium that informants frame positively. As DE (#2) puts it: *“there isn’t really a confrontation – occasional clashes, but not often, between the big and the small players. Sometimes the big players feel they’re not plugged into the same reality – not disconnected exactly, but they don’t anticipate how the indies will respond. That’s normal; it’s not their daily reality.”* The three poles coexist through reciprocal externalities rather than direct exchange: *“the indés need the large ones to shine. The large ones need the indés to stay vibrant —*

because when Ubisoft or Asobo lay people off, it will create other indie studios. And those indie studios will grow and rejoin other structures later” (DE, #2)

Within the indie pole, knowledge sharing is intensive and topical: ML (#4) emphasises its non-technical character – *“on an informal Slack, there are technical channels – but far fewer messages than on marketing, publishers, sharing of figures. Technical knowledge is more easily found on the Internet. The sinews of the war right now are: finding money and selling games.”* This sharing is asymmetric along an employer/employee axis. JN (#1) observes some over-representations of employer spaces. *“They are mostly for people who created their own company. We find many fewer employees in these networks.”* Founder-operators dominate this informal infrastructure, with consequences for worker representation through STJV.

7.3.1.2 Educational institutions

The Bordeaux cluster’s educational infrastructure is structured around a single dominant anchor and a diffuse periphery of private programmes – a pattern sharply distinct from the Lyon cluster’s typologically diverse and quantitatively abundant education layer. The centre of gravity is unambiguous: the CNAM-ENJMIN (“National School of Gaming and Digital Interactive Media”), located in Angoulême. One mid-size studio director (AO, #3) – whose studio interacts relatively little with local institutions – nonetheless identifies the ENJMIN as the single educational actor with structural significance: *“very clearly, in terms of skills structuring, the ENJMIN plays a very, very important role. If I had to choose one school in which to invest time, it would be the ENJMIN.”*

The ENJMIN’s distinctive profile combines national recruitment, public-institution rigour, and close industrial integration. One informant (DE, #2) who holds a half-time pedagogical engineer position at the school alongside running an indie studio, describes the composition as approximately 50% academic researchers and 50% professional practitioners among instructors, with the academics holding roughly 80% of formal teaching hours. Following a France 2030 plan jointly developed with SO Games, a team of four pedagogical engineers was established and was tasked with *“bringing more industry into this institution, which is very university-oriented.”* (DE, #2)

The ENJMIN’s national reach is consequential for the cluster’s talent economy. One informant (DE, #2) reports student placements *“across France, even around the world – I sent a student to Capcom in Japan,”* including occasional students from engineering grandes écoles. Another informant, involved with ENJMIN (JN, #1) maintains an alumni-CNAM Discord as part of the informal infrastructure, and one institutional informant (LB, #5) lists the CNAM-ENJMIN as a structural partner of the Wiz incubation programme, providing classroom and equipment access in exchange for co-hosted workshops. The school is therefore both the principal talent pipeline – supplying internships, graduate hires, and increasingly micro-studio service-provision to Bordeaux and to other national and international clusters – and a site of cluster-wide coordination via France 2030, the Wiz partnership, and its industry-facing pedagogical engineers.

Beyond the ENJMIN, the Bordeaux educational landscape includes Gaming Campus (Bordeaux campus opened 2018 as part of a three-campus network with Lyon and Paris), Rubika, and various private offerings; LB (#5) mentions *“around fifteen image schools in Angoulême”* driven by the

broader image cluster. The private-school segment is described consistently as problematic. One studio manager ML (#4) articulates the shared concern: *“schools have grown exponentially, creating far too many students for what the studios can absorb. People take out student loans for schools costing 8,000–9,000 euros and end up unemployed or on minimum wage. The schools want to make people dream – ‘you’ll be an art director or a game designer.’ But in production, there are many more people doing props, bushes, trees.”*

The same informant highlights a governance complexity specific to the Bordeaux case: SO Games’ statutes foresee a *“pôle Écoles et Formation”* (A sub-part for schools and training programs) with a quality charter, but the association lacks volunteer capacity to operate it, and integrating private schools within the association risks being perceived as implicit quality endorsement. The Bordeaux cluster’s relationship with private schools is deliberately arm’s-length: SO Games works primarily with the CNAM-ENJMIN (externally validated public institution) and maintains informal individual relationships with private-school instructors without institutional engagement.

How educational institutions interact with the cluster

The school–studio relationship is bidirectional but asymmetrical across schools. The CNAM-ENJMIN operates dense, institutionalised relationships with studios of all sizes: practitioner-teachers, real-project student briefs, internship placements, and formal advisory mechanisms including the France 2030 investment plan. The Triple-I director (AO, #3) describes an aspiration to deepen his studio’s ENJMIN engagement. Its location in Angoulême rather than Bordeaux anchors the Angoulême sub-pole institutionally and underpins the cluster’s bipolar architecture.

Private schools interact with studios primarily through individual practitioner-teachers rather than institutional partnerships. One informant (ML, #4) describes the operational reality: *“for some freelancers, without the teaching, it would be very complicated to make a living.”* Teaching provides income supplementation in an economy where projects are episodic, creating two-way dependence that does not extend to institutional co-governance.

7.3.1.3 Cultural intermediaries and cross-sector actors

One of the most significant cultural intermediaries in the Bordeaux cluster is Magelis – the Pôle Image Magelis – a joint authority of public actors (Conseil Départemental de la Charente, Grand Angoulême, Ville d’Angoulême, Région Nouvelle-Aquitaine) dedicated to developing the Angoulême image cluster across comics, animation, movies, and video game. The Magelis perimeter aggregates over 200 image-sector companies and hosts training programs of fifteen schools on its Angoulême campus; its mission is to drive economic development of the image cluster by attracting businesses to the territory and providing tailored tools for entrepreneurs in animation, video game, publishing, and audiovisual production. Magelis operates with an unusually extensive set of tools and mechanisms: dedicated real estate in the *“quartier de l’image”* (image area), including the Pépinière Images (hosting the Wiz incubator), a regional fund for video game production, direct co-financing of EurekaTech, and a structural partnership with CNAM-ENJMIN. The representative of a local hub (LB, #5) describes Magelis as one of EurekaTech’s four principal financiers; Another

informant (DE, #2) characterises Magelis as “*very structuring among the institutional forces*” of the Angoulême pole.

The absence of an equivalent Bordeaux-side institution is the source of the cluster’s bipolar structuring: “*there is no Bordeaux equivalent. It’s a binary star: one does not exist without the other.*” (DE, #2) Bordeaux has métropole-level support (co-funding of Horizon and other events) but no image-cluster joint authority of comparable weight: institutional/creative depth is concentrated in Angoulême, economic weight in Bordeaux – a persistent coordination challenge.

Eurekatech itself operates as a second-tier cultural intermediary with a specifically incubation-oriented mission. Created in 2017 and operational from 2018–2019, it is one of eleven technopoles in the Nouvelle-Aquitaine network, positioned distinctly from the competitiveness-cluster model. It is not a competitiveness cluster but a ‘loi 1901 association,’ under private law and financed by public actors (LB, #5). Its mandate is to support innovative projects, federate the local ecosystem, amplify the visibility of partner initiatives, and serve key regional sectors (LB, #5). Its Wiz program fills a structural incubation gap that is not directly served by SO Games or by any Bordeaux-side equivalent. Eurekatech operates along an innovation axis (incubation, technology transfer), Magelis along a cultural-structuring axis (real estate, production fund, sectoral identity). This complementarity gives Angoulême denser institutional infrastructure than Bordeaux despite its smaller demographic and economic weight. A distinctive Eurekatech feature is its international linkage capacity, exemplified by company-exchange programs with foreign homologues and an emerging Franco-Mexican serious-game coproduction supported by Grand Angoulême’s decade-long cooperation with Zapopan. Peripheral intermediaries include the SPN (absorbed into Digital Aquitaine after the 2016 merger) and Digital Aquitaine itself — referenced but not central in any informant’s map. The Région’s digital delegation is a higher-level funder and interlocutor rather than a day-to-day collaborator.

7.3.1.4 Other key actors: governmental and public institutions and national meta-organisations

Beyond the three core categories, studios, cultural intermediaries and educational institutions, cluster dynamics are also shaped by governmental institutions and by national meta-organisations interactions that flow mainly through SO Games, and for anchor and selected mid-size studios directly through national channels.

Governmental and public institutions

- The Nouvelle-Aquitaine region is the primary funder of SO Games and operator of the regional “fonds d’aide Jeu Vidéo,” (Help Fund for Video Games) with a statutorily reserved board seat. The digital delegation within the Region’s directorate houses the cluster’s principal institutional interlocutor (MP, #6), who serves as the operational guichet: processing applications, consulting cluster actors on policy direction, and relaying regional strategic priorities downward to SO Games. The institutional interlocutor confirms that the Region approaches the video game sector as one component of a broader ICC portfolio, interfacing with a range of other regional and national actors in a coordinating role. Priority

themes – notably digital sobriety – flow downward from the Region’s strategic agenda and structure SO Games’ programmatic priorities: *“to secure our funding, we have to align with their priorities”* (ML, #4).

- Pôle Image Magelis, described above as cultural intermediary but functionally a public-sector institution, operates the principal video-game help fund for the Angoulême territory. Its operational tools — real estate, fund management, direct studio support – position it as a de facto second regional authority within the cluster.
- The CNC (National Center of Cinema), through its CIJV (Video Game Tax Credit) and direct subsidy scheme, is the principal national funder.
- Bordeaux Métropole and Grand Angoulême co-fund cluster events and participate regularly in SO Games’ after-works. One informant describes the relationship: *“the Region and the metropolises are very regular partners – they even come to the after-works”* (ML, #4). The two operate on differentiated logics: Bordeaux Métropole prioritises international visibility aligned with anchor-studio goals; Grand Angoulême supports the image-cluster ecosystem through Magelis and EurekaTech and is more attuned to the indie studios.
- The DGE (General Direction for Enterprises) manages, at national level, the CIJV interface. Smaller studios interact with CIJV primarily through accountancy firms and tax-credit consultants rather than directly.

Studios interact with the government mainly through SO Games; on the Angoulême side, Magelis provides an alternative interface with distinct priorities and tools.

National meta-organisations and inter-cluster actors

- The SNJV (National Video Game Union) is the principal national industry association. SO Games’ relationship is institutionalised through a statutorily reserved board seat, and bridging individuals serve as personal connectors: one mid-size studio director (AO, #3) holds an individual SNJV board seat; previous SO Games board members had also held dual mandates. ML (#4) describes the relationship as historically complicated and diagnoses a structural representational mismatch: *“the SNJV is disconnected from many small studios and freelancers. Its members are essentially medium-to-large studios. For us, in the regions, freelancers make up a large share of the membership.”*
- The STJV (Video Game Workers' Union) operates as the national worker union and is present in Bordeaux through individual memberships. ML (#4) links her departure from the SO Games board explicitly to the tension between syndicate membership and meta-organisation board participation: *“when you’re on the SO Games board, you become a bit of an employer of the permanent staff – and for me, as a union member on the workers’ side, that creates a contradiction.”*
- The SELL (Association of Leisure Software Publishers), publisher-oriented, plays a less prominent role for Bordeaux than for Paris-centric clusters, reflecting the relative scarcity of traditional publishers in Nouvelle-Aquitaine: *“there are no publishers in SO Games – we don’t have many in Nouvelle-Aquitaine”* (ML, #4).

- Capital Games (Paris) and Game Only (Lyon) are peer professional associations governing other regional clusters. ML describes pragmatic horizontal coordination: *“with all the other clusters too – at major events like Game Camp, all the clusters coordinate. JYROS meetings led by the consortium.”* This horizontal coordination operates in parallel with — and sometimes competes with — the SNJV’s federal role.

Inter-cluster cooperation is event-mediated and individually sustained. A small studio manager (DE, #2) describes an unusually extensive international dimension where SO Games delegations (Nordic Game, Develop Brighton, Reboot) combined with studio-level engagement (Serbia, Japan, Canada). Beyond the core national funders, the cluster benefits from supplementary support from the AFD (French Development Agency) on economic-development projects, the French Tech network on startup support to Magelis and EurekaTech.

7.3.2 Collective actions

7.3.2.1 Facilitating networking, collaboration, and inter-organisational relationships

Collective actions are organised through SO Games (meta-organisational), EurekaTech/Wiz (incubation), and Magelis (Angoulême territorial frame). The repertoire is broad but loosely coordinated, and relies heavily on informal infrastructure — Slack, Discord, event culture — for operational cohesion.

SO Games operates a varied set of recurring events consistently confirmed across informants:

- GameConf and Game Invest, the two flagship international events — described as the cluster’s principal showcases — are co-organised by Magelis with SO Games, the CNC, the CNAM-ENJMIN, and Crédit Agricole Charente-Périgord (a local bank), combining meta-organisational, state-level, academic, and private-banking anchors.
- Horizon — an event oriented toward studio business operations (structuring a studio, managing admin/compta, financing), co-designed with Bordeaux Métropole. Horizon crystallises the cluster’s governance tensions: it was *“incredibly useful for the ecosystem but did not meet the Région’s needs”* (ML, #4).
- Spawn — a public-facing event with stronger indie orientation, organised by the CNAM-ENJMIN with the backing of the Région Nouvelle-Aquitaine, Magelis, and SO Games
- Annual game jam, described by AO (#3) as an event that even anchor-studio employees occasionally attend informally, despite anchor institutional disengagement.
- National events and afterworks such as Add-on, Game Camp, Game Biz, convening the indie community regularly. A small studio manager describes these gatherings as *“essential for exchanging information — which publisher is available, what kind of contract.”* JN (#1) These events thus function as informal business-intelligence channels.

Within SO Games, and alongside the event program, two digital infrastructures sustain day-to-day collaboration. The SO Games Slack, 700 to 800 members, operates as the principal meta-organisational communication space. Its design is deliberately open: non-member freelancers,

employees, and students are admitted to most channels, with member-only content confined to specific private channels. This open design was an explicit governance choice: “this choice *made sure that everyone was exposed to the news, the updates, the job offers. The non-member part is very active. It’s a good community that is alive*” (DE, #2). Complementing the SO Games Slack, an ecosystem of Discords – organised by affinity group (alumni CNAM, ex-Angoulême Jeux Vidéo) – provides denser, more curated sociality for sub-populations. Inter-cluster cooperation operates through many channels including JYROS consortium meetings, event-mediated encounters, individual cross-cluster board memberships, and SO Games delegations to Nordic Game and other European events – running in parallel with studio-level international engagement.

7.3.2.2 Structured functions and service architecture

Beyond relational facilitation, SO Games performs several structured services:

- Institutional intermediation and political representation: SO Games operates as the principal transmission belt between the industry and public institutions, at regional and national levels, particularly for the indie pole. The SNJV-reserved board seat contributes to institutionalising the regional-national pipeline.
- Policy priority translation: Digital sobriety, a Region priority, has been internalised by SO Games as a flagship theme, now carried to the SNJV and international working groups.
- Unity Excellence Center: SO Games operates a Unity Excellence Center concentrating expertise in the widely-used Unity engine – a technical-specialisation function.
- Recruitment and training professional conferences: This dedicated regional recruitment and training event addresses the persistent talent mismatch problem.
- Incubation — through EurekaTech/Wiz rather than SO Games: Wiz – operated by EurekaTech in Angoulême under Magelis and regional co-funding – is the cluster’s main incubation programme. Now in its fifth edition (pivoted from mixed ICC to 100% video game after four years), it has accompanied 24 projects and generated 13 company creations. The program counts 100 hours per project over six months, a dedicated expert pool (marketing, IP, specialised accountancy), co-location with the Pépinière Images and Chrysalide Fab Lab, and ENJMIN partnership (LB, #5). SO Games grants cohort participants free membership, Slack access, and subsidized event stands.
- Financial expertise and subsidy navigation: Wiz’s expert pool provides structured CNC dossier preparation and CIJV accompaniment. Crédit Agricole Charente-Périgord (a local bank) has assigned a dedicated banking officer to the image sector (LB, #5). Larger studios rely on a distinct architecture: AO (#3) describes a Bordeaux “banque d’innovation” relationship strategically maintained despite most specialized counsel being Paris- or London-based.

7.3.2.3 Resources & governance

The cluster’s collective-action capacity operates under significant resource constraints. SO Games employs only two permanent staff for a region the size of Switzerland – a constraint consistently identified as the principal limit on operational reach. One of the interviewees states bluntly: “we have a reduced headcount at SO Games – two, three people. Even small events take time.” ML (#4) The association depends heavily on board and member volunteer labour.

Governance is multi-layered – formal board for political representation, open working groups for operational programming, distributed Slack/Discord sociality for day-to-day exchange with three distinctive features:

- **Territorially representative board:** The ten-member board includes two statutorily reserved seats (Région, SNJV) and a minimum of six members distributed across the region’s departments, specifically designed to manage the bipolar geography and broader regional extension.
- **Differentiated membership committees:** Active members (contributing companies) hold voting rights whereas consultative members (associations, schools) participate without voting. The benefactor members provide financial support without operational involvement. The governance structure counts also “young professionals” membership which integrates emerging talent without a fee barrier. This committee architecture manages the three-pole tension by differentiating participation rights rather than homogenising them.
- **Mixed-bureau tripartite structure** (president, treasurer, secretary) with two-year renewable-once mandates ensuring leadership turnover. As one of the informants puts it, “to renew a community’s interest, the leaders must renew themselves regularly” (DE, #2)– a deliberate rotation-over-continuity design.

Recurring tensions – Ubisoft’s unsuccessful board candidacy, the large-studio retention debate, Horizon’s event programmatic dissonance – reflect the difficulty of reconciling the three poles within a single frame. Despite these tensions, the governance model is consistently described as operationally functional. Decision-making combines board authority for strategy, open working groups for programming, and general-assembly validation for statutory matters. One of our interviewees summarises: “the big decisions are made on the board, but there are working groups open to all members.” (ML, #4)

7.3.3 Cluster perimeter

The cluster’s perimeter is defined along three axes: territorial, institutional, and relational. Each exhibiting distinct boundaries.

7.3.3.1 Geographic perimeter

The cluster’s territorial perimeter is formally coextensive with the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region. Relational density, however, is strongly bipolar: two sub-poles emerge clearly — Bordeaux Métropole (anchored by Ubisoft, Asobo, Shiro Games, Motion Twin, Evil Empire, Big Bad Wolf,

Dotemu, Les Pancakes Délicieux) and Angoulême (anchored by the ENJMIN, Magelis, EurekaTech, the Wiz cohort, and a dense population of micro-studios including HeadBang Club, Seed by Seed, La Poule Noire). One cooperative cofounder (JN, #1) captures the asymmetric profiles: *“Angoulême with its fairly low rents is a refuge city with a myriad of small projects. It is a refuge city, a city of small budgets, a city of BD, a city of animation. Bordeaux is a bigger city, much longer distances, much less crossover, less density, many more large studios.”* Another informant reinforces this framing (DE, #2): *“it really is Angoulême and Bordeaux. Bordeaux has the very large ones and fewer small ones. The more time passes, the more the small ones come to Angoulême. It’s a binary star: one does not exist without the other.”* Beyond the two geographical poles, density drops sharply: La Rochelle hosts studio activity, while Poitiers, Limoges, and Pau host isolated studios without hub status.

7.3.3.2 Institutional perimeter: national & international

SO Games’ approximately 110 members constitute the formal cluster institutional boundary. The association’s representativeness is substantial but not exhaustive. Notable absences include Shiro Games and several mid-to-large studios. The institutional perimeter is mediated through SO Games’ relationships with the SNJV, Capital Games, Game Only, and through individual studio-level engagement with national institutions. Two distinctive features emerge: active individual SNJV engagements (currently and in the past) – AO (#3) holds a personal board mandate as a compensatory channel for weak local operational coordination — and an extroverted international posture described (Nordic Game, Develop Brighton, Reboot, Serbia, Japan, Canada.) Four informants nonetheless converge on the diagnosis that national coordination functions imperfectly, suggesting a structural feature of the French cluster system rather than a cluster-specific pathology. This is partitioned across the three poles in distinctive ways. Anchor studios (Ubisoft, Asobo, Shiro Games) operate within global publisher or platform networks hermetically sealed from the local ecosystem. Mid-size Triple-I studios operate specialised international peer networks (one informant’s studio organises private GDC gatherings; other mid-size studios rely on publisher networks). The indie pole operates through SO Games delegations, specialised international publishers sought individually, and emerging institutional channels (EurekaTech–Mexico, potential Spielfabrique acceleration).

7.3.3.3 Political perimeter

The Region, Bordeaux Métropole, and Grand Angoulême are consistently described as cooperative partners. One subtle political-perimeter feature is the historical institutional identity friction surrounding the SO Games fusion: the fusion carried a genuine risk – *“people in Angoulême did not necessarily recognise themselves in a regional cluster the size of Switzerland. We had to fight for people to understand that it was still their tool, just made bigger.”* DE (#2) Sub-regional pride versus regional-scale institutional efficacy remains an ongoing tension that the territorially representative board design attempts to contain.

7.3.4 Value chain

The cluster is functionally complete in creative production – AAA (Ubisoft, Asobo), Triple-I (Evil Empire, Motion Twin), indie and porting – but structurally dependent on external actors for publishing, distribution, and specialized services (legal, financial, specialized creative). A distinctive **T4.4** finding is that local intra-cluster commercial relationships are substantially thin. The two anchor studios operate within fully integrated global value chains controlled by their parent organizations. Ubisoft Bordeaux contributes to Assassin’s Creed titles coordinated within Ubisoft’s international network; Asobo’s flagship project (Microsoft Flight Simulator) is developed under a twenty-year Microsoft partnership. Outsourcing – as DE (#2) observes – flows predominantly to large international providers (Keywords, Virtuos) rather than local indies, for QA (Quality Assurance) and scale reasons.

Mid-size Triple-I studios present a sharper value-chain separation from the local economy than Lyon’s mid-size independents. One Triple-I director (AO, #3) provides the most explicit articulation based on his own experience: *“I realise, having this conversation, that if I really talk about actors in the value chain and in my collaborations, I have tended to separate myself from local partners rather than the opposite. When I arrived, on my core-business skills, I had people who were not specialised enough. Naturally, I turned to others — my lawyers, for example: today, I no longer have a Bordeaux lawyer on any of my matters. On core-business topics, I left again with people based between Paris and London.”* The only local value-chain interaction AO reports having deliberately preserved is a banking relationship – *“a relationship with an innovation bank in Bordeaux”* – and an emerging audio/music production relationship with a local provider linked to the ENJMIN. Even these links are framed as effortful preservation against a structural delocalisation tendency.

The same informant also offers an analytically important framing of the broader value-chain question: *“what I observe in video games is that there is very, very little outsourcing or collaboration. We internalise the know-how, taking on the financial risk it implies – we operate in project economies. Paradoxically, I have difficulty seeing a genuinely distributed value chain, because we internalise everything.”* The pattern combines a general industry feature – internalisation-driven project economies – with a Bordeaux variant where weak local specialised-service supply compounds the tendency: ambitious studios build teams locally (the Kalisto diaspora supplying the senior pool) but source specialised non-labour inputs (legal, financial, specialised art or audio, technical specialities) from Paris, London, or internationally. For indie studios, the value chain is fragmented and individually negotiated – a complexity that Wiz, the CNAM-ENJMIN incubator, and the marketing-/publishing-oriented service-provider niche directly address.

A distinctive Bordeaux value-chain feature is the significant role of porting and technical-services studios. One indie studio operates as a specialised provider – console portings, Epic Games Store adaptations, platform-specific optimisations – for third-party publishers and studios, including Dotemu (Paris), Sylvan Studios (Angers), and Graphite Lab (US). Though operationally globalised, the niche contributes at cluster level by disseminating technical capacity and platform expertise through cross-fertilisation with the ENJMIN and the indie community. Plug-In-Digital, a French

editor, plays an analogous role on distribution, operating a network of more than 200 resellers (Epic, Steam, Games Planet) and serving as a distribution interface for cluster-member studios.

Another important local feature of the local video game value chain is the financing gap which persists at the interface between public subsidy and market financing. The cluster lacks meaningful venture capital presence, and the absence of pre-IPO growth financing constrains studio trajectories from mid-size to large. Public support at project level (regional aid fund, CNC CIJV, supplemented by Magelis in Angoulême) is substantive, but the equity-financing layer between project subsidy and international commercial scale remains underdeveloped.

There is also a cross-sector dimension in the Bordeaux-Angoulême context. A representative of a local hub (LB, #5) notes growing use of game engines in animation. The ENJMIN's curriculum increasingly addresses this convergence. Angoulême's "quartier de l'image" (2,500 professionals across BD, animation, cinema, and video game) generates cross-fertilisation unavailable to a purely video-game geography. Wiz's four years of mixed ICC cohorts left also a cross-disciplinary alumni network; its subsequent pure-video-game specialization nonetheless indicates that the diversification logic faces operational constraints.

7.4 Conclusion

The **T4.4** mapping reveals a Bordeaux/Nouvelle-Aquitaine cluster with bipolar architecture, three-pole ideological-functional structuring, plural institutional governance, and a structurally thin local value chain coexisting with a dense but socially mediated indie community.

Several vulnerabilities warrant attention. SO Games' resource constraints limit operational reach and leave certain coordination functions structurally under-developed. The continuing tension between large-studio representation imperatives and operational disengagement generates recurring governance dissonance, crystallised in cases like Horizon event. These coexist with distinctive strengths: the open-channel Slack philosophy which generates vitality; the distributed governance architecture which is more resilient to single-institutional failure than integrated-hub models; the ENJMIN's talent pipeline whose quality is universally recognized; the Kalisto diaspora which provides a continued legitimising relational substrate; and the cluster's international orientation.

8 FUNDÃO

8.1 Overview of the Cluster

Fundão is a municipality located in the Castelo Branco District of central Portugal, within the Beiras and Serra da Estrela sub-region (NUTS 3). The municipality has long been known for its rich agricultural landscape, particularly its cherry cultivation, with the fertile land supporting fruit production for centuries. However, like many interior Portuguese regions, Fundão has faced significant demographic and economic challenges in recent decades.

As documented in prior deliverables of the present project, particularly research conducted under WP4 of the **GAME-ER** project, these challenges have rendered economic diversification a central strategic priority for the municipality. Over the past two decades, Fundão has undergone a substantial transformation, transitioning from a predominantly agricultural economy toward one increasingly oriented around technology and innovation. Among the strategic decisions taken by the municipality in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic was a deliberate focus on the rising video game industry, capitalising on broader trends within Portugal's digital economy. Fundão today stands as a notable case study of a rural municipality successfully leveraging strategic vision, institutional support, and quality-of-life factors to develop a nascent but growing gaming cluster. Its evolution from a predominantly agricultural economy to a technology-driven hub constitutes a relevant reference point for other rural territories seeking to diversify their economic base and attract knowledge-intensive industries.

8.2 Data Collection

Data collection for the actor mapping exercise was conducted between September and November 2025, with primary empirical data gathered through a participatory workshop held in the municipality of Fundão on 23 October 2025, coinciding with the inauguration of the **GAME-ER** Gaming Lab. The timing of the workshop was strategically determined by the concentration of cluster stakeholders and strategic partners present at the event, thereby maximising the representativeness of the participant pool. **A total of 36 participants (N=36)** attended the session dedicated to actor mapping, the majority of whom were based in Fundão or in adjacent municipalities within the cluster's periphery. All participants were informed of the purpose of the mapping exercise and the objectives of **T4.4** and provided informed consent in compliance with GDPR requirements. Consistent with patterns recorded in earlier phases of the research, the gender distribution exhibited a pronounced male predominance.

Participants were organised into independent groups through a randomised allocation procedure, with stratification applied according to actor typology – encompassing policy, education, and game development, among others – to ensure adequate thematic coverage across the cluster ecosystem. Each group was tasked with identifying and mapping actors and organisations relevant to the innovation and video game ecosystem in Fundão. Each group designated a spokesperson responsible for presenting the group's mapping rationale and methodological decisions to a representative of INOVA+ and to the assembled participants. These presentations were recorded to

serve as a supplementary qualitative data source for the elaboration of both the intermediary and final actor mapping outputs.

8.3 Actor Mapping

As set out in the preceding Data Collection section, the Fundão cluster is characterised by an early-stage configuration: it exhibits a strong community identity but a relatively concentrated actor base, with a limited number of organisations accounting for the bulk of cluster activities. Cluster members are actively engaged in efforts to attract new companies and key stakeholders to the territory, with the aim of broadening the value chain and addressing existing gaps in skills and talent supply. During the workshop, four classification tiers were employed to structure the mapping exercise (see Figure 19): *core* (central actors), *important* (relevant actors), *emergent* (peripheral actors), and *external* (partners located outside Fundão). This classification framework enabled the localisation of actors not only within the cluster’s core but also across its tenuous periphery, the broader regional innovation ecosystem, and the national institutional landscape.

Figure 19: Actor mapping template used during the actor mapping workshop

Each group was assigned to a dedicated mapping canvas, facilitated by a member of the INOVA+ research team responsible for the study of the Fundão cluster under **WP4**. During the session, participants articulated their reasoning as they constructed the maps; these verbal accounts were recorded for subsequent analytical reference. Collectively, participants identified 44 actors and

organisations, which were subsequently digitised and transferred to a Miro collaborative board to produce a comprehensive ecosystem map.

Figure 20: Actor mapping workshop – teams creating and presenting their maps

Across the different groups, a degree of convergence was observed, particularly with regard to educational and municipal actors, most notably the Universidade da Beira Interior (UBI) and the Câmara Municipal do Fundão (CMF). **Figures 20–22** present examples of draft mapping exercises carried out by participants during the workshop. A colour-coding scheme was established for the sticky notes annotations employed during the session: (a) blue denoted gaming companies, studios, and initiatives; (b) yellow indicated educational and research Actors; (c) green represented public

bodies and organisations; and (d) light orange identified community and gaming events relevant to the cluster.

Figure 21: Example of an individual actor map (Fundão)

Figure 22: Example of an individual actor map (Fundão)

Following the workshop, the research team independently developed an internal conceptual map based on the data synthesised in **D4.1** and **D4.2**. This preliminary exercise aimed to establish a shared analytical reference framework, facilitating systematic comparison with participants' representations and supporting the organisation of subsequent research phases. The combined analysis of the individual group maps and the recorded session material enabled the construction of an intermediate summary map (**Figure 23**).

Figure 23: Draft version of the final map (Fundão)

The resulting map was subsequently subjected to a review and validation process involving key stakeholders of the Fundão cluster, most notably representatives of the Câmara Municipal do Fundão (CMF), the principal institutional driver of the cluster’s development, as extensively documented in **D4.1**.

8.3.1 Key Actors and Features

Figure 24: Final actor map (Fundão)

Unlike many European gaming clusters that emerged organically from pre-existing creative or digital entertainment industries, Fundão historically lacked any significant video game sector. Its rural and agrarian heritage meant that the cluster’s emergence would necessarily require deliberate policy intervention and targeted infrastructure development, rather than the gradual consolidation of an established industry base. Fundão’s actor map accordingly positions the Câmara Municipal do Fundão at its centre, reflecting an ecosystem that is fundamentally policy-driven and deliberately constructed through sustained municipal intervention.

The Fundão map organises actors into three primary layers: (1) the gaming ecosystem, (2) the cultural intermediaries and innovation ecosystem, and (3) the national ecosystem, within which several overlapping sub-ecosystems are nested, including the education, co-creation, and partnerships ecosystems. This concentric structure, validated through the workshop process, illustrates how gaming activity in Fundão is embedded within, and remains dependent upon, a broader territorial innovation strategy that predates the cluster’s gaming-specific orientation.

Within the gaming ecosystem, CMF operates as the *de facto* cluster management organisation, providing venues, funding, staff capacity, and convening authority; as one game developer noted: *“CMF is of utmost relevance due to its continuous support and investment in several initiatives.”* Across all workshop groups, participants consistently identified CMF as the most central actor in the ecosystem, corroborating the hub-and-spoke governance model documented in **D4.1**, even as the network has begun to evolve toward a more distributed configuration.

The video game industry component of the cluster remains limited in scale. [Digitality Games](#) is the only dedicated gaming studio with a permanent physical presence in Fundão, occupying a central position in participants’ maps as the anchor firm for the gaming-specific segment. One Game design and development Master student observed: *“It makes perfect sense for us to place Digitality Games as a key actor here in Fundão, as we recognise that those who make video games and understand their processes have a great deal of knowledge. They are a key part and a catalyst of the ecosystem.”* Beyond Digitality Games, several companies participate through the municipality’s Online Incubation Programme, a distinctive mechanism through which primarily Brazilian studios (EduHub, SERA462, Hibuddy, Desvenda, Aequitas, among others) maintain remote engagement with the cluster whilst preparing for potential physical relocation. The anticipated arrival of an additional studio is expected to deepen the cluster’s human capital base, expanding the pool of resident game developers and specialist talent.

The educational dimension of the cluster is anchored by the [Universidade da Beira Interior](#) (UBI), a regional university that launched Portugal’s first university-level programme dedicated to video game development in 2012, and which constitutes the primary talent pipeline for the cluster. Participants consistently identified UBI as a key actor, alongside the [Instituto de Emprego e Formação Profissional \(IEFP\)](#), the Fundão School Network, [Castelo Branco Polytechnic \(IPCB\)](#), and [Lusófona University](#). The Code Academy (*Academia do Código*), a bootcamp initiative co-promoted by the municipality, functions as a complementary reskilling mechanism, providing structured pathways for local youth and lower-skilled workers seeking entry into the digital sector. According to a Fundão-based tech professional, the region has seen strong collaboration between UBI, the

CMF, and the IEFP in Covilhã to address regional challenges, particularly talent attraction. This professional emphasised that *“the recruitment of people from outside the region has been actively worked on through highly targeted programmes, with the role of the IEFP being fundamental.”* Similarly, an association representative remarked on the significance of local educational institutions like UBI, explaining that they *“allow talent to be developed locally, preventing students from having to move to Porto or Lisbon to study video game [development].”* Regarding IPCB, one male software student commented that he *“must recognise the role of this institution in the development of the Fundão ecosystem, bringing ideas, new tools, and fostering technologies that ultimately improve the economy and development of the region.”*

The [Portuguese E-Sports Federation](#) (*Federação Portuguesa de Desportos Eletrónicos*, FPDE) also features prominently on the map as a central actor within the gaming ecosystem, reflecting the productive intersection between competitive gaming and the broader game development community.

The map further identifies a set of significant co-creation actors situated at the interface between the gaming core and the wider cultural and innovation ecosystems. As illustrated in **Figure 12 of D4.2**, these actors display a notable degree of geographical concentration. Among them are [A Moagem](#), the [Fab Lab Aldeias do Xisto](#), and the Centro de Acolhimento de Empresas Tecnológicas (CAET) — entities that contribute to the creative and innovation environment without being directly engaged in game production. Their presence illustrates how the gaming cluster both draws upon and reinforces a broader strategy of territorial innovation, in which gaming constitutes one specialised strand within a more encompassing vision of rural economic transformation. Fundão-based tech professional mentioned that *“FabLab is also a determining factor; I think it was what first drew me to explore the whole Fundão ecosystem, where they have a lot of machines with very easy access for anyone.”*

8.3.2 Collective Actions

At the heart of Fundão’s collective action framework are regular networking events that create structured opportunities for interaction among diverse ecosystem actors. Collective actions in the Fundão cluster are characterised by a high degree of municipal coordination and a dual orientation: (a) local community-building on the one hand, and (b) external visibility and networking on the other. At the local level, the most distinctive initiative is *Café na Praça*, an informal networking forum held at the A Praça Incubator where tech professionals, entrepreneurs, and students exchange ideas over coffee. Thematic nationality lunches – gatherings celebrating the cultural diversity of Fundão’s international community – serve a complementary role, strengthening social cohesion within the cluster’s notably cosmopolitan workforce (approximately 4,000 foreign nationals from 78 countries reside in the municipality). As a male entrepreneur from the Fundão Innovation Ecosystem noted: *“one of the advantages of being in a space like this, an incubator like the one here in Fundão, is the networking that happens and the partnerships formed between the startups that are here. Café na Praça has brought several companies and startups from the region.”*

Training and capacity-building represent a second pillar of collective action, as one participant pointed out: *“Fundão’s job fair is very relevant as it brings new qualified talent to the region.”* However, also the Code Academy bootcamp, co-promoted by the municipality and IEFP, provides structured reskilling programmes. Additional training sessions, bootcamps, and pitching workshops are regularly organised, often co-funded by regional grants or corporate sponsors. These initiatives address shared skill gaps identified by cluster members and are closely aligned with educational institutions’ talent development activities. The **GAME-ER** project itself is positioned on the map as a collective action linking the Gaming Lab, CMF, and the broader ecosystem. Over the past three years, it has played a significant role in the development of the cluster by supporting its establishment, providing funding, enabling the acquisition of equipment, and fostering community-building processes. In this regard, Fundão offers a distinctive context for the practical validation and further development of several **GAME-ER** policy recommendations, as one of the two pilots of the project.

External participation constitutes a third dimension, represented on the map in the national ecosystem, inside the partnerships sphere. The cluster collectively participates in national showcases such as Lisboa Games Week and WebSummit, external activities typically coordinated and partially funded through municipal resources; one male student pointed out: *“Games Week is an annual event of great relevance for showcasing the best in video game development in Portugal and could potentially bring investors to the region in the future”*, and another added that *“many people from Fundão participate in Games Week and end up bringing various contacts and experiences with different professionals.”*

Fundão’s collective actions are more institutionally mediated and less community-driven. This reflects the cluster’s nascent stage: the small number of dedicated gaming companies limits the scope for purely industry-led initiatives, making municipal facilitation not only valuable but necessary. In this context, a male entrepreneur remarked: *“There are several initiatives in collaboration with the University of Beira Interior and even with Fundão Universe. The ecosystem has been highly dynamic in promoting networking and in developing initiatives focused on knowledge transfer and sharing.”*

8.3.3 Cluster Perimeter

The perimeter of the Fundão cluster is simultaneously well-defined in institutional terms and ambiguous in spatial and sectoral ones. The innermost ring, the gaming ecosystem, constitutes the cluster’s core, comprising CMF, the Portuguese E-Sports Federation (FPDE), the Online Incubation Programme, the Gaming Lab, and its connections with the education ecosystem, particularly UBI and its game development lab, G3DLab. As one video game development Master’s student stated: *“UBI, and especially G3DLab, is of utmost importance as the former students who created Digitality went through there and today are one of the most important actors in the cluster.”* This core is tightly bounded and small in scale; however, a narrow definition centred solely on this ring would exclude much of what renders the Fundão case analytically distinctive.

The second ring, the co-creation ecosystem, incorporates incubation facilities, co-creation spaces, and innovation infrastructure that are integral to the cluster’s functioning, even though they are not gaming-specific. These entities represent the foundational layer from which the gaming cluster itself emerged as a specialised strand of the broader innovation ecosystem.

The third ring, the cultural intermediaries/innovation ecosystem, encompasses creative infrastructures as well as technology companies whose presence in Fundão validates the municipality’s diversification strategy and whose employees contribute to the wider talent community from which gaming professionals are drawn. Spatially, the cluster’s perimeter extends beyond the administrative boundaries of the municipality. UBI, the cluster’s primary educational anchor, is situated in Covilhã (approximately 20 km from Fundão), yet is universally perceived by participants as internal to the ecosystem; Castelo Branco Polytechnic (IPCB), located in Castelo Branco, occupies a comparable position. The relevant spatial frame is therefore closer to the Beiras and Serra da Estrela sub-region (NUTS 3) than to the municipality of Fundão alone, even as CMF and its associated infrastructure remain the gravitational centre of the ecosystem.

The Online Incubation Programme introduces a further dimension of complexity: the Brazilian companies participating remotely are functionally integrated into the ecosystem while remaining physically located outside Portugal. Their anticipated eventual relocation to Fundão suggests a cluster perimeter that is not only geographically elastic but also temporally dynamic.

At the national level, several actors sit outside the cluster’s perimeter whilst maintaining important bridging functions. Associação de Produtores de Videojogos Portugueses ([APVP](#)), as the national game developers’ association, connects Fundão to the broader Portuguese industry and to international representation; [AICEP](#), the Portuguese trade and investment agency, facilitates international visibility; [gaminghub Lisboa](#) provides national coordination infrastructure; eGamesLab situates Fundão within a nationwide R&D network; and [SPCV \(Portuguese Society for Video Game Science\)](#) and [Portugal Ventures](#) occupy analogous positions within the national ring. These actors do not constitute part of the Fundão cluster per se, but are essential to its integration within national and international circuits. One male participant added that *“the Rural MOVE initiative is also a relevant organisation at a national level that promotes the relocation of digital nomads to rural regions in the interior of Portugal.”* The partnerships ecosystem, depicted as a dashed outer region on the map, captures the external events and platforms through which the cluster gains visibility and establishes connections, without these being considered constituent elements of the cluster itself.

8.3.4 Value Chain

The Fundão cluster presents a markedly incomplete yet strategically oriented configuration in terms of the video game industry value chain. Its position within the global production network is best characterised as emerging and peripheral, with deliberate institutional efforts underway to build the missing components. On the production side, Digitality Games and the small number of resident studios focus primarily on game development for PC, mobile, and VR platforms. Most companies are micro-enterprises operating within an indie production model. Business-to-business activity – including work-for-hire and service provision for external clients – coexists with business-to-

consumer projects, with the balance varying across individual companies. The broader technology companies present in Fundão (Cappgemini, Readiness IT, and others) contribute indirectly to the value chain through talent circulation, shared infrastructure, and the creation of a general technology employment market that reduces the risk for individuals entering the gaming sector. Publishing is absent from the local ecosystem. No local or national publisher operates within the cluster, and Fundão-based studios rely either on self-publishing through digital distribution platforms or on external publishing arrangements. The educational segment of the value chain is comparatively well-developed relative to the cluster's overall scale. UBI's game development programme, the Code Academy, IPCB's associated programmes, and various supplementary training initiatives collectively generate a talent pipeline that, paradoxically, exceeds the cluster's current absorption capacity. The incubation and acceleration segment represents a distinctive feature of Fundão's value chain. The A Praça incubator and the Online Incubation Programme provide early-stage company support mechanisms that are unusual for a cluster of this size, reflecting the municipality's deliberate strategy of constructing value chain components from the top down rather than waiting for them to emerge organically.

Distribution, retail, and intellectual property management functions are largely absent from the local ecosystem. The cluster does not host specialised gaming events, trade fairs, or dedicated media outlets of its own. National events – including Lisboa Games Week, Game Dev Camp, and Indie X – together with APVP's coordination activities, partially compensate for this gap; however, Fundão-based actors engage with these resources as participants rather than organisers.

In summary, Fundão's value chain is narrow but vertically ambitious: it encompasses education, incubation, and early-stage development, whilst remaining structurally dependent on national and international actors for publishing, distribution, visibility, and market access. The municipality's infrastructure investments, most notably the Gaming Lab, represent a deliberate attempt to deepen this value chain over time, progressively establishing the conditions for a more complete local production ecosystem.

8.4 Conclusions

The actor mapping exercise not only corroborates but also strengthens the insights derived from the project's previous research (**D4.1, D4.2 and D4.3**). Throughout the process, participants consistently highlighted the Câmara Municipal do Fundão as the central coordinating entity within the ecosystem, positioning it as the primary nexus that connects the diverse stakeholders comprising the Fundão gaming cluster. In parallel, UBI emerges as the second pivotal node, underpinning the educational dimension and facilitating the talent pipeline crucial for the cluster's ongoing development. The map produced through this exercise offers a comprehensive and coherent overview, clearly delineating the core actors and solidifying the cluster's collective identity within the local community. Although still in its early stages, the cluster demonstrates tangible signs of consolidation, as evidenced by the reaffirmation of actor configurations and operational mechanisms initially outlined in earlier deliverables.

However, a significant challenge remains in the value chain, which continues to exhibit structural uncertainties. Notably, gaps persist in the domains of publishing, distribution, and market access, compelling the cluster to depend heavily on external national and international entities to fulfil these critical functions. Rather than adhering to a conventional linear production model, the local value chain is characterised by a dynamic and overlapping web of relationships that intertwines gaming companies, educational institutions, and the broader innovation infrastructure driven by the municipality. Another key observation concerns CMF's dual institutional role: it not only ensures the internal cohesion of the local ecosystem but also plays a crucial part in positioning the cluster within both national and international networks. These two functions (internal coordination and external visibility) are indispensable for the cluster's sustainable growth beyond its current scale. The continued alignment of these roles will be vital to ensuring the long-term viability and expansion of the Fundão gaming cluster.

9 CONCLUSION

This deliverable presents in-depth mapping of actors of the six video game industry clusters examined within the **GAME-ER** project. The analysis draws on the principles of social network analysis and prior scholarship on video game production ecosystems. It employs relatively novel qualitative methodology by combining an ethnographic interview method with a visualisation exercise, guiding a respondent through a task of describing the key cluster actors, their activities, and relationships. This process yielded rich data, which further build on previous deliverables from WP4 and highlight the specific composition of each cluster, including game development companies as well as other actors and institutions, such as schools and universities or various cultural intermediaries.

The outcome of this task is two-fold. First, each cluster is represented by a final actor map, which shows main actors, activities, and relationship in a visual manner, highlighting the central actors, but also the cluster periphery and connections outside the cluster's spatial borders. Second, the six chapters also provide a detailed analysis of the relationships between the actors based on interview transcripts collected as part of mapping sessions. Together, the report provides a quick visual overview of each of the six clusters as well as more in-depth exploration of their inner workings. Compared to the previous **WP4** deliverables, which often highlighted the historical evolution and thus took a diachronic approach to the study of video game industry clusters, this report focuses on the current state of the **GAME-ER** clusters. Some recent changes and developments are reflected in the analysis, but the approach is at its core synchronic.

The analysis shows the complexity of video game industry clusters and the importance of collective actions as well as the diversity of actors involved. While previous WP4 deliverables, for example, addressed the governance and coordination of clusters in more general terms, this report shows the concrete relationships through which the cluster is established and sustained. In this sense, this report complements earlier findings but importantly reflects on the practical and logistical aspects of video game industry clusters and how they manifest through relationships between various actors and their collective activities.

Lastly, the observations gathered on the level of each of the six **GAME-ER** clusters will be crucial for the comparative work carried out in WP3. In particular, this report provides insights into the types of actors represented within each cluster, highlighting unique or missing components, the differences in centrality between these actors across the six clusters, as well as each cluster's placement in relation to the video game industry value chain.

10 REFERENCES

- Bennett, James, Smyth, Sarah, Woolard, Adrian, et al. 2025. *CoSTAR National Lab Annual Report Oct 2023 – Dec 2025*. CoSTAR Network.
https://cms.costarnetwork.co.uk/api/media/file/CoSTAR_NationalLabAnnualReport_Oct23Dec25.pdf
- Browne, Pierson, and Brian R. Schram. 2021. 'Intermediating the Everyday: Indie Game Development and the Labour of Co-Working Spaces'. In *Game Production Studies*, edited by Olli Sotamaa and Jan Švelch. Amsterdam University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1hp5hqw.7>.
- Bulut, Ergin. 2020. *A Precarious Game: The Illusion of Dream Jobs in the Video Game Industry*. ILR Press, an imprint of Cornell University Press.
- Consalvo, Mia. 2006. 'Console Video Games and Global Corporations: Creating a Hybrid Culture'. *New Media & Society* 8 (1): 117–37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444806059921>.
- Costalunga Nicola, Fassone Riccardo, Gómez-Urrego José David, et al. 2026. *D4.3 Historical Development of Clusters*.
- Creative Communities. Co-Creating Growth: Dundee Creative Spaces City.
<https://creativecommunities.uk/co-creating-growth-dundee-creative-spaces-city/>
- Creative Dundee. "Fabric: Peer-led space to share, reflect and imagine how collective action can shape a better tomorrow." <https://createdundee.com/fabric/>
- Davies, Hugh. 2024. 'Independent Game Production in Southern China'. *Media Industries* 11 (1): 1.
<https://doi.org/10.3998/mij.3914>.
- De Paoli, Stefano, Luís Leça, Tânia Moreira, et al. 2025. *D4.1 - Report on Primary Data Collection*. November 5. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535331>.
- De Paoli, Stefano, Costalunga Nicola, Fassone Riccardo, et al. 2025. *D4.2 - Report on Document Analysis*.
- Dubois, Louis-Etienne, and Johanna Weststar. 2021. 'Games-as-a-Service: Conflicted Identities on the New Front-Line of Video Game Development'. *New Media & Society* 24 (8): 2332-2353.
- Dundee Creates. *Dundee's Creative Industries Strategy 2017-2021*.
<https://dundeecreates.creativedundee.com/>
- Dutch Game Garden. 2024. *Dutch Game Garden to close its doors after 17 years as of 2025: End of an era for the Dutch games industry*. <https://www.dutchgamegarden.nl/dutch-game-garden-to-close-its-doors/>
- Dutch Game Garden. 2025. *About Dutch Game Garden*. <https://www.dutchgamegarden.nl/home-old/>
- FEE CTU. 2025. *Prague has launched a new game accelerator. Half of the teams are made up of FEE CTU students*. <http://fel.cvut.cz/en/what-s-on/news/81935-prague-has-launched-a-new-game-accelerator-half-of-the-teams-are-made-up-of-fee-ctu-students>
- Game Cluster. 2022. *Brno Game Jam 2022*. Itch.io. <https://itch.io/jam/brno-game-jam-2022>

- Gamebaze. 2025. *Gamebaze_course*. <https://gamebaze.cz/course/>
- GameDev Area. 2025. *GDA Network. Projects*. <https://gamedevarea.com/projects/>
- GameDev Area. 2026. *Game Access Music*. <https://gamedevarea.com/projects/game-access-music/>
- Gamer Pie. 2026. *Gamer Pie History*. <https://www.gamerpie.wtf/en/#history>
- Gamestudies.cz. 2025. *About us*. MU Game Studies Association. <https://gamestudies.cz/en/about-us>
- Gislaam, Charlotte, Garry Crawford, Gaynor Bagnall, Victoria Gosling, and Neta Yodovich. 2025. 'Do Video Games Matter? Examining Video Games' Pathways to Legitimacy and Cultural Value Through Cultural Intermediaries'. *Games and Culture*, Online First. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15554120251341621>.
- Gómez-Urrego, Jose & O'Regan, Wren. Forthcoming. *Creative Clusters in the Video Games Industry*. Routledge.
- González-Piñero, Manel. 2017. 'Redefining the Value Chain of the Video Games Industry'. *Memory* 36 (4): 75–90.
- Harvey, Alison. 2019. 'Becoming Gamesworkers: Diversity, Higher Education, and the Future of the Game Industry'. *Television & New Media* 20 (8): 756–66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1527476419851080>.
- Hernández-Bécares, Jennifer, Luis Costero, and Pedro Pablo Gómez-Martín. 2017. 'An Approach to Automated Videogame Beta Testing'. *Entertainment Computing* 18 (January): 79–92.
- Immersive Arts. 2026. *The Game*. <https://immersivarts.uk/projects/the-game/>
- Johns, Jennifer. 2006. 'Video Games Production Networks: Value Capture, Power Relations and Embeddedness'. *Journal of Economic Geography* 6 (2): 151–80. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeg/lbi001>.
- Kerr, Aphra. 2017. *Global Games: Production, Circulation and Policy in the Networked Era*. Routledge.
- Lehtonen, Miikka J., Antti Ainamo, and J Harviainen. 2020. 'The Four Faces of Creative Industries: Visualising the Game Industry Ecosystem in Helsinki and Tokyo'. *Industry and Innovation* 27 (9): 1062–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2019.1676704>.
- Lehtonen, Miikka J., Katharina S. Schilli, and J. Tuomas Harviainen. 2022. 'Resilient Values in Game Industry Formation: Institutional Perspective to the Finnish Context'. *Games and Culture* 17 (4): 614–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15554120211049572>.
- Maiuga, Alexandra. 2025a. 'The Foreigner Indie Video Game Community in Japan from Tokyo Indies to Bitsummit'. *Youth and Globalization* 6 (1–2): 98–123. <https://doi.org/10.1163/25895745-bja10037>.
- Maiuga, Alexandra. 2025b. 'The Role of Grassroots Indie Game Events: How Occupational Communities Help Expatriates Integrate In Japan'. *Replaying Japan* 7 (March): 131–42.

- Mančář, Michal. 2025. 'Značka Kingdom Come je silnější než Zaklínač. Prodeje merche jsou neuvěřitelné, říká šéf obchodu Xzone'. *CzechCrunch*. <https://cc.cz/znacka-kingdom-come-je-silnejsi-nez-zaklinac-prodeje-merche-jsou-neuveritelne-rika-sef-obchodu-xzone/>
- McSwan, A., Austin, H., Brown, H., Johnson, G., Livesey-Stephens, B., Love, L., Lynagh, M., Sloan, R.J.S., Xiaoxiong, X., 2024. *InGAME international Pathway To Collaboration: UKChina Collaboration in Games*. Abertay University. https://innovationforgames.com/ingame_international/china-and-the-uk-a-pathway-to-collaboration/
- MUNI. 2025. *MU Game Studies*. <https://www.muni.cz/en/students/join-the-community/student-clubs-associations/mu-game-studies>
- Ozimek, Anna. 2019. 'Outsourcing Digital Game Production: The Case of Polish Testers'. *Television & New Media* 20 (8): 824–35. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1527476419851088>.
- Ozimek, Anna. 2021. 'Supporting the Global Digital Games Industry: Outsourcing Games Production in Poland and Estonia'. In *Topologies of Digital Work: How Digitalisation and Virtualisation Shape Working Spaces and Places*, edited by Mascha Will-Zocholl and Caroline Roth-Ebner. Dynamics of Virtual Work. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80327-8_3.
- Paris, Thomas, and Stefano De Paoli. 2025. D3.1 - Analysis Grid and Interview Script. November 6. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17542326>.
- Parker, Felan, and Matthew E. Perks. 2021. 'Streaming Ambivalence: Livestreaming and Indie Game Development'. *Convergence* 27 (6): 1735–52.
- Parker, Felan, Jennifer R. Whitson, and Bart Simon. 2018. 'Megaboost: The Cultural Intermediation of Indie Games'. *New Media & Society* 20 (5): 1953–72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444817711403>.
- Perks, Matthew E., Felan Parker, Jennifer R. Whitson, et al. 2019. 'Autonomy, Integration, and the Work of Cultural Intermediation in Indie Games'. *Media Industries* 6 (2): 17–38.
- Porter, Michael E. 2000. 'Location, Competition, and Economic Development: Local Clusters in a Global Economy'. *Economic Development Quarterly* 14 (1): 15–34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/089124240001400105>.
- Scottish Construction Now. 2024. *Capacity reduced at proposed Dundee esports arena*. <https://www.scottishconstructionnow.com/articles/capacity-reduced-at-proposed-dundee-esports-arena>
- SpielFabrique. 2025. *SpielFabrique—About*. <https://spielfabrique.eu/Thunderfox/#anchor-about>
- Švelch, Jaroslav. 2021. 'Promises of the Periphery: Producing Games in the Communist and Transformation-Era Czechoslovakia'. In *Game Production Studies*, edited by Olli Sotamaa and Jan Švelch. Amsterdam University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1hp5hqw.15>.
- The Audience Agency. 2026. *Valuing Creative and Cultural R&D and Innovation*. <https://theaudienceagency.org/en/valuing-creative-and-cultural-rd-and-innovation>

- Thorhauge, Anne Mette. 2023. *Games in the Platform Economy: Steam's Tangled Markets*. Bristol University Press.
- VisionGame. 2025. *Ateliér Duchů*. <https://visiongame.cz/studio/atelier-duchu/>
- Wasserman, Stanley, and Katherine Faust. 1994. *Social Network Analysis: Methods and Applications*. Structural Analysis in the Social Sciences. Cambridge University Press.
- Whitson, Jennifer R, Bart Simon, and Felan Parker. 2021. 'The Missing Producer: Rethinking Indie Cultural Production in Terms of Entrepreneurship, Relational Labour, and Sustainability'. *European Journal of Cultural Studies* 24 (2): 606–27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1367549418810082>.
- Whitson, Jennifer R. 2018. 'Voodoo Software and Boundary Objects in Game Development: How Developers Collaborate and Conflict with Game Engines and Art Tools'. *New Media & Society* 20 (7): 2315–32.
- Wong, K. T. 2024. 'Globalization and Heterogeneity: Locating the Malaysian Indie Game Production Culture'. *Media Industries* 11 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.3998/mij.3882>.
- Woodcock, J. 2021. 'Game Workers Unite: unionization among independent developers', in P. Ruffino (ed) *Independent Videogames: Cultures, Networks, Techniques And Politics*, 163–174. Routledge.
- Xzone.cz. 2024. *Tisková zpráva: Xzone otevřel svoji největší prodejnu a herní HUB*. <https://www.xzone.cz/tiskova-zprava-xzone-otevrel-svoji-nejvetsi-prodejnu-a-herni-hub-2024>
- Yodovich, Neta, Gaynor Bagnall, Garry Crawford, Charlotte Gislam, and Maria Stukoff. 2025. 'Video Games in/as Culture: The Evolving Cultural Significance of Video Games'. *International Journal of the Sociology of Leisure* 8 (3): 339–55.
- Young, Chris J. 2022. 'Scene Tracing: The Replication and Transformation of Global Industry, Movements, and Genres in Local Game Production'. *Lateral* 11 (1). <https://doi.org/10.25158/L11.1.4>.
- Žák, Miroslav. 2022. *Výstava Kompas představí studentskou herní tvorbu*. VisionGame. <https://visiongame.cz/vystava-kompas-predstavi-studentskou-herni-tvorbu/>
- Žák, Miroslav. 2025. *Lektvar 2: Fanart – Festival studentské herní tvorby v Brně se blíží*. VisionGame. <https://visiongame.cz/lektvar-2-fanart-festival-studentske-herni-tvorby-v-brne-se-blizi/>